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<i>Abstract</i>	<p>This report presents key findings for the development of an envisioned digital platform that facilitates collaboration between scientists, higher education institutions (HEIs), and research networks. It is divided into four sections: an analysis of available data sources to integrate existing information efficiently, recommendations on the platform’s scope to enhance collaboration, a schema for user authentication and access control, and intelligent search methods to optimize the discovery of acceleration services. The report emphasizes sustainability for long-term viability and highlights challenges and open issues in platform development. It serves as a foundational guide for further work on the Agora platform.</p>

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Abbreviation list

AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
ACL	Access Control List
AFR	Agora Functional Requirement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANFR	Agora Non-Functional Requirement
API	Application Programming Interface
AS	Acceleration Service
aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
CI/CD	Continuous integration and continuous deployment
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IdP	Identity Provider
IP	Internet Protocol
IT system	Information Technology System
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MVS	Minimum Viable Solution
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OTP	One-Time Password
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SSO	Single Sign-On
VS	Viable Solution
WP	Work Package

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Foreword

This deliverable provides an analysis of key aspects necessary for the development of future digital support and consulting infrastructure to facilitate collaboration between researchers, HEIs, and other networks in the EU. The envisioned platform aims to offer a variety of acceleration services, including tools for discovering funding opportunities and forming research partnerships.

The document is divided into four parts that provide detailed insights into specific components of the platform:

- **Part I – Analysis of available data sources:** The first part analyzes various data sources, primarily information about researchers and institutions from existing databases, to minimize the need for manual data updates in the target platform. Participating universities should contribute data from their systems to provide insights into key stakeholders within the Agora.
- **Part II – Outline of the intended platform scope:** This part focuses on defining the outline of the platform's scope and functionalities. It outlines the information structure and key features to facilitate scientist-to-scientist, HEI-to-HEI, and network-to-network interactions. User requirements from partner institutions are incorporated into the design of the envisioned system that effectively supports the Agora of acceleration services.
- **Part III – Schema of access rights for users in the created system:** This part of the document explains how different stakeholders should be represented within the Agora of acceleration services. A permission system will grant them varying levels of access to services and data processed in the system.
- **Part IV – Idea of intelligent search approach for effective collaboration:** This part focuses on analyzing existing intelligent search methods and solutions for various relevant scenarios, such as matching calls with scientists working on similar topics. The document provides an overview of available intelligent information search methods that can significantly enhance processes like building international research teams. Additionally, legal requirements in the EU have been considered, and a set of recommendations on how an intelligent search engine should be designed is provided.

Together, these components form a comprehensive foundation for the future development of a sustainable and efficient digital ecosystem that will facilitate collaboration and funding acquisition across European HEIs and networks.

Part I: Analysis of available data sources

I.1 Introduction

Part I of the report summarizes the results of the work conducted under Task T3.1 of aUPaEU project, which involved analyzing data from various platforms. These platforms include those with general data, as well as those providing information from individual Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Analyzing these data sources is crucial for understanding the inputs for the Agora of acceleration services. It is expected that the HEIs participating in the Agora will contribute data from their own platforms. However, integrating data sources collected outside HEIs is also assumed to be beneficial in enriching the Agora. This integration aims to eliminate the need for manually collecting data that has already been stored by researchers and institutions in other systems.

The document presents examples of data sources, illustrating different types of data and their distribution methods. The sample data sources, obtained from project partners, demonstrate various approaches to sharing information on researchers, research infrastructure, and other relevant information provided by HEIs. This information may be useful in defining acceleration services in subsequent project tasks (see Part II Outline of the intended platform scope). During the development of this document, it was assumed that data sources would be interpreted in a very broad term, as preliminary analyses indicated significant data duplication at different levels (university, regional, national, international). Consequently, the final selection of data sources for the Agora should not only include those directly providing information about identified acceleration services but also consider general data sources that may implicitly contain relevant information.

I.2 The methodology

The adopted methodology facilitates the identification and classification of data sources that provide information on researchers, HEIs and research conducted at HEIs, including acceleration services for the Agora. A survey was designed to identify and preliminarily classify data sources used at various levels within HEIs: unit/institution, regional, and national/international (see Appendix A). The report is based on the surveys obtained in this manner.

After collecting the surveys, a data analysis was conducted. This analysis allowed for the identification of the general characteristics of the data sources and highlighted key issues from an automation perspective for data delivery to the Agora.

I.2.1 Data sources categories covered in the survey

The selected categories of data sources originate from an approach focused on providing clear descriptions of both researchers and research teams, as their seamless integration within the Agora is necessary. The following data categories were used for this purpose:

I.2.1.1 Data category: People

Researchers. This category includes researcher profiles with identifiers, such as ORCID. Profiles and business cards of researchers are crucial to identify an individual's potential. Expected data sources include a broad range of information, including basic contact details, descriptions of scientific interests, discipline assignments, and publications. This category focuses on systems and databases that enable precise identification and disambiguation of a researcher's identity. Systems that do not objectively verify the validity and reliability of data are still considered acceptable within this category.

Experts. This specific data source provides reliable information about experts, including scientists and domain specialists such as industry professionals. These sources have high data reliability due to their maintenance by external entities and well-defined criteria for evaluating and verifying the data. Expert databases typically demonstrate significantly higher reliability levels than those for scientists. In most cases, they are maintained separately, as expert information is stored in different systems. Examples of collected data include details on experts' fields of specialization, their workplaces, publications, scientific achievements, inventions, and business competencies.

I.2.1.2 Data category: Publications

This category encompasses data sources related to publications, books, articles, conferences, and conference materials that validate expertise in a subject area. These sources apply external evaluation criteria, such as the Impact Factor, to assess the quality of a researcher's output. Both centrally managed publication databases, such as Scopus and Web of Science, and open, community-managed databases, such as arXiv, are relevant for verifying a researcher's output quality. Special attention should be given to publication registries that comply with open science policies

I.2.1.3 Data category: Scientific Projects

The Scientific Projects category includes data sources related to research projects, R&D projects, and science popularization projects. Data sources covering scientific and teaching

activities conducted both within the surveyed organization and by individual researchers were considered. The scope of data includes information on the operational culture, sources of research funding, collaboration between research units and researchers, organizational and legal conditions in a research unit, the unit's experience in implementing specific types of projects, management competencies of leaders and individual team members, R&D projects, datasets, and more.

I.2.1.4 Data category: Patents

In the Patents category, databases that confirm the acquisition of patents and other forms of intellectual property protection were considered. This category encompasses databases documenting the implementations of technological solutions, completed development work, commercialization of research results, and purely commercial projects undertaken in cooperation with the private sector. The data contained in such databases enable the verification of an organization's expertise in commercialization, its capabilities, and the level of support offered by a research unit in this area.

I.2.1.5 Data category: Financing

The Financing category includes data sources on current and upcoming grant calls, research funding institutions, as well as funding methods and priorities. Directories of funding sources were analyzed, considering their classification by funding purpose. This breakdown includes conceptual research, fundamental research, innovation implementation, development, R&D projects, acquisition of small and large research infrastructure, teaching projects, and initiatives aimed at increasing a research unit's capacity.

I.2.1.6 Data category: Research Infrastructure and Services

The Research Infrastructure and Services category includes information on research equipment in HEIs and supporting teams. It is used to present catalogs of research, analytical, consultancy, and expertise services provided by HEI to third parties. Additionally, it includes catalogs of research and support infrastructure, along with the services and support offered by HEIs.

I.2.1.7 Data category: Other

This category includes catalogs of any other data not covered in the previous categories but useful to users when made available in the Agora. For example, it may encompass systems that collect general information on HEIs, policies implemented by them (such as equality or inclusivity policies), various rankings, aggregators of data on HEIs. Additionally, it includes systems with functions similar to those of the Agora.

I.2.2 Regionality of data sources covered in the survey

The analysis of data sources in the survey considers their geographic scope at the following levels:

1. Unit/Institution: This level includes internal HEI systems, covering those aimed at institution staff as well as those providing data externally.
2. Regional: Systems with regional coverage are included in this level. “Regional” refers to data sources that cover more than one HEI but do not encompass an entire country.
3. National/International: This level comprises national and international data catalogs. It includes services provided by HEIs associations and catalogs aggregating information on researchers and HEIs.

I.2.3 Characteristics of surveyed data sources

Due to the wide variety of systems identified in the initial phase of the analysis, it was decided to characterize data sources in a coarse-grained manner. This approach aims to capture fundamental differences between systems without focusing on irrelevant details. It enables the comparison of systems with different purposes, including the data they contain, their content providers, degrees of access authorization, and other relevant aspects.

Data sources have been systematically characterized by listing the following features:

Link/URL	Provides the link to the welcome page of the system or the page that gives information about the system and its scope.
Name	The name of the system, or a short summary in cases where systems do not have proper names, e.g.: a faculty web page.
Purpose/Aim of the System	<p>Understanding the purpose of a surveyed data source is crucial for determining its utility from the perspective of the Agora. The goal behind data collection can influence its quality, scope, and the perspective adopted in its description. Depending on the presentation approach, data may be systematically incomplete or biased. In the further processing of a data source within the Agora, it will be necessary to consider its credibility, reliability, and potential biases.</p> <p><i>Examples include reporting university/region/country-wide levels, periodic evaluation of the researcher/institution unit/entire institution, acquiring partners, obtaining financing at the local/institution/regional/national/European level.</i></p>

<p>Scope of Gathered Data</p>	<p>Determining the scope of collected data is essential for acceleration services. The distinguished data categories include researchers, experts, publications, projects, patents, funding, grants, infrastructure, and services. Information about these types of resources is crucial for fostering collaboration at various levels, such as scientist-to-scientist, HEI-to-HEI, alliance-to-alliance. The description of a data source should encompass all types of data processed in the system, as valuable information often emerges at the intersection of multiple domains or results from interactions between different data sets.</p>
<p>Access</p>	<p>Data accessibility is crucial for automating the process of obtaining data for the Agora. One of the project's outcomes will be a call for changes in local, national, and European data access policies related to the higher education system and research units. In particular, the principles of data sharing (access rights) within Europe and beyond should be clearly defined.</p> <p><i>Examples: open, closed (an internal system that requires consent for access), limited (legal and organizational conditions hindering access to data, and whether the scope of data made available to users is varied by different authorization levels).</i></p>
<p>Data Validity</p>	<p>Data validity is a key parameter affecting the investment plan, as data updating is time- and cost-intensive. When selecting data sources for the Agora, their completeness, reliability, and accuracy must be verified.</p> <p><i>Examples: always up to date/automatic, updated as needed, periodically updated, once a month/year, once created and not updated.</i></p>
<p>API</p>	<p>Ensuring programmatic access to data significantly increases the likelihood of its long-term utilization (sustainability). The absence of API access does not exclude a source from being used in the Agora, but it substantially increases the cost of its utilization, limits its usability over time, or necessitates working with semi-structured or unstructured data.</p> <p><i>Examples: yes/no/no information, link to API, link to documentation describing API, etc.</i></p>

Languages	Languages of user interface, stored data, etc.
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I.3 Analysis of prominent data sources

The following section presents an analysis of prominent data sources focusing on each specific system. These analyses are presented in tabular form to provide a clear and structured overview. The analyzed data sources are grouped in the following subsections, organized according to the data categories and regional classifications as defined in the previous section. This organization facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the scope, relevance, and characteristics of each data source, aiding in the identification of their potential use and integration within the Agora. The tabular analysis includes key aspects such as the source's name, link/URL, purpose, data scope, access level, data validity, API availability, and supported languages, providing a holistic view of each data source's attributes and capabilities.

I.3.1 People

I.3.1.1 Unit/Institution

Name	AMU Research Portal
Link/URL	https://researchportal.amu.edu.pl
Scope of gathered data	Researchers, publications, patents, PhD theses
Purpose/aim of the system	Recording, archiving and disseminating the results of scientific and research activities and documenting the professional achievements of staff and doctoral students at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated by researchers as needed. Publication metadata verified by library staff.
API	Private API. Key is needed for access.

	https://researchportal.amu.edu.pl/api.seam?lang=pl
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Faculty staff web pages of Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science UAM
Link/URL	https://wmi.amu.edu.pl/wydzial/pracownicy
Scope of gathered data	Researchers (address data, scientific profiles, didactic profile), administration (address data)
Purpose/aim of the system	Information about the staff of the faculty of mathematics and computer science, official staff home pages
Access	Open
Data validity	Some data downloaded automatically from other university systems; some data updated by staff as needed
API	Not available
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Uniwersytecki System Obsługi Studiów (USOS, University Study Support System)
Link/URL	https://usosweb.amu.edu.pl (each university has its own instance)
Scope of gathered data	Students, teachers (researchers), studies

Purpose/aim of the system	The system is primarily used to support the study process at Polish universities. It mainly contains information about the classes being held. Additionally, each teacher can create his/her profile and enter his/her e-mail address, website address, telephone number, ORCID number, PBN number and his/her scientific interests.
Access	Depends on individual set privacy settings
Data validity	Updated as needed
API	Some methods and data need API key, https://apps.usos.edu.pl/developers/api/
Languages	Polish, English

Name	UAM expert database
Link/URL	https://amu.edu.pl/dla-mediow/baza-ekspertow
Scope of gathered data	Researchers (research interests, address)
Purpose/aim of the system	The database that facilitates contact between scientists and journalists looking for people to comment on topics taken up by the media.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated by university staff
API	Not available
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Annual reporting system of Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science UAM
Link/URL	https://sprawozdanie.wmi.amu.edu.pl
Scope of gathered data	Researchers (publications, participation in conferences, participation in conference organizing committees, scientific awards, organizational activities for the university, conducted teaching, scientific supervision of bachelor's, master's and doctoral theses, development of an educational program).
Purpose/aim of the system	The system for the preparation of annual reports by scientific employees on scientific and organizational activities
Access	Restricted
Data validity	Reliable data
API	Restricted
Languages	Polish

Name	PoliTo's Research Database (Anagrafe della ricerca): University web page
Link/URL	https://www.polito.it/en/research/scenario/research-database
Scope of gathered data	People, Publications, Projects
Purpose/aim of the system	The research database lists all professors, researchers, Ph.D. students and research personnel working at PoliTo. The research brings up the person's personal page, their publications and projects.
Access	Open

Data validity	Automatic
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

I.3.1.2 Regional

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.1.3 National

Name	SEDN (System Ewaluacji Dorobku Naukowego)
Link/URL	https://sedn.opi.org.pl
Scope of gathered data	Researchers (First name, Last name, PESEL, Discipline, Employee / PhD student Included in the evaluation The basis for being included in the evaluation)
Purpose/aim of the system	System for the evaluation of scientific entities run by the Polish Ministry of Science
Access	Restricted
Data validity	ORCID and PESEL (Polish personal identification number)
API	Available (not public)
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Polska Bibliografia Naukowa (PBN, Polish Scientific Bibliography)
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Link/URL	https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	Employment, researchers, publications
Purpose/aim of the system	The Polish Scientific Bibliography is a portal of the Ministry of Education and Science that gathers information on publications of Polish scientists, publication output of scientific units, and Polish and foreign journals. It is part of the POL-on Integrated Information System for Science and Higher Education. In the middle 2024 the system will probably be replaced by a new integrated system Ludzie Nauki (People of Science).
Access	Open
Data validity	Periodically updated, some records can be manually edited by researchers
API	Yes, https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl/api/
Languages	Polish

Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/nauczyciele-akademiccy-badacze-i-osoby-zaangazowane-w-dzialalnosc-naukowa
Scope of gathered data	Academic teachers, other teaching staff, researchers, and people involved in scientific activities
Purpose/aim of the system	The list contains public data on the staff employed by the institutions of the higher education and science system in Poland, including academic teachers and other persons giving classes, persons conducting scientific activities, and participating therein. The list includes people with active employment. Legal basis: Polish Act of 20 July 2018 on Higher

	Education and Science (Ustawa z dnia 20 lipca 2018 r. - Prawo o szkolnictwie wyższym i nauce).
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated once daily from the POL-on system; rectors and directors of state research units enter the data into the POL-on system. The law mandates that data in the POL-on system must be correct and up to date (under threat of withholding funding from the academic unit by the ministry); still, it does not impose specific deadlines, making it unclear how often data is entered and updated.
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_employee , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

Name	LSI - experts
Link/URL	https://lsi.ncbr.gov.pl/ekspert
Scope of gathered data	Experts and proposal evaluations
Purpose/aim of the system	Grant, project and other funding evaluation. The system is used at all stages of proposal evaluation: reviewer selection, review orders, evaluation criteria, appeals/protests.
Access	Closed, internal system
Data validity	Updated as needed
API	Not available

Languages	Polish, English
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Name	CINECA website: National- Ministry of Education, University and Research website
Link/URL	https://cercauniversita.cineca.it/php5/docenti/cerca.php
Scope of gathered data	Professors, researchers
Purpose/aim of the system	All professors and researchers working at Italian public universities are listed here. The search shows for each person: title, first and last name, gender, university, scientific sector code, department. National level.
Access	Open
Data validity	Automatic
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian

I.3.1.4 International

Name	ORCID
Link/URL	https://orcid.org
Scope of gathered data	Employment, researchers, publications, funding/grants
Purpose/aim of the system	Author identification and public publication/grant record
Access	open

Data validity	Manual update but with useful tools to import data from other sources
API	Yes, https://info.orcid.org/documentation/features/public-api
Languages	English

Name	ResearchGate
Link/URL	https://www.researchgate.net
Scope of gathered data	Employment, researchers, publications, fields of expertise
Purpose/aim of the system	Social media, collaboration, publication sharing
Access	Open
Data validity	Publications updated automatically, other information requires manual update
API	No
Languages	English

Name	Academia
Link/URL	https://amu.academia.edu
Scope of gathered data	Employment, researchers, publications

Purpose/aim of the system	Social media, collaboration, publication sharing
Access	Open
Data validity	Publications updated semiautomatically (requires author confirmation), other information requires manual update
API	No
Languages	English

I.3.2 Publications

I.3.2.1 Unit/Institution

Name	AMUR
Link/URL	https://repozytorium.amu.edu.pl
Scope of gathered data	PhD theses, scientific articles, conference materials, teaching materials, scientific journals, posters, administrative reports
Purpose/aim of the system	AMUR is an institutional repository of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań. The purpose of the repository is to disseminate the scholarly output of staff and to promote research conducted at UAM. The AMUR repository is an archive of its own electronic documents.
Access	Access to metadata is open. Access to the full texts is open by design with an option to restrict it for selected objects to the authorized users only.
Data validity	Doctoral dissertations are archived obligatorily, in accordance with the decree of the Rector of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan.

API	Yes, https://repozytorium.amu.edu.pl/server/api
Languages	Polish, English

Name	KITopen
Link/URL	https://dbkit.bibliothek.kit.edu/login?basis_application=vv_veroeff&basis_role=kunde
Scope of gathered data	Publications, research data/software, Audio/Video, pictures, teaching materials, dissertations
Purpose/aim of the system	Making research output at KIT findable, accessible, interoperable and reuseable. Reporting for Helmholtz
Access	Closed internal system for KIT affiliated students/researchers
Data validity	There is an intellectual validity process run by the "KITopen Team"
API	API's to other systems (Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions...)
Languages	German

Name	PORTO (IRIS)
Link/URL	https://iris.polito.it/?locale=en
Scope of gathered data	Politecnico's publications

Purpose/aim of the system	PORTO is the registry of research conducted by researchers at the Polytechnic University of Turin that draws from IRIS. All Italian universities are connected to IRIS.
Access	Open access
Data validity	Updated by researchers
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

I.3.2.2 Regional

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.2.3 National

Name	SEDN (System Ewaluacji Dorobku Naukowego)
Link/URL	https://sedn.opi.org.pl
Scope of gathered data	Publications (Title, Type, People who have declared this achievement, Instances of participation, Scoring of the source, Scoring of all instances of participation, Scoring of the instances of participation in evaluation)
Purpose/aim of the system	System for the evaluation of scientific entities run by the Polish Ministry of Science
Access	Restricted
Data validity	ORCID and PESEL (Polish personal identification number)
API	Available (not public)
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Polska Bibliografia Naukowa (PBN, Polish Scientific Bibliography)
Link/URL	https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	Employment, researchers, publications
Purpose/aim of the system	The Polish Scientific Bibliography is a portal of the Ministry of Education and Science that gathers information on publications of Polish scientists, publication output of scientific units, and Polish and foreign journals. It is part of the POL-on Integrated Information System for Science and Higher Education. In the middle 2024 the system will probably be replaced by a new integrated system Ludzie Nauki (People of Science).
Access	Open
Data validity	Periodically updated, some records can be manually edited by researchers
API	Yes, https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl/api/
Languages	Polish

Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/publikacje
Scope of gathered data	Publications
Purpose/aim of the system	The list contains public data on publication achievements of the institutions of the higher education and science system in Poland as well as information on scientists' affiliations. The list

	includes publications related to the profiles of institutions in the PBN system.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated once daily from the POL-on system; rectors and directors of state research units enter the data into the POL-on system. The law mandates that data in the POL-on system must be correct and up to date (under threat of withholding funding from the academic unit by the ministry); still, it does not impose specific deadlines, making it unclear how often data is entered and updated.
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_publication , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

I.3.2.4 International

Name	Scopus
Link/URL	https://www.scopus.com
Scope of gathered data	Publications, researchers
Purpose/aim of the system	Abstract and citation database
Access	Limited (part of data open on website)
Data validity	Data systematically provided by journal and book publishers and conference organizers. Author profiles are sometimes created automatically and combine several scientists with similar names into a single scientist. Publications assigned to profiles automatically, but they can also be assigned manually.

API	Yes, no-charge for non-commercial users, and paid for commercial users, https://dev.elsevier.com
Languages	English

Name	Web of Science
Link/URL	https://www.webofscience.com
Scope of gathered data	Publications, researchers
Purpose/aim of the system	Abstract and citation database
Access	Limited
Data validity	Data systematically provided by journal and book publishers and conference organizers. Author profiles are sometimes created automatically and combine several scientists with similar names into a single scientist. Publications assigned to profiles automatically, but they can also be assigned manually.
API	Yes, free and paid – depends on scope and usage, https://developer.clarivate.com/apis
Languages	English

Name	DBLP
Link/URL	https://dblp.org/
Scope of gathered data	Publications, researchers

Purpose/aim of the system	Open bibliographic information on major computer science journals and proceedings.
Access	Open
Data validity	Curated by dblp team.
API	Yes, https://dblp.org/faq/How+to+use+the+dblp+search+API.html
Languages	English

Name	PubMed
Link/URL	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov
Scope of gathered data	Publications
Purpose/aim of the system	Abstract and citation database
Access	Open
Data validity	Data systematically provided by journal and book publishers and conference organizers.
API	Yes, https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/home/develop/api/
Languages	English

Name	arXiv
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Link/URL	https://arxiv.org
Scope of gathered data	Publications
Purpose/aim of the system	Pre-print and post-print archive.
Access	Open
Data validity	Data provided by the authors of the submitted papers. Updated as needed.
API	Yes, https://info.arxiv.org/help/api/index.htm
Languages	English

Name	Zenodo
Link/URL	https://zenodo.org
Scope of gathered data	Publications
Purpose/aim of the system	Open repository of research papers, datasets and software. Every uploaded item is assigned a DOI.
Access	Open with the option of restricting access.
Data validity	Data provided by the authors of the submitted papers. Updated as needed.
API	Yes, https://developers.zenodo.org
Languages	English

Name	Google Scholar
Link/URL	https://scholar.google.com/
Scope of gathered data	Publications, author information
Purpose/aim of the system	To search for scholarly literature
Access	Open
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown (there is no open API for Google Scholar, but some external tools that can be used to access the data from this source, e.g. https://github.com/scholarly-python-package/scholarly)
Languages	English, German, Spanish, French, Catalan, Czech, Danish, Filipino, Croatian, Indonesian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Hungarian, Dutch, Norwegian, Polish, Portuguese, Brazilian Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovenian, Finnish, Swedish, Vietnamese, Turkish, Greek, Bulgarian, Russian, Serbian, Ukrainian, Hebrew, Arabic, Persian, Hindi, Thai, Korean, Simplified Chinese, Taiwanese Mandarin and Japanese

Name	ResearchGate
Link/URL	https://www.researchgate.net
Scope of gathered data	Publications, author information
Purpose/aim of the system	Access over 160 million publication pages and stay up to date with what's happening in your field. Connect with scientific

	community sharing research. Get in-depth stats on who's been reading your work and keep track of your citations.
Access	Need registration. The access of the publications depends on the journal rules.
Data validity	Updated by users
API	Unknown
Languages	English

Name	SSRN
Link/URL	https://www.ssrn.com/index.cfm/en
Scope of gathered data	Publications
Purpose/aim of the system	Repository of 1,293,400 research papers from 1,440,568 researchers in 70 disciplines.
Access	Access to most services via registration
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	English

I.3.3 Scientific projects

I.3.3.1 Unit/institution

Name	Research's results
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Link/URL	https://www.polito.it/ricerca/risultati
Scope of gathered data	PoliTo Projects
Purpose/aim of the system	Searching for all research projects PoliTO is involved in. Divided in categories.
Access	Open
Data validity	Automatic
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

I.3.3.2 Regional

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.3.3 National

Name	NCN project database
Link/URL	https://projekty.ncn.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	<p>The search tool displays basic information on the project, list of research-related publications, equipment purchased under the project, etc. It allows to find other projects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● carried out at the research institution, ● managed by the person concerned, ● submitted to the same call, ● submitted to the same panel, ● similar keywords.
Purpose/aim of the system	Project database is a search tool allowing you to search for information on NCN-funded research projects, i.e. projects for which a funding agreement has already been concluded by the Applicant and the National Science Centre, therefore it does not

	include projects for which a funding agreement has not been concluded even if they have been recommended for funding.
Access	Open
Data validity	Created when application is submitted and updated when project is finished.
API	Not available
Languages	Polish, English; all data available in both languages.

Name	SEDN (System Ewaluacji Dorobku Naukowego)
Link/URL	https://sedn.opi.org.pl
Scope of gathered data	Achievements (Year, ID, Title, Type of Scientific projects, Score, Meets the evaluation conditions)
Purpose/aim of the system	System for the evaluation of scientific entities run by the Polish Ministry of Science
Access	Restricted
Data validity	ORCID and PESEL (Polish personal identification number)
API	Available (not public)
Languages	Polish, English

Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
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Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/projekty
Scope of gathered data	Projects
Purpose/aim of the system	The list contains public data on the projects implemented by the institutions of the higher education and science system in Poland, including research and development projects, popularization of science.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated once daily from the POL-on system; rectors and directors of state research units enter the data into the POL-on system. The law mandates that data in the POL-on system must be correct and up to date (under threat of withholding funding from the academic unit by the ministry); still, it does not impose specific deadlines, making it unclear how often data is entered and updated.
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_project , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

Name	LSI – proposal generator
Link/URL	https://lsi.ncbr.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	Proposals
Purpose/aim of the system	Funding proposal submission
Access	Closed, internal system

Data validity	Updated as needed
API	Not available
Languages	Polish, English

Name	PRIN
Link/URL	https://prin.mur.gov.it
Scope of gathered data	Scientific projects funded at National level
Purpose/aim of the system	Portal of the PRIN research calls of the Directorate-General for Research of the MIUR (Italian Ministry of University and Research)
Access	Open Access with some sections limited to researchers
Data validity	Updated as needed
API	No information
Languages	Italian

I.3.3.4 International

Name	CORDIS
Link/URL	https://cordis.europa.eu/search?q=(%2Farticle%2Frelations%2Fcategories%2Fcollection%2Fcode%3D%27brief%27%20OR%20(%2Fresult%2Frelations%2Fcategories%2Fcollection%2Fcode%3D%27deliverable%27%2C%27publication%27%20OR%20contenttype%3D%27project%27))%20AND%20language%3D%27en%27&p=1&num=10&srt=/article/contentUpdateDate:decreasing

Scope of gathered data	Projects, topics, and publications funded by the EU's research programs
Purpose/aim of the system	Comprehensive information about EU Research & Development projects
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated as needed
API	Yes, https://cordis.europa.eu/api/dataextractions/getExtraction
Languages	English, German, Spanish, French, Italian, Polish

I.3.4 Patents

I.3.4.1 Unit/Institution

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.4.2 Regional

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.4.3 National

Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/projekty
Scope of gathered data	Patents and protected rights
Purpose/aim of the system	The list contains public data on the patents and protected rights of the institutions of the higher education and science system in

	Poland, including invention patents, utility model protected rights, and exclusive rights of growers to plant varieties.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated once daily from the POL-on system; rectors and directors of state research units enter the data into the POL-on system. The law mandates that data in the POL-on system must be correct and up to date (under threat of withholding funding from the academic unit by the ministry); still, it does not impose specific deadlines, making it unclear how often data is entered and updated.
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_product , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

Name	National patent office database
Link/URL	https://it.espacenet.com/?locale=it_IT
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	Patent Search In cooperation with the European Patent Office
Access	Open
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian

Name	Ufficio Italiano Brevetti e Marchi (Italian Patent and Trademark Office)
Link/URL	https://uibm.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/
Scope of gathered data	Patents, trademarks
Purpose/aim of the system	<p>Database: DGTPI UIBM.</p> <p>Conduct searches on trademarks, inventions, utility models, and other Industrial Property titles.</p> <p>Obtain statistics and information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the industrial property system, • counterfeiting and anti-counterfeiting activities. <p>Consult official Bulletins.</p>
Access	Open
Data validity	Not recent
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian

I.3.4.4 International

Name	Questel patent search software
Link/URL	https://www.questel.com/
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	According to a representative of the patent office, they mainly use Questel as a data source for patent registrations. KIT has an internal database for its own patents, which is closed in terms of

	access. The patent office uses Questel for accessing national and international patent databases, as it provides anonymized access to those.
Access	Unknown
Data validity	Automatic updates, frequent updates
API	Unknown
Languages	English, German, Japanese, Chinese

Name	EPO - Espacenet
Link/URL	https://www.epo.org/en/searching-for-patents https://worldwide.espacenet.com
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search and find patent publications. • Machine-translate patent documents. • Track the progress of emerging technologies. • Find solutions to technical problems. • See what your competitors are developing.
Access	Espacenet is available free of charge, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.
Data validity	Updated daily
API	Yes, https://data.epo.org/linked-data/documentation/api-overview.html
Languages	English

Name	WIPO
Link/URL	https://patentscope.wipo.int/search/en/search.jsf
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	The PATENTSCOPE database provides access to international Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) applications in full text format on the day of publication, as well as to patent documents of participating national and regional patent offices.
Access	Open
Data validity	International publication usually occurs on the first Thursday following the expiration of 18 months from the priority date, which is the earliest potential date for international publication. (Exceptions may occur if the International Bureau is closed on Thursday, meaning publication occurs on a different day, or if the applicant requests early publication). Changes to publication dates are always announced in advance in the PCT Newsletter.
API	Yes, https://wipopearl.wipo.int/en/api
Languages	English, French, Arabic, Chinese, Russian, Spanish

Name	PATSTAT - EPO
Link/URL	https://data.epo.org/expert-services/index.html
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	PATSTAT contains bibliographical and legal event patent data from leading industrialized and developing countries. This is extracted from the EPO's databases and is either provided as bulk data or can be consulted online.

Access	<p>Some contents are not accessible, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • some of the EPO's online services and advanced tools linked from this website, • PDFs and other downloads linked from this website, • some images which may not have a text alternative, or where the text may not describe the image accurately.
Data validity	Publication takes place every Wednesday, at 14.00 hrs CET.
API	Yes, https://data.epo.org/linked-data/documentation/api-overview.html
Languages	English

Name	KNOWLEDGE SHARE
Link/URL	https://www.knowledge-share.eu/en/patent/
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	Meeting point for Italian companies with the expertise developed by the Italian universities and Research Centers, which can become practical applications. It is a portal created to make available, in a clear and understandable way, information related to patents and technologies that represent the excellence of the scientific know-how of the Italian Universities and Research Centers, in order to share the news and information about the Universities' third mission, the technology transfer, and to bring together research groups and companies to enhance the results.
Access	Access is open to Italian and foreign SMEs and takes place after registration. With the login, they have access to the patents and technologies' information and can contact the Universities owner of those patents. Furthermore, they could receive a newsletter and be approached by the Universities in order to put forward possible partnerships.

Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

Name	Orbis Intellectual Property (database Bureau van Dijk)
Link/URL	https://bib.kuleuven.be/english/ebib/collection/data/databases/orbisip
Scope of gathered data	Patents
Purpose/aim of the system	Orbis IP contains global patent data on 115 million patents linked to 300 million companies, including patent transaction data, patent valuations, patent ownership timelines, and integrated company structure information.
Access	Closed. Access provided to Polito students and researchers.
Data validity	Unknown
API	Yes, https://www.bvdinfo.com/en-gb/our-products/data/international/orbis
Languages	Multilingual

I.3.5 Financing

I.3.5.1 Unit/Institution

Name	Internal funding and initiatives (POLITO)
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Link/URL	https://www.polito.it/en/research/research-funding/internal-research-funding-and-initiatives
Scope of gathered data	Funding opportunities
Purpose/aim of the system	Politecnico di Torino provides funding and promotes initiatives aimed at encouraging the quality of scientific production, design in fundamental and collaborative research, participation in projects of excellence, multidisciplinary and internationalization of research. Subsections: 'Visiting Professor' call, Attraction and retention of excellent professors through "Starting Grant", Call for Proof of Concept projects, Apprenticeships for research activities.
Access	Partially closed. Only POLITO accounts can log in on the section "Visiting Professor' call"
Data validity	Updated as needed
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian and English

I.3.5.2 Regional

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.5.3 National

Name	NCN Funding Stream Support System (OSF)
Link/URL	https://osf.opi.org.pl
Scope of gathered data	Research grant applications (mainly basic research) and project reports. The system contains applicant data including publications, previous projects, and other activities. Project reports contain information about publications and conferences.

	Detailed system description (in Polish): https://opi.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/OSF-ebook.pdf
Purpose/aim of the system	A system dedicated to Polish scientists and entrepreneurs. It is used to register and handle applications for financing R&D projects and studies with the funds provided by the Ministry of Education and Science, the National Science Centre, and the National Centre for Research and Development.
Access	Limited, regular user may access only own applications; no data is available publicly
Data validity	Updated and the end of each project with the information about project outcomes.
API	No API, planned to implement as optional feature
Languages	Polish, English; applications are written mainly in Polish

Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/projekty
Scope of gathered data	Patents and protected rights
Purpose/aim of the system	The list contains public data on the patents and protected rights of the institutions of the higher education and science system in Poland, including invention patents, utility model protected rights, and exclusive rights of growers to plant varieties.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated once daily from the POL-on system; rectors and directors of state research units enter the data into the POL-on

	system. The law mandates that data in the POL-on system must be correct and up to date (under threat of withholding funding from the academic unit by the ministry); still, it does not impose specific deadlines, making it unclear how often data is entered and updated.
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_product , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

Name	L'Anagrafe nazionale delle ricerche (ANR) (The National Register of Searches)
Link/URL	https://www.anagrafenazionalericerche.mur.gov.it/
Scope of gathered data	Funding
Purpose/aim of the system	In order to have access to public funding, all entities (administrations, public and private institutions and bodies, companies) carrying out research activities must be registered with the ANR. In addition, administrations and funding bodies are obliged to notify the ANR of funding granted for research activities.
Access	Partially closed
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian

I.3.5.4 International

Name	Funding & tender opportunities
Link/URL	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home
Scope of gathered data	Calls for proposals and tenders
Purpose/aim of the system	Funding & Tenders Opportunities is a portal created by the European Commission, through which calls for proposals are published and funding applications are submitted. It serves as an electronic administration platform for projects co-funded by the European Union.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated continuously
API	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/apis
Languages	All EU official languages

I.3.6 Research infrastructure and services

I.3.6.1 Unit/Institution

Name	SEZA/CADISAD – System Zarządzania Aparaturą UAM (Research equipment management system AMU)
Link/URL	https://seza.amu.edu.pl
Scope of gathered data	Infrastructure, services

Purpose/aim of the system	The system collects AMU infrastructure devices on a single platform and allows electronic ordering of analyses for all AMU employees and AMU collaborating environment.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated manually as needed
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

Name	MyPoli
Link/URL	https://www.swas.polito.it/services/sisinfo/
Scope of gathered data	Services for researchers, professors, and administrative staff
Purpose/aim of the system	<p>The MyPoli Online Services provide access to a range of services and information for the University's staff.</p> <p>Some are public services (accessible to all staff) while others are services accessible to a restricted user base and are governed by specific enabling policies.</p> <p>Services are accessed through the individual MyPoli portal.</p> <p>It Includes Documentation about European, Regional and National Funding Service.</p> <p>It includes Funded Research Project Management Support Service,</p>
Access	Data are made available to varying degrees to users (all belonging to the university- PoliTo accounts) with different types of authorizations

Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian

Name	Portale della didattica (Personal Education Portal)
Link/URL	https://didattica.polito.it/
Scope of gathered data	Services for researchers, professors and students
Purpose/aim of the system	Information about own courses, Available teaching materials, E-learning courses open to the University community, Remote signature service, Contracts for supplementary teaching, Tools for interacting with students in the classroom.
Access	Only POLITO accounts. Data are made available to varying degrees to users with different authorizations.
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian and English

Name	Research labs website
Link/URL	https://didattica.polito.it/laboratori.html https://didattica.polito.it/laboratori_en.html
Scope of gathered data	Links

Purpose/aim of the system	The page provides links to the private pages of each university laboratory
Access	Some pages are open access, for other the access is limited to POLITO accounts
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

Name	Servizi amministrazione
Link/URL	https://www.polito.it/ateneo/chi-siamo/amministrazione
Scope of gathered data	Administration's structure: departments, offices, hubs, departmental districts
Purpose/aim of the system	Transparency and access to information about the administration
Access	Open
Data validity	Up to date
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

Name	Polito Services
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Link/URL	https://www.polito.it/impatto-sociale/biblioteche-di-ateneo/servizi
Scope of gathered data	Link of services for researchers
Purpose/aim of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to libraries. • Lending and consultation. • DigProxy: access to electronic resources from outside the University. • Purchase proposals. • Documentation.
Access	Open access
Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian and English (new website, so they are currently translating in English; there was the English page with the old website)

I.3.6.2 Regional

Name	Nauka dla Biznesu (Science for Business)
Link/URL	http://naukadlabiznesu.pl
Scope of gathered data	Services, R&D units (also universities)
Purpose/aim of the system	Improving the management of scientific and technological development in Silesia region (Poland) and development of activities aimed at initiating and strengthening cooperation of business and R&D units and business environment institutions for the development of smart specializations through the identification of business areas/topics where joint action and implementation of new innovative business ideas would be possible.
Access	Open

Data validity	Manually updated, probably only through the scope of the project
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

Name	PPNT – Poznański Park Naukowo-Technologiczny (Poznan Science and Technology Park)
Link/URL	https://ppnt.poznan.pl/en
Scope of gathered data	Infrastructure, services
Purpose/aim of the system	Textual (sometimes general, but sometimes more specific) description of infrastructure and services that can be used by researchers and business.
Access	Open
Data validity	Manually updated as needed
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

I.3.6.3 National

Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/inwestycje
Scope of gathered data	Investments made by Polish higher education and science institutions, including scientific and research equipment and IT infrastructure investments exceeding 500,000 PLN (approx.

	110,000 EUR), also co-funded by foreign investors. The data in the RAD-on system are part of the POL-on system (Integrated Information System for Higher Education and Science).
Purpose/aim of the system	To fulfill the statutory duty owed to the Minister of Science and Higher Education, such as implementing the state's science policy and supervising the higher education and science system. Legal basis: Polish Act of 20 July 2018 on Higher Education and Science (Ustawa z dnia 20 lipca 2018 r. - Prawo o szkolnictwie wyższym i nauce; art. 342, ust. 4; art. 346, ust. 1, pkt. 13-14).
Access	Open
Data validity	<p>Updated once daily from the POL-on system; rectors and directors of state research units enter the data into the POL-on system. The law mandates that data in the POL-on system must be correct and up to date (under threat of withholding funding from the academic unit by the ministry); still, it does not impose specific deadlines, making it unclear how often data is entered and updated.</p> <p>The description of infrastructure data can be either general or detailed. For example, an HPC cluster can be referred to as a "computing cluster" or be specified with explicit GPU card models.</p> <p>The indexing used in the search engine mechanism means that it can be challenging to find specific data; for example, a variation of the word "cluster" in Polish, i.e., "klaster" and "klastra" give different results, and the root of the word "klast" does not return results at all.</p>
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_investment , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

Name	Polska Mapa Infrastruktury Badawczej (Polish Research Infrastructure Map)
Link/URL	https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja-i-nauka/polska-mapa-infrastruktury-badawczej https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja-i-nauka/polska-mapa-infrastruktury-badawczej-70-najlepszych-infrastruktur-w-jednej-broszurze
Scope of gathered data	Infrastructure
Purpose/aim of the system	To select critical Polish infrastructure that needs extra central funding from the national budget. The map (list) is created to fulfill law regulations.
Access	Open
Data validity	Updated once per few years
API	No, only PDFs with general tabular data and descriptive brochure
Languages	Tabular data: Polish Brochure: English

Name	PCSS – Poznańskie Centrum Superkomputerowo-Sieciowe (PSNC – Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center)
Link/URL	https://www.psnc.pl
Scope of gathered data	Infrastructure, services

Purpose/aim of the system	Textual (sometimes general, but sometimes more specific) description of infrastructure and services that can be used by researchers and business.
Access	Open
Data validity	Manually updated as needed
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

I.3.6.4 International

Data sources were not identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.7 Other

I.3.7.1 Unit/Institution

Name	Pico
Link/URL	https://pico.polito.it/discovery/search?vid=39PTO_INST:VU&lang=en
Scope of gathered data	Electronic resources
Purpose/aim of the system	Pico lets you search all at once electronic resources, both for pay and for free ones, printed publications owned by the Politecnico libraries, the institutional repository "PORTO" of publications by the university researchers, and lets you reach directly the full text, when it is available. It lets you select a subset of the searched resources (printed material only, electronic resources only...)
Access	You need POLITO account

Data validity	Unknown
API	Unknown
Languages	Italian, English

I.3.7.2 Regional

No data sources were identified at this regionalization level.

I.3.7.3 National

Name	NCBiR PartFinder
Link/URL	https://partfinder.ncbr.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	R&D research partnership announcements
Purpose/aim of the system	Targeted to research groups searching for international partnership opportunities. Started in mid-2022. Contains 106 announcements as of 03.11.2023. System processes: project description, project goal, project leader and list of regional/national/EU Programme calls.
Access	Open: list of announcements;
Data validity	Once created and not updated, data is not verified, every logged in user may add a new announcement.
API	No API, scrapable data
Languages	English

Name	Platforma "Innowacje" ("Innovations" hub)
Link/URL	https://innowacje.opi.org.pl
Scope of gathered data	Links to external portals
Purpose/aim of the system	An information portal that supports business innovation (publications, research apparatus, experts, project funding, scientific projects, reports and analyses, patents and rights of protection, online courses); funded by the Polish Ministry of Education and Science.
Access	Open
Data validity	Manually updated as needed
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Sieć POL-on – zintegrowany system informacji o nauce polskiej i szkolnictwie wyższym (POL-on hub – integrated system of information on Polish science and higher education)
Link/URL	https://polon.nauka.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	Website provides links to external portals (note that POL-on is some kind of a data meta-system)
Purpose/aim of the system	POL-on was created and is maintained by the National Information Processing Institute, which gathers information on Polish science and makes it available to the public; conducts research on the activity of scientific institutions, higher education units, and organizations that support the transfer of technology; and creates comprehensive IT systems that

	contribute to the development of science and higher education.; funded by the Polish Ministry of Education and Science.
Access	Open
Data validity	Manually updated as needed
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Ludzie Nauki (Academics)
Link/URL	https://ludzie-nauki.edukacja.gov.pl
Scope of gathered data	N/A
Purpose/aim of the system	The system that will extend RAD-on functionalities and provide e-services for business (middle 2024).
Access	Open
Data validity	The same as in POL-on
API	N/A
Languages	Polish

Name	Nauka Polska (Polish Science)
Link/URL	https://nauka-polska.pl

Scope of gathered data	Researchers, institutions, publications, conferences
Purpose/aim of the system	The oldest database maintained by Polish National Information Processing Institute since 1990 and available free online since 1999. Data are used to analyze Polish research activity as well as they support policymakers in creating science policies in Poland.
Access	Open
Data validity	Manually updated as needed
API	No
Languages	Polish, English

Name	Krajowy Punkt Kontaktowy Programów Badawczych UE. Narodowe Centrum Badań i Rozwoju (National Contact Point for EU Research Programs. National Center for Research and Development)
Link/URL	https://www.kpk.gov.pl/poszukiwanie-partnerow/poszukiwanie-partnerow-2
Scope of gathered data	List of external websites
Purpose/aim of the system	This site is intended to bring together external systems where you can find partners for EU projects (e.g. see above-mentioned NCBiR PartFinder).
Access	Open
Data validity	Updates as needed
API	No

Languages	Polish; external websites in English
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Name	RAD-on – source of reports, analyses, and data on higher education and science in Poland.
Link/URL	https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/instytucje-systemu-szkolnictwa-wyzszego-i-nauki https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/dane/ewidencja-uczelniniepublicznych
Scope of gathered data	Higher education and science institutions and register of nonpublic higher education institutions, and non-public universities entered in the register of non-public universities
Purpose/aim of the system	The list contains public data on the entities of the higher education and science system in Poland, including public and non-public higher education institutions, church higher education institutions, and scientific institutions.
Access	Open
Data validity	The data come from the POL-on integrated system of information on science and higher education and are updated once a day (at night) - the list reflects the state of the POL-on data from the previous day.
API	Yes, https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_institution and https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/api/katalog-udostepniania-danych/dane-polon/polon/reports_nonpublic_university , public API.
Languages	Data: Polish. Interface: Polish, English.

h3>I.3.7.4 International

Name	GoTriple
Link/URL	https://gotriple.eu
Scope of gathered data	Researchers, projects, documents, publications
Purpose/aim of the system	<p>A discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities (SSH), funded by European Commission. It provides one of the central access points for discovering and reusing research artefacts that are relevant to the wide variety of disciplines under the umbrella domain of SSH: Publications and research data, project descriptions and researcher profiles are automatically imported from aggregators and source providers.</p> <p>The platform enables users to discover and reuse open scholarly SSH, which are currently scattered across local and discipline-specific repositories; find and connect with other researchers and projects across disciplinary, cultural and language boundaries; make use of innovative tools and services to support research, visualization of search results, web annotation, personalized recommendations and social networking; explore new ways of funding research such as crowdfunding.</p>
Access	Open
Data validity	Depends on validity of external data sources
API	Yes, https://api.gotriple.eu , public API
Languages	Croatian, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Spanish

Name	Research data repositories, e.g., RADAR4KIT
Link/URL	https://www.re3data.org/search?query=ROR%3A04t3en479 https://www.bibliothek.kit.edu/radar.php
Scope of gathered data	Research data sets (plus metadata, e.g. researchers, projects, publications)
Purpose/aim of the system	KIT hosts several institutional repositories, such as KITOpen, Radar4KIT, and others. With this link (https://www.re3data.org/search?query=ROR%3A04t3en479) you can also find information on APIs, access, etc., which vary from repository to repository.
Access	Depends on repository and data set.
Data validity	Depends; at least periodically updated.
API	Depends on repository
Languages	English, German

I.4 Discussion

As a result of analyzing prominent data sources, certain characteristics have been identified, enhancing our understanding of the data inputs required for the Agora. This section presents conclusions from three perspectives: the qualitative analysis of the data sources analyzed, the identification of general issues, and open questions relevant to the implementation of other Work Packages (WPs). The discussion may continue during the work on defining acceleration services and selecting data sources that identify and provide information about these services.

I.4.1 Qualitative analysis of data sources features

This qualitative analysis provides a comprehensive summary of the features of the surveyed data sources, offering broader insight into the data that can serve as inputs for acceleration services on the Agora platform.

I.4.1.1 Scope of the gathered data

Systems are functionally heterogeneous, processing various data types simultaneously. This heterogeneity creates uncertainty among researchers regarding where to store specific types of data (e.g. information about people, projects, publications), leading to data fragmentation, consistency issues, and duplication. This is often a result of national policies that inconsistently define data storage locations. For example, the use of the ORCID system in Poland is inconsistent; while it is legally required only for identification, it is not widely adopted for storing publication information.

I.4.1.2 Purpose/aim of the System

Systems designed for mandatory data collection as required by laws and regulations – such as those used by HEIs to submit periodic reports on their activities – often contain low-quality, quickly outdated data. Despite this, such systems tend to have a high degree of completeness due to the obligatory nature of data collection.

I.4.1.3 Access

The more localized a database is, the more limited access to its data becomes. This limitation is not an oversight but rather reflects a broader phenomenon. To balance open science requirements with the interests of individuals, HEIs, countries, and the European Union, access rights must be defined at various levels of regionalization. As discussed in Part III, however, access rights extend beyond mere data and source access to encompass broader issues— including ethical, legal, and contextual dimensions of information sharing. This also involves policies for accessing information about scientists and their research outside Europe.

I.4.1.4 Data Validity

It is important to note that many systems are developed concurrently to process similar ranges of data. Furthermore, new systems often replace older ones without ensuring backward compatibility or the possibility of data migration. An example is the Polish PBN system, which changes frequently, leading researchers to question the value of creating a profile in a transient system. European-level legislation may be needed to recommend a uniform system for storing data across different categories. Additionally, the validity of data is often overlooked by researchers and institutions due to the lack of systematic methods for maintaining data quality across various databases.

I.4.1.5 API

It has been observed that newer IT systems are more likely to offer API access, owing to the popularization of the JSON data format and REST web interface architecture. This standardization positively impacts the ability to utilize data from various sources. However,

there is currently no uniform schema for data describing researchers, publications, projects, and other related information. This highlights the necessity for methods capable of processing unstructured or semi-structured data. Additionally, the mere existence of an API does not guarantee automated data access. Issues with closed API access lead to limited data availability, automation challenges, or the need for specific authorizations, contracts, or collaborations.

I.4.1.6 Languages

In addition to national languages, system interfaces are often available in English. However, data in systems up to the national level are typically described in the respective national language. Technological advances, particularly in automatic translation and Large Language Models (LLMs), are likely to significantly mitigate this issue.

I.4.2 General problems with development and maintenance of sustainable data sources

Problems with uniquely identifying a researcher. Many research units attempt to use ORCID as an identifier for their employees in their systems, and it's common to see a researcher's ORCID listed in scientific papers alongside their name and e-mail address. However, the ORCID identifier is not widely adopted by all commercial platforms (e.g., Google Scholar), where it competes with alternative solutions. As a result, relying on ORCID as the sole researcher identifier limits the usability of available databases.

Limited scope of analysis due to restricted data access and a lack of knowledgeable people in the overall systems and available data. Knowledge of specialized systems beneficial for scientific work is not widespread, and only some researchers are familiar with them. Additionally, there is limited understanding among researchers regarding the interconnections between systems and the data they store. Awareness of which systems are up to date and where to categorize specific types of data is not as common as it should be.

Diversity of database systems. There is significant variation in systems and databases across different countries and scientific disciplines (e.g., MathSciNet for mathematics, PubMed for medicine). This diversity has led to a multitude of systems, each requiring a separate programming solution for data access. As a result, this fragmentation creates challenges in aggregating and analyzing data across different sources.

Lack of awareness of the need for data storage systems. Not all scientific disciplines recognize the importance of databases. Disciplines that typically do not involve large teams or extensive projects may not see the necessity of entering and updating data in such systems.

I.4.3 Open issues and tasks to consider in further work on WPs

The role of data sources connected to the Agora must be evaluated from various perspectives, taking into account multiple needs and constraints. This issue should be explored in detail while working on other WPs that focus on defining and delivering acceleration services through the Agora.

I.4.3.1 WP2 Analysis & Methodology towards R&I acceleration services

1. There is a need to ensure that in defining acceleration services, attention is paid to whether there are data sources capable of identifying offered services and whether these sources can effectively provide information on the scope of the services, access rules, restrictions, data validity, and other relevant aspects.
2. It is recommended to consider whether data sources as such should also be counted as acceleration services.

I.4.3.2 WP3 Investment and Sustainability Plan

1. The results of the analysis of data sources have been incorporated into the work on *Part II: Outline of the intended platform scope*, *Part II: Schema of access rights for users in created system* and *Part IV: Idea of an intelligent search approach for effective collaboration*.
2. A more comprehensive analysis is needed on a larger set of available systems, as the current analysis has not sufficiently identified the role and nature of systems with regional coverage.
3. The analysis suggests that the Agora can be fed with data in an automated manner, using both structured and unstructured data sources. Part IV discusses that problem in terms of sustainability and role played by the information manually fed into the Agora. In particular, what is its reliability in relation to external and automatically acquired data sources.

I.4.3.3 WP4 Coaching Service and Guidance for networks of HEIs

The implementation of acceleration services, and open R&I requires appropriate methods for publishing data on available and offered services. When creating business processes and new policies, they should take into account the need to publish information about services in a way that allows its continuous use as a sustainable data source for the Agora.

I.4.3.4 WP5 Implementation of Digital Transition

1. The technical architecture of the Agora should facilitate the integration of external data sources for efficient searching using an intelligent search engine. It is crucial to determine whether the Agora will retrieve and share data from the intelligent search engine connected to external data sources, whether the search engine will use data

collected on the Agora for efficient searches, or whether a hybrid (two-way) architecture should be adopted.

2. It needs to be decided whether data from external data sources, i.e. outside the Agora should appear in the search engine or only information stored on the Agora should be considered.

I.5 Appendix A

The following appendix contains a survey template, which is a form to help a scientific unit identify the data sources used, according to the methodology adopted in the analysis.

Task 3.1 Data Sources Survey

A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities through Digital Services (aUPaEU)

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0		An initial version of the survey

aUPaEU partner:

Contact information to the person responsible for filling the survey:

Instruction

Dear partners, please complete the tables (as many as you want) below as a part of Task 3.1, describing data sources for the Agora platform. Please focus on the data sources in the following areas:

1. People:
 - a. Researchers (scientist profiles with identifiers, e.g., ORCID)
 - b. Experts (in what field they specialize, where they work, what they have published and what scientific achievements they have, what inventions they created, what business competencies they have)
2. Publications (books, articles, conferences, and conference materials)
3. Scientific projects (research projects, R&D projects, science popularization projects)
4. Patents
5. Financing (granting institutions, grant calls)
6. Research infrastructure and services (information about research equipment in units, supporting staff)

To obtain complete information, please indicate the IT systems (used at your institution and/or other systems you know) at such levels:

1. unit/institution,
2. regional,
3. national/European.

Please indicate in this survey the nonexistence of a particular data source by leaving the table empty.

Use the following legend to describe a data source system in a tabular form:

Name	Name and a short summary of the system, for example: a faculty web page.
Link/URL	Link to system welcome page, information about the system, and its scope.
Scope of gathered data	For example: researchers, experts, publications, projects, patents, funding, grants, infrastructure, or services.
Purpose/aim of the system	For example: reporting university/region/country-wide, periodic evaluation of the researcher/institution unit/entire institution, acquiring partners, obtaining financing at the local/institution/regional/national/European level.
Access	For example: open, closed (internal system – requires consent for access), limited – available to whom and to what extent, legal and organizational conditions hindering access to data, and whether data are made available to varying degrees to users with different authorizations.
Data validity	For example: always up to date/automatic, updated as needed, periodically updated, once a month/year, once created and not updated.
API	Yes/no/no information, link to API, link to documentation describing API, is API public?
Languages	User interface languages and stored data languages.

Data sources

People

Name	
Link/URL	

Scope of gathered data	
Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	
API	
Languages	

...

Publications

Name	
Link/URL	
Scope of gathered data	
Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	
API	
Languages	

...

Scientific projects

Name	
Link/URL	
Scope of gathered data	
Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	
API	
Languages	

...

Patents

Name	
Link/URL	
Scope of gathered data	
Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	

API	
Languages	
...	
Financing	
Name	
Link/URL	
Scope of gathered data	
Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	
API	
Languages	
...	
Research infrastructure and services	
Name	
Link/URL	
Scope of gathered data	

Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	
API	
Languages	

...

Other relevant data sources

Name	
Link/URL	
Scope of gathered data	
Purpose/aim of the system	
Access	
Data validity	
API	
Languages	

...

Part II: Outline of the intended platform scope

II.1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to collect, analyze, and define the high-level requirements and features of the Agora platform as software. It focuses on the capabilities required by stakeholders and target users, explaining the rationale behind these needs. Details on how the Agora platform meets these requirements through acceleration services are provided in the use-case and supplementary specifications.

The document outlines the logical architecture of the Agora platform, focusing on architectural components that impact its sustainability. In the context of the IT system supporting Agora, 'sustainability' refers to a set of practices and strategies aimed at ensuring long-term efficiency, flexibility, and minimizing negative environmental impact. Specifically, this involves designing for durability—building an IT system that is easy to maintain, update, and scale. This approach extends its usefulness, reduces the need for frequent software replacement, and ensures optimal hardware utilization

The main premise of the recommended architecture for the Agora IT system, ensuring sustainability, is an approach where the IT system consists of a limited and well-defined set of **core modules** and is designed to integrate IT modules responsible for handling business processes related to Acceleration Services (the so-called **Acceleration Services modules**). This approach enables the implementation of new Acceleration Services on the Agora in a standardized technical pattern, reduces the costs of implementing and maintaining Acceleration Services, and facilitates technical updates and replacements when necessary. An important assumption of the proposed architecture is to consider, during the construction of software modules responsible for managing Acceleration Services, the different levels of responsibility the Agora has for each Acceleration Service (Acceleration Services integration level perspective), the system of permissions to Agora's functionalities ensuring the handling of the Acceleration Service (access rights), and the users and stakeholders of Agora described in a general manner (personas).

II.1.1 Scope of the document

The document "Outline of the Intended Platform Scope" presents recommendations for the technical architecture of the IT system called Agora of Acceleration Services, which is being developed as part of the aUPaEU project. It serves as a reference point for the construction of

the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) within the project, i.e., a prototype of the target system that will be used to test the proposed model of delivering Acceleration Services to higher education institutions.

Additionally, this document is intended to serve as a reference for any other initiative aiming to integrate Acceleration Services from various sources, directed at different audiences, with the overarching goal of coherently fostering the development of higher education institutions through such a solution.

II.1.2 Purpose

The purpose of the *Outline of the intended platform scope* document is to present the recommended technical architecture of the Agora of Acceleration Services, with a particular focus on its sustainability. The document was created as part of the aUPaEU project, in which a consortium of partners is working to define how Acceleration Services contribute to the development to higher education institutions, how these services should be made available to users through the Agora IT system, and how these services should be implemented at universities to drive meaningful change and growth.

Another key objective of the project is to develop a Minimum Viable Solution (MVS)—a prototype IT system implementing selected Acceleration Services—and to test this solution with representatives of the target groups. Throughout the process, the sustainability of the platform will be a central consideration, ensuring that the developed solution continues to support university growth even after the completion of the aUPaEU project.

II.2 Positioning

Agora of Acceleration Services is an IT system designed to provide users with unique services that are not directly offered by any other existing solution. The platform's key feature, as outlined in this document, is its ability to integrate Acceleration Services of various types and forms. By utilizing carefully selected and tested tools, the platform ensures that the acceleration process meets the expectations of both service providers and consumers.

The system, developed based on the recommendations in this document, will enable the delivery of Acceleration Services as needed, facilitate their exchange when necessary, and support their maintenance within an optimal financial model.

The following table presents a product position statement that conveys the purpose of the platform and highlights the project's significance for all relevant stakeholders:

For	researchers and university personnel, business representatives, officials from EU, national, and local administrations, citizens
Who	are interested in the development of universities by harnessing their own potential, achieving synergistic growth through collaboration with other universities, including those united in alliances, fostering and maintaining cooperation between universities and businesses, and sustaining relationships between universities and European, national, and local authorities, as well as citizens
The Agora	is a platform offering Acceleration Services
That	using IT tools integrated within Agora to ensure the delivery of Acceleration Services with appropriate functionalities, provide necessary data, and guarantee a permissions system that grants access to these services.
Unlike	other systems, it offers services that operate on integrated data from various sources, provides access to data that is unavailable in other systems due to lack of access control mechanisms ensuring compliance and enables efficient retrieval for necessary information through an integrated search engine.
Our product	thanks to its flexible architecture, will allow the addition and removal of Acceleration Services as needed and enable the design of services tailored to a well-defined group of recipients through the close collaboration between Agora's operators and the actors of the given service

II.3 Stakeholder and user descriptions

Understanding the roles, needs, and expectations of stakeholders and users is a crucial aspect of defining the scope of any IT project. Ensuring this alignment helps the platform's development meet their requirements and effectively address their concerns.

In the case of Agora, which is designed to provide multiple Acceleration Services for stakeholders with diverse needs, it is assumed that system users and the level of access they receive to specific functionalities will be defined separately for each Acceleration Service. This assumption stems from challenges identified in the project, as described in DS4.2.1 "Policy and Roadmap Approach".

To design a universal system for managing permissions to functionalities defined for individual Acceleration Services within Agora, it is necessary to categorize the platform's recipients at the highest possible level of abstraction. For this purpose, a persona-based approach has been chosen.

II.3.1 Personas

Personas are fictional characters created based on user research to represent the different user types that might interact with a product, helping to guide design and development decisions. The personas defined below will be used in the final recommendations to determine eligibility and access rights for individual Acceleration Services integrated into the Agora. The identification of the stakeholders was initially done in D7.1 "First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping" (section 3 Stakeholders mapping). For the purpose of the outline of the intended platform scope and for further software requirements engineering process, we regrouped the personas in the following categories of Agora stakeholders:

- Academia,
- EU/national/local authorities,
- Business,
- General public.

II.3.1.1 Academia

The following section lists the personas associated with HEIs.

II.3.1.1.1 Academic authority

Name and surname	Rudee van Hagen
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Age	59
Gender identity	Female
Education	PhD, Ethnolinguistics
Job/position description	Holds the position of rector of a university; highest academic and administrative leader, responsible for setting strategic direction and ensuring the institution's mission and goals are achieved; oversees academic programs, faculty, and staff, while also representing the university in external affairs and partnerships.
Motivation	She wants to search for information and attend conferences and virtual symposiums on building inter-university partnerships in Europe and with business; due to her high position and limited time, she wants the search and registration for these events to be occasionally handled by her delegated assistant.
Proficiency in using applications	Highly proficient in using screen readers and voice command applications.

II.3.1.1.2 Academic unit authority

Name and surname	Yan Novak
Age	60
Gender identity	Male
Education	PhD, Social Sciences
Job/position description	Holds the position of dean of a faculty; responsible for the long-term strategic planning and development of his institution; contributes to the development and implementation of academic policies and procedures;

	represents his institution at external events, meetings, and conferences.
Motivation	Interested in building strategic alliances with other institutions at the national and international level; interested in establishing and maintaining relationships with industry partners, government agencies, and non-government organizations.
Proficiency in using applications	Proficient user of office suites and reporting tools.

II.3.1.1.3 Research group leader

Name and surname	Heinrich Schmidt
Age	52
Gender identity	Male
Education	PhD, Computer Science
Job/position description	Defines research agenda and sets strategic goals for the group; identifies and prioritizes research projects that align with the group's expertise and interests; responsible for recruiting, training, and mentoring research staff; oversees the planning, execution, and completion of research projects.
Motivation	Interested in identifying funding opportunities and writing grant proposals to secure research funding; wants to establish and maintain collaborations with other research groups, institutions, and industry partners; interested in effective management and acquisition of resources such as laboratory equipment, workforce, and laboratory space.
Proficiency in using applications	Highly proficient in using various types of applications; however, due to the overwhelming number of responsibilities he does not have time to read manuals

	or navigate through complicated multi-faceted user interfaces.
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II.3.1.1.4 Scientific project leader

Name and surname	Celine Olson
Age	45
Gender identity	Female
Education	PhD, History
Job/position description	Oversees the planning, execution, and management of research projects, ensuring alignment with scientific goals and organizational objectives; leads multidisciplinary teams, coordinates with stakeholders, and manages resources to drive project success; her role involves critical decision-making, data analysis, and maintaining high standards of scientific integrity and innovation.
Motivation	Wants to find suitable researchers and students for internships who can augment her team in planned and ongoing research projects.
Proficiency in using applications	Expert in using voice-to-text software and adaptive keyboards.

II.3.1.1.5 Senior researcher

Name and surname	Igo Marquez
Age	38
Gender identity	Male
Education	PhD, Artificial Intelligence
Job/position description	Holds the position of associate professor in his department; works independently within a larger research department, focusing on developing machine

	learning algorithms for natural language processing; his responsibilities include designing experiments, publishing papers, and presenting findings at international conferences; collaborates with colleagues within the institute, but does not have a dedicated research team.
Motivation	Interested in a software platform that can streamline the process of finding funding opportunities and managing grant applications; seeks a system that can help establish essential contacts with other researchers and foster international collaborations; wants to participate in open science and work life balance trainings.
Proficiency in using applications	Extremely proficient in programming in Python using modern Artificial Intelligence libraries like TensorFlow and PyTorch. Skilled in data analysis, statistical methods, and has a solid understanding of ethical considerations in Artificial Intelligence.

II.3.1.1.6 Early-career researcher

Name and surname	Sabrina Papanicolau
Age	29
Gender identity	Female
Education	Graduate, Mathematics
Job/position description	She is in the position of PhD student; works in a research team that deals with advanced computational mathematics, and in the team performs computational simulations; occasionally teaches students; she is completing the final work on the preparation of her dissertation.
Motivation	Actively looks for external research institutions where she will be able to do a post-doctoral fellowship; for the

	post-doc, she is looking for a research unit that is not only characterized by a high research level, but also will provide her with support for the move with her husband and child; looks for courses that will allow her to better implement Open Science principles into her research process.
Proficiency in using applications	Self-taught; can prepare programs for high-performance computing; likes to experiment with software without first reading the manual; not fond of graphical user interface.

II.3.1.1.7 Student

Name and surname	Laszlo Tantino
Age	23
Gender identity	Male
Education	Undergraduate, sociology
Job/position description	Currently finishing his master's thesis in sociology; he occasionally earns extra money in part-time jobs when his expenses exceed the funds from the scholarships he receives.
Motivation	Looking for internships; searching for opportunities for direct further educational development; contact students who want to create and run a travel club.
Proficiency in using applications	High – modern technology enthusiast

II.3.1.1.8 Technical staff

Name and surname	Willy Corobescu
Age	39
Gender identity	Male
Education	Undergraduate, Information Technologies
Job/position description	Responsible for maintaining and troubleshooting technical systems and equipment, ensuring optimal

	functionality and minimal downtime; provides technical support, implements upgrades, and collaborates with other research team members to resolve technical issues; his role involves continuous learning and adapting to new technologies to support the organization's technical infrastructure.
Motivation	Wants to manage the list and availability of services of the research infrastructure of the laboratory where he works; he is responsible for sharing the results of the outsourced experiments with external entities.
Proficiency in using applications	Skilled in office applications, mostly working with spreadsheets; always using magnification tools and high-contrast display settings.

II.3.1.1.9 Director of the Project Support Center

Name and surname	Marcus Gitfer
Age	56
Gender identity	Male
Education	Graduate, Management in Local Administration
Job/position description	Oversees the strategic planning and management of support services for all organizational projects; leads a team of project support specialists, ensuring the provision of high-quality resources, training, and administrative assistance; his role involves coordinating with project managers, optimizing support processes, and driving continuous improvement initiatives to enhance project outcomes.
Motivation	He wants to search for information on current calls for dedicated inter-university research competitions within HEIs alliances and for partnerships with business, so that he can spread them to his university's research

	teams; he offers and seeks training in effective administrative management of research projects.
Proficiency in using applications	Efficient in using automation tools and applications that minimize work effort.

II.3.1.1.10 Director of Center for Innovation and Technology Transfer

Name and surname	Brenda Underberg
Age	50
Gender identity	Female
Education	Graduate, Bioinformatics
Job/position description	Leads efforts to drive technological advancements and facilitate the transfer of innovative solutions from research to market; manages a team of experts, foster partnerships with industry and academic institutions, and oversee the commercialization of new technologies; her role involves strategic planning and promoting a culture of innovation within the organization.
Motivation	Wants to present training offerings in the broad field of entrepreneurship and innovation, which are directed to university employees and HEIs alliance partners; wants to search for such requests from the industry that can be carried out by university research teams; wants to expand the accessibility of the university's expert base and infrastructure, which are already commercially available to industry, to make them accessible to the general public.
Proficiency in using applications	Most of the time use text processor application; extensively use speech-to-text applications.

II.3.1.1.11 Project support staff

Name and surname	Anna Smith
Age	47

Gender identity	Female
Education	Graduate, Biology
Job/position description	Responsible for the preparation and distribution of documentation such as reports, memos, and meeting minutes; ensures all project documents are up to date and assists in the preparation of documentation for review and approval; processes invoices, tracks project expenses and prepares financial reports and summaries; works at the university department with 20 years of experience in the academic environment.
Motivation	Wants to enter and lookup data in the platform without considerable effort; however, objects to any innovations in her workflow, and expects that she can maintain her routines intact.
Proficiency in using applications	Becomes proficient in using applications after she gets accustomed to them; expects that the introduction of any new tool will be preceded by proper training with a certificate being issued for the participants.

II.3.1.1.12 Communication officer

Name and surname	Eleen Ken
Age	29
Gender identity	Female
Education	Graduate, New Media in Communication
Job/position description	Responsible for developing and implementing communication strategies to effectively convey the organization's messages to internal and external audiences; creates and manages content across various platforms, handles media relations, and ensures consistent branding; her role involves monitoring communication channels, measuring the impact of communication efforts, and maintaining positive public relations.
Motivation	When preparing news for social media, she wants to get information about the effects of projects currently

	under development at the university, especially those being developed in partnership with other HEIs in alliances and in partnership with industry/business.
Proficiency in using applications	Uses a variety of modern social media applications; prefers using mobile applications instead of working on a laptop.

II.3.1.2 EU/national/local authorities

The personas including EU, national, and local authorities, involved in the regulatory framework and interested in leveraging the potential of higher education institutions in the development strategy at the EU, national, regional and local levels.

II.3.1.2.1 EU/national/local policy creator

Name and surname	Alice Govina
Age	47
Gender identity	Female
Education	PhD, Economics
Job/position description	Works as Secretary of State in Ministry of Science; responsible for developing and overseeing national science policies, ensuring the effective implementation of scientific programs, and fostering innovation and research; represents the ministry in governmental and public forums, advocating for the importance of science and technology in national development.
Motivation	As she prepares for government and inter-ministerial talks on the current national science policy, she needs detailed statistics describing partnerships and international cooperation of national universities.
Proficiency in using applications	Familiar with modern technologies.

II.3.1.2.2 EU/national/local officer

Name and surname	Jack Norton
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Age	51
Gender identity	Male
Education	Graduate, Law
Job/position description	Manages and coordinates interactions between the organization and governmental bodies at various levels, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and policies; monitors legislative developments, advocates for the organization's interests, and facilitates effective communication with policymakers; his role involves strategic planning, stakeholder engagement, and providing guidance on regulatory matters.
Motivation	During the legislative work on the amendment to the law on state science policy, he is preparing an impact assessment document, i.e., he wants to provide decision-makers (the government and members of parliament) with the fullest possible information on the potential effects of the changes, hence he needs up-to-date summaries and statistics collectively describing the internationalization of universities and the degree of cooperation with business and accessibility for citizens.
Proficiency in using applications	Easily gets accustomed to the interface of new applications; prefers to chat instead of video calls; when using teleconferencing applications, switches on speech-to-text feature to better understand interlocutor.

II.3.1.3 Business

The personas from the business environment interested in using the Agora.

II.3.1.3.1 Company CTO

Name and surname	Maria Kowalska
Age	45
Gender identity	Female
Education	Graduate, Computer Science; Master of Business Administration (MBA)
Job/position description	Chief Technology Officer at a mid-sized local IT company; responsible for overseeing the technological direction of the company, managing the tech team, and ensuring that the company's technology strategy aligns with its business goals; her role includes staying abreast of new technologies, managing the company's IT infrastructure, and leading R&D initiatives to foster innovation; collaborates closely with other executives to drive the company's growth into new markets, including international ones.
Motivation	Looking for a software platform that can help her identify and track ongoing research in Artificial Intelligence, especially those relevant to her company's product offerings; interested in tools that facilitate initiating and managing collaborations with local research institutions and universities; wants to use the product to gain insights into where and what kind of Artificial Intelligence research is being conducted and to connect with researchers and institutions for potential collaborations; needs a system that allows her to submit problems identified in her company's operations, which could be the basis for new research and development projects.
Proficiency in using applications	Not up to date with current programming practices; has a strong understanding of technology trends and project management; knowledgeable about Artificial Intelligence concepts and applications; familiar with

	the strategic implications of adopting Artificial Intelligence in business.
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II.3.1.3.2 Company officer

Name and surname	Jeremy Oxtens
Age	42
Gender identity	Male
Education	Graduate, Biophysics
Job/position description	Oversees key operational functions within the organization, ensuring efficient and effective implementation of company policies and procedures; collaborates with department heads to streamline processes, enhance productivity, and support strategic initiatives; his role involves performance monitoring, resource management, and contributing to overall organizational success.
Motivation	Wants to find available university biolab infrastructure that is cheaper than market solutions, and then wants to use it commercially to achieve the company's business goals; wants to prepare an application for funding to a government agency to finance an innovative R&D project in partnership with a university.
Proficiency in using applications	Competent in using applications that support one-handed or alternative input methods.

II.3.1.4 General public

The following section lists relevant personas not included in previous sections.

II.3.1.4.1 Journalist

Name and surname	Stacy Rosenbruck
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Age	38
Gender identity	Female
Education	Graduate, Journalism and Social Communication
Job/position description	Researches, investigates, and reports on news stories, delivering accurate and compelling content for various media outlets; conducts interviews, gathers information, and writes articles or scripts under tight deadlines; her role involves maintaining ethical standards, verifying facts, and providing insightful analysis to inform and engage the audience.
Motivation	Interested in reaching out to experts in the given field so that she can talk to them about the article she is currently preparing; while she prepares popular science articles, she wants to find accessible information about the university's scientific achievements and university-business partnerships; interested in whether universities have e.g. gender equality policies, how they implement them, and whether they are a good place to study, which she will use to prepare a news article for undergraduate study candidates.
Proficiency in using applications	Often uses text processors; enjoys graphical data visualizations (especially maps); pays special attention to secure and encrypted communication and data storage.

II.3.1.4.2 Citizen

Name and surname	Pedro Horowitz
Age	58
Gender identity	Male

Education	Graduate, Electronics
Job/position description	Works as Circuit Design Engineer in medium-size international IT company; responsible for designing, testing, and optimizing electronic circuits to meet specific technical requirements and performance standards.
Motivation	Raise practical problems to be solved related to the functioning of the local community; access the results of research conducted by universities.
Proficiency in using applications	Modern technology enthusiast.

II.3.2 Actors and user roles

The above analysis of the Agora stakeholders' requirements is intended to be illustrative, highlighting the most important user needs, as well as their differences and similarities, for the developers of Agora. After examining the example demands of the personas introduced above, it becomes evident that different users will often have similar expectations regarding what the Agora should offer them. The key differences lie in the specific information users seek and the data sources they wish to retrieve

It can also be assumed that different users may require varying levels of permissions for certain types of data. Some data will be openly accessible, some available to all logged-in Agora users, and other data restricted to users with higher permissions. Therefore, in defining Agora's architecture, it was assumed that the detailed **classification of the actors** using Agora and the **roles assigned to specific users** would be comprehensively specified for each Acceleration Service embedded within the platform

This approach is supported by the analysis performed in DS4.1.2 "Policy and roadmap approach". It implies that Agora should be equipped with general mechanisms for managing permissions assigned to users based on the role they are given in a specific Acceleration Service. This issue of defining actors and users' roles is discussed in detail in chapter *Part III: Schema of access rights for users in the created system*.

II.4 Agora platform architecture

The process of building the Agora of Acceleration Services requires consideration of specific design assumptions that will influence architectural decisions, define the methodology for

designing and developing the IT system on which Agora operates, and establish the principles of system evolution. Specific design choices will impact the sustainability of the solution and the costs incurred during its development and maintenance.

The proposed system architecture, based on analyses conducted as part of the aUPaEU project, takes into account the scenarios identified during the examination of Acceleration Services—how they will be utilized by end-users, their durability, whether they will undergo changes, and whether all Agora users will access the same services to the same extent.

In defining the platform architecture, consideration was also given to a modular approach to system development using open-source tools. It is assumed that the proposed architecture can be implemented using various technical and software solutions.

II.4.1 Architectural principles

The primary assumption in defining the architecture of Agora is the division of its modules into two parts (Fig. 1):

- Core modules,
- Acceleration services modules.

This division is based on the fact that end users will always perceive Agora through the Acceleration Services it provides. Therefore, Agora itself is expected to serve as a tool for deploying new Acceleration Services within the platform.

At the same time, its architecture and tools will enable the convenient and cost-effective deployment of new services. Additionally, it will ensure that all tools used by end users are perceived as consistent. A detailed description and examples of both types of modules are provided in Section 4.4.

Figure 1: Agora of Acceleration Services

Due to the anticipated diversity of Acceleration Services offered through Agora, it is assumed that Agora's role in delivering each service will vary. Technically, this means that different Acceleration Services will be implemented in different ways. Additionally, the way users interact with and perceive each Acceleration Service will also differ.

Agora users are expected to leverage the Acceleration Services offered on the platform to achieve their goals through the following activities (Fig. 2):

- Presentation,
- Exploration,
- Relationship,
- Execution,
- Intelligent search.

Figure 2: Ways of leveraging Acceleration Services by Agora users

Presentation refers to all activities in which the user obtains information from Agora about the existence of a needed Acceleration Service. Agora presents the Acceleration Service, meaning that information about the service is available on the platform. This does not necessarily mean that the Acceleration Service is hosted on Agora; rather, Agora acts as an information hub,

directing the user either to an internal Acceleration Service hosted on Agora or to an external system where the service can be accessed

Exploration includes all activities in which Agora enables users to obtain detailed information about what a particular Acceleration Service offers. In practice, this involves searching the information resources associated with the Acceleration Service. This process allows users to make informed decisions by providing them with a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. The searched data may either be stored within Agora or retrieved from external sources and then aggregated on the platform.

Relationship refers to situations where Agora is used for two-way interactions between participants of a given Acceleration Service. This means that the process of implementing the Acceleration Service (acceleration process) is facilitated through communication between the participants of the AS, tracking the progress of the different phases of the acceleration process and automating certain repetitive tasks. Providing this type of support within Agora requires defining specific procedures and rules to ensure that the acceleration process is carried out efficiently.

Execution means that Agora will be used as a tool to manage the acceleration processes directly. In practice, this involves integrating software modules within Agora to handle all or part of the processes supporting the transformation. The functionalities of such software are expected to be developed specifically for a given Acceleration Service, following an analysis of the required support. The software will be provided according to a permissions system, assigning different roles to Agora in managing the Acceleration Service.

The process of finding Acceleration Services on Agora is supported by a fifth key component— an *intelligent search* engine. This component plays a crucial role in ensuring that Agora users can find Acceleration Services even when they are unsure of what exactly they are looking for. Therefore, the search engine should utilize all available information resources within Agora and the Acceleration Services, regardless of their nature. To facilitate this, Acceleration Services should be implemented in a modular and standardized manner, ensuring that their information can be easily processed by the AI-driven retrieval and search engine. The search engine should also leverage the latest advancements in Artificial Intelligence in the fields of information retrieval and search. These technologies enable natural language interaction with the system and expand the search context by considering previously identified user needs within similar categories.

II.4.2 Acceleration Services integration level perspective

The concept of Agora assumes that end users will perceive it based on the Acceleration Services it provides. It is also expected that these Acceleration Services will vary in nature and be implemented in different ways using Agora's tools. Implementation will involve the use of various IT tools, the management of processes with different levels of complexity, and the delivery of diverse outcomes expected by users.

The complexity of the software running Acceleration Services will impact the cost of their development, deployment within Agora, and maintenance. To manage this complexity during the design and implementation of Acceleration Services, it is proposed to categorize them based on the level of integration of the Acceleration Service within Agora. The following levels of integration for Acceleration Services within Agora are proposed (Fig. 3), ranging from the lowest integration level (Level 0) to the highest (Level 4):

- Level 0: Acceleration service discovery,
- Level 1: Acceleration through data integration,
- Level 2: Acceleration process management,
- Level 3: Agora supported acceleration,
- Level 4: Embedded acceleration service.

Figure 3: Levels of integration of Acceleration Services in Agora

The concept of tiered integration of Acceleration Services into Agora is designed to provide a structured approach to defining their relationship with the Agora platform. This tiered system allows for varying degrees of integration, ensuring that services can be customized to meet specific needs and capabilities. It is therefore expected that different Acceleration Services may require different levels of integration. Furthermore, the same Acceleration Service may be offered by different providers through Agora with varying integration levels. For example, one provider may offer a basic version of an Acceleration Service that supports only Level 1 integration, while another may offer a more advanced version supporting Level 3 integration. An overview of possible integration levels for Acceleration Services, as discussed in Section 3 of document D5.1 Report on the Implementation Gap Analysis and the Ideation of the Digital Transition, is provided in Appendix 2.

Building Acceleration Services with higher levels of integration will increase costs and impact the platform's sustainability. This is particularly important due to the need to design, implement, and maintain more complex software code. Additionally, as services become more integrated, the platform must handle larger volumes of data and more complex interactions, requiring a robust infrastructure and ongoing resource management.

The levels of integration are designed to be sequential, with each level building upon the previous one. For example, achieving Level 3 (Agora supported acceleration) requires that level 1 (Acceleration service via data integration) has already been implemented. This sequential structure ensures that each level of integration enhances the functionality and interoperability of the Acceleration Service within the Agora platform, providing a clear path toward progressively deeper integration. By organizing integration in this way, the Agora platform can support a wide range of services with varying complexity and data requirements while effectively managing the associated costs and sustainability challenges.

II.4.2.1 Level 0: Acceleration Service Discovery

The most basic, zero level of integration for Acceleration Services within the Agora platform is the inclusion of Acceleration Services in the Acceleration Service Catalog (as defined in Section 6 of D2.1 "Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services Catalogue"). At this level of integration, Acceleration Services are presented to users and Agora allows interested parties to efficiently search for and discover these services. This level of integration does not facilitate detailed searches for data relevant from the perspective of the value added by the Acceleration Service, direct contact or relationship management with the Acceleration Service stakeholders. It allows users to browse available services without delving into specific details or content

Example: A representative of a higher education institution (HEI) can search for available Acceleration Services that provide information about research infrastructure for use but cannot directly obtain details in Agora about specific research equipment availability or the conditions under which it can be accessed. Additionally, the platform does not allow interaction with service providers through the platform, for example, to request detailed information on equipment availability conditions or to reserve the selected equipment for a specific period of time through the Agora.

The added value of Acceleration Services at this level of integration is providing Agora users with information about external services that may benefit them. The subsequent engagement with such an Acceleration Service will take place outside Agora. However, given the problem of information overload and the challenge of identifying truly valuable resources, the mere inclusion of information about a service related to research infrastructure is already highly beneficial.

II.4.2.2 Level 1: Acceleration through data integration

This level of integration involves more extensive data integration within Agora for selected Acceleration Service, facilitating comprehensive data exploration. Beyond simply listing services, this level enables in-depth searching of resources associated with a specific Acceleration Service. Users can view detailed information and define rules for filtering and sorting data. Information related to an Acceleration Service can be entered and stored directly in Agora, while data retrieved from external systems via API can also be accessed. All actions comply with the access permission levels defined for the specific user and Acceleration Service.

Example: A researcher is looking for computing resources to run experiments for a machine learning project. At Level 1 integration, Agora allows them not only to identify which partner universities—both national and international—offer cloud-based Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) services (as in Level 0 integration) but also to search for available resources directly within Agora. When searching, they can specify parameters of interest, such as GPU type, availability period, and cost. This detailed information enables them to make a precise selection based on their specific needs.

Thanks to Acceleration Services at this level of integration with Agora, users gain access to data in one place, without needing to switch to other systems, create accounts there (if even possible), or manage access permissions to obtain the required data. When such an Acceleration Service is launched on Agora, it can be assumed that its creators will make every effort to ensure that the data presented meets users' anticipated needs. They will configure the service so that the necessary information is accessible to all users belonging to groups with specific requirements. By integrating data within Agora, the issue of limited access to external systems—particularly those of other universities, both national and international—can be mitigated.

II.4.2.3 Level 2: Acceleration process management

This level of integration focuses on maintaining relationships with service participants. It includes initiating contact, sustaining ongoing communication, and monitoring interactions. Additionally, it supports the business aspects of collaboration, such as understanding the details of offered Acceleration Services, ordering, selling, and managing the entire usage process. It is expected that a CRM (Customer Relationship Management) approach will be leveraged to enhance and accelerate the transformation using Acceleration Services at this level of integration. This approach aligns with the analyses conducted in D4.1 "Inventory, Action Plan and preliminary Set of Business Processes" and D5.1 "Report on the implementation gap analysis and the ideation of the digital transition".

Example: A researcher seeking computing resources to run experiments for a machine learning project can contact the service provider, discuss service details, and negotiate terms

of service directly through Agora, ensuring a structured follow-up process and sustained engagement.

The advantage of Level 2 integration is the ability to maintain relationships between the parties involved in the Acceleration Service. Offering these services through Agora means that the service provider does not need to develop their own solutions to offer services. Alternatively, if they already have such solutions, they are not required to make them available to potential users outside their institution. Users interested in the service are not restricted from accessing external systems; the appropriate permission system in Agora will grant them access to the necessary resources. Additionally, managing the entire process through Agora enables its operators to fully monitor the workflow, thereby increasing the likelihood of a successful transformation. Effective transformation using Acceleration Services integrated at Level 2 requires implementing appropriate procedures and rules to ensure that both parties engaging with the service have confidence that their needs will be properly addressed. The implementation and monitoring of such procedures should be part of the oversight carried out by Agora operators.

II.4.2.4 Level 3: Agora supported acceleration

This level of integration involves embedding and executing part of the Acceleration Service lifecycle within the Agora platform. By 'part,' we mean a specific segment of the overall transformation process that Agora supports. For example, this could include assisting in launching the service and tracking its execution, while the actual service is performed outside Agora. Supporting the transformation may also involve providing data from external services at certain stages of the managed process and facilitating interactions between service recipients.

Example: In the case of running computations for a machine learning project, integrating the service at this level may involve embedding dashboards directly into Agora to display selected data from an external service. For example, users can monitor billing for computational power usage directly within Agora.

A key benefit of Acceleration Services integrated at Level 3 is the ability to provide selected elements of the managed process directly within Agora. Modern IT systems that handle complex business processes, which can be used as Acceleration Services, often offer the capability to share selected data from their processes via an API for external use. For Level 3 services, leveraging this capability can be beneficial both in terms of end-user convenience and cost efficiency, allowing selected data to be presented directly within Agora.

II.4.2.5 Level 4: Embedded Acceleration Service

The highest level of integration involves embedding the entire lifecycle of the Acceleration Service within the Agora platform, encompassing its creation, delivery, and implementation.

At this level, Agora manages all aspects of collaboration, from ideation and development to deployment and ongoing administration of the Acceleration Service. This level represents a fully integrated version of the Acceleration Service, where the service is created by Agora and is directly linked to it, making it an inseparable and integral part of the platform.

Example: In the case of running computations for a machine learning project, Level 4 service integration means full control over the process of searching, ordering, launching, and monitoring the entire computation workflow directly from Agora. A user logged into Agora can execute computations without needing to log into external systems.

Launching Acceleration Services integrated at Level 4 may mean that Agora serves as an access point for managing processes that are fully executed using external systems (e.g., servers providing the necessary computational power). In this approach, the advantage of managing these processes through Agora is that it centralizes all necessary services in one place, eliminating the need for users to log into external systems. Agora functions as a hub for managing external services, particularly in cases where handling external users (i.e., those outside the institution providing computational power) is not the primary focus.

Another type of Acceleration Service that can be provided at Level 4 includes services entirely managed by software running on Agora. An example of such a service is a conference management system— a relatively simple software solution that could be useful to many different Agora users.

II.4.3 Intelligent search engine

Taking into consideration that Agora is a collaborative platform that provides access to heterogeneous Acceleration Services that differ in the kind, scope and volume of collected data, the search service is a key component of the platform. As the collected data and provided services vary in complexity, origin, access rules, intended users and the level of integration with the platform, the search capabilities have to go beyond conventional techniques utilized in information retrieval systems. Thus, we propose to enhance the discovery, exploration and analysis of the data gathered in the Acceleration Services by introducing intelligent search techniques. In particular, we postulate enabling interaction with Agora via AI assistants. However, it should be noted that such an interaction has to be provided under a set of constraints that are substantially more complex than in the case of general-purpose AI assistants available to the mass audience. For example, Section 3 of DS4.2.1 “Policy and roadmap approach” describes challenges regarding legal and regulatory aspects of using Agora by industry and other external stakeholders. An AI Assistant in the field of Acceleration Services should:

1. Guarantee satisfactory precision and recall of the employed retrieval method with regard to the common types of queries that arise in the practice of interacting with Acceleration Services.
2. Ensure that search results are unbiased.

3. Fulfill the specific requirements placed by the stakeholders and owners of the Acceleration Services regarding copyright and access rights.
4. Comply with GDPR and the EU Artificial Intelligence Act.

Ensuring (1) requires thorough requirement analysis, conducting experiments with the end users in a controlled environment and the analysis of usage logs to collect representative evaluation data. Fairness (2) is a key concern that has to be addressed in the search engine which aims to streamline collaboration between scientists and institutions on the basis of qualifications and competences. Failing to fulfill (3) will prevent HEIs from integrating with Agora and limit its growth. Finally, (4) is mandatory for all AI systems deployed in the European Union.

The fast-paced progress in the field of AI also means that the requirements for the intelligent search engine cannot be reduced to a set of recommendations that indicate particular types of AI models, categories of system architectures or specific service providers. Instead, to make Agora a sustainable platform, there is a need for an open, transparent, and reproducible benchmark that will test the capabilities of an AI Assistant along the aforementioned dimensions before and after the assistant is integrated into the platform. The requirements for the integration of the intelligent search engine in Agora are described in chapter IV.3 Intelligent Search Methods.

II.4.4 Key components of the platform

To develop a tool that enables stable growth, integration of new Acceleration Services, and modification of existing ones, the Agora architecture is assumed to consist of logical modules divided into two parts: *core modules* and *Acceleration Service modules*. The core modules define the structure of all Acceleration Services delivered through Agora, ensuring consistent data presentation, uniform access permission levels, and mechanisms for searching resources available on the platform. The Acceleration Service modules are responsible for the provided services, considering their different natures and levels of integration within Agora.

The following discussion presents the general approach used to define the Agora architecture. Appendix 1 illustrates how the specific user requirements map to defined here components of Agora.

II.4.4.1 Core modules of the platform

The core modules include the following (Fig. 4):

- Federated login,
- User management,
- Intelligent search engine,
- Personalization module,
- Notifications module,

- Data Visualization engine,
- CRM engine,
- Off-the-shelf plugins,
- Custom modules.

Federated login is a part of Agora that allows users to access Acceleration Services with a single set of credentials. Due to the convenience of access, this type of login is assumed to be managed by a trusted third party. This approach simplifies the user experience by reducing the need to remember multiple usernames and passwords, while increasing security through centralized authentication. It is assumed that the login method should be natural for higher educational institutions users, but should also be feasible for users outside the university, such as business representatives or citizens. For university representatives, existing authentication systems such as eduGAIN are natural. To allow authentication for other users, it is advisable to include other authentication methods, but it should be noted that these are mostly managed by commercial companies outside the EU (e.g. LinkedIn).

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User Management is a module responsible for granting access rights to logged-in users for the Acceleration Services available to them. As shown in Section 3, Agora will be used by users with different needs, and roles within specific Acceleration Services. For example, in an Acceleration Service supporting the distribution of research infrastructure, users will have different roles: some will search for infrastructure, while others will be responsible for providing it.

The intelligent search engine is a key module within Agora's core components. It is assumed that this module has access to the data and resources of all platform components, including all Acceleration Services. This ensures that any platform user can submit queries with the guarantee of accessing all informational resources that constitute the platform's added value. The use of an AI assistant (see Section 4.3) enables query expansion and provides accurate answers, even when questions are not precisely formulated.

The personalization module is a platform component that enables full customization of system behavior and appearance based on the user's profile. This module will be responsible for

adapting both the system's functionality and interface to individual user needs while also considering the requirements of the user's category. This document presents the expected final functionalities of Agora; therefore, it is assumed that this module is beyond the scope of the aUPaEU project. However, given the nature of modern information systems, adapting the platform to users' needs and specificities is a crucial aspect. As a result, this module cannot be omitted from the Agora architecture and should be continuously developed as the platform evolves to support the transformation of higher education institutions.

The notifications module ensures that users receive notifications about events of interest related to the Acceleration Services they use. This module should be integrated with Acceleration Services to identify events relevant to the user. Such events may include the availability of a specific document in an exploration-type Acceleration Service, a message from a service provider in a relationship-type Acceleration Service, or any event occurring at any stage of the workflow in an execution-type Acceleration Service.

The data visualization engine is a core module designed to ensure that Agora maintains a consistent appearance, even as new Acceleration Services are added over time. The modular nature of Agora, which allows operators to introduce Acceleration Services whenever needed, may lead to inconsistencies in the platform's visual and functional aspects throughout its lifecycle. This module ensures that the platform remains visually coherent as it evolves, preventing inconsistencies in the appearance of individual services. Maintaining such consistency is crucial for the platform's sustainability. This approach is exemplified by the 'Generic Module' proposed in Section 4.2 of D5.1 Report on the Implementation Gap Analysis and the Ideation of the Digital Transition and implemented in Agora

The CRM engine is a module designed to enhance Acceleration Services that facilitate relationship management between actors when needed. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a well-established category of information systems aimed at maintaining comprehensive customer-provider relationships. Therefore, we assume that a module with this functionality will seamlessly integrate into Agora as a tool for organizing information exchange between users, storing data on the status of offered services, and automating selected repetitive tasks. Including such a module in the platform will ensure that relationships between actors in Agora are managed consistently. An important aspect of the CRM module is that various Acceleration Services can be managed using well-defined business modeling languages (such as BPMN). Such standardization will significantly contribute to the long-term sustainability of the solution.

The inclusion of *off-the-shelf plugins* in Agora's core modules suggests that many Acceleration Services will be developed using existing, ready-made components. This approach to building information systems aligns with best practices in modern software development, minimizing the human effort, time, and cost required to create a new IT solution. However, for this approach to be feasible, Agora as an IT platform must be built on an engine that supports the integration of existing modules.

Custom modules are Agora components that need to be integrated to support Acceleration Services with complex logic that standard plug-ins cannot handle. Developing such solutions is an inherent part of software development, but it always requires significant effort, time, and cost. Therefore, when introducing an Acceleration Service, it is essential to first determine whether it can be implemented using existing reusable Agora modules

II.4.4.2 Acceleration Service modules

The following modules are distinguished within the Acceleration Service modules of Agora (Fig. 4)

- Presentation modules:
 - Dashboard
 - Acceleration Service directory (AS Directory)
- Exploration modules:
 - Internal Data Visualization Modules
 - External Data Visualization Modules
- Relationship modules:
 - Acceleration Service relationship management (AS relationship management)
- Execution modules:
 - Partial workflow management
 - Comprehensive workflow management

The dashboard is a key component of the presentation modules. Its role is to provide each user with a homepage that grants access to Acceleration Services. The dashboard should adapt to the user by personalizing the platform experience. Personalization should consider the user's individual preferences, their history of using Agora, and the Acceleration Services of interest to other users within the same group (category). Additionally, the dashboard provides access to Acceleration Services integrated at Level 0 (Acceleration Service discovery) as well as those at all higher levels of integration.

The Acceleration Service Directory (AS Directory) is a module responsible for presenting the list of Acceleration Services available in Agora. It functions as a standard resource listing module with sorting and filtering options. This is a key module for users who want to begin using Agora by exploring its available offerings. The directory displays Acceleration Services at all levels of integration with Agora.

Internal Data Visualization Modules is a generic term for Acceleration Services that provide users with access to detailed information related to a specific domain area impacting transformation. For these types of services, it is assumed that detailed data is stored directly in Agora. This means that data is either entered directly by service providers or transferred and stored from external systems via an API. By leveraging the Data Visualization Engine core module to build such an Acceleration Service, users will be able to apply filtering and sorting mechanisms when searching for data. The level of detail of the provided information will depend on the specific Acceleration Service and the user's permission level.

External Data Visualization Modules, like *Internal Data Visualization Modules*, is a generic term for Acceleration Services that provide users with access to detailed information related to a specific domain. The key difference is that the data presented to Agora users is not stored in Agora's internal database but is retrieved in real time from external systems via an API. This approach is particularly useful when developing systems that require detailed information about a specific subject area. Real-time data retrieval ensures that the information is always up-to-date and eliminates the need to merge it with data in a local database. However, it is essential to implement a policy that ensures the availability of external APIs, maintains their consistency, and adheres to appropriate technological standards during software updates on both Agora and external systems. As shown, this presents a substantial set of challenges that must be addressed to ensure the sustainability of the solution. Acceleration Services built using Internal and External Data Visualization Modules provide access to Acceleration Services integrated at Level 1 (Acceleration through data integration).

Acceleration Service Relationship Management is a generic term for modules responsible for Acceleration Services where transformation relies on the exchange of information between service actors and the monitoring of progress through various phases of service implementation. It is assumed that such services are implemented using the CRM engine provided by Agora's core modules. This ensures that relationship management between users is handled within the functionalities of CRM tools with well-defined boundaries. The specific communication and service management flow is expected to be defined individually for each Acceleration Service. Acceleration Services built using Acceleration Service Relationship Management facilitate access to Acceleration Services integrated at Level 2 (Acceleration process management).

Partial Workflow Management and *Comprehensive Workflow Management* are two generic terms for Acceleration Services that require execution-type modules for implementation. These Acceleration Services rely on advanced software to achieve their defined objectives. This software can be provided by reusable modules that function as plugins within Agora or by fully dedicated software developed specifically for integration with Agora. These are the most advanced types of Acceleration Services, with the key difference being their level of integration within Agora. The workflow can be partially embedded in Agora, reaching integration Level 3 (Agora-supported acceleration), or it can be fully executed within Agora, reaching integration Level 4 (Embedded acceleration service).

Figure 4: Logical model of Agora of Acceleration Services

II.5 Sustainability perspective

Even if the Agora architecture is well-designed and the Acceleration Services it provides fully meet user needs, technical and organizational factors may still arise that impact the sustainability of the solution. Maintaining, expanding, and troubleshooting an IT system is a complex process that can be disrupted in various ways. Designing Agora from the outset with an approach that ensures sustainability at every stage of development increases the likelihood of launching a platform that remains effective in the long term.

In the technical context of Agora, 'sustainability' is understood as a set of practices and strategies aimed at ensuring long-term efficiency, flexibility, and minimizing negative environmental impact. Specifically, this involves designing for durability—building an IT system that is easy to maintain, update, and scale. This approach extends the system's lifespan, reduces the need for frequent software replacements, and ensures optimal hardware utilization.

The long-term sustainability of the Agora platform will be influenced by the following factors, regardless of how well it is built in the initial phase:

1. Deployment strategy of the Agora platform,
2. Maintainability of the Agora platform as open-source software,
3. Data interoperability, validity and integrity,
4. Access rights and authorization,
5. Procedures for managing acceleration services.

II.5.1 Deployment strategy of the Agora platform

Ensuring the development and maintenance of the Agora platform requires designing an appropriate deployment model. The choice of deployment model—i.e., the process of setting up and configuring software systems for use in a specific technical environment—will significantly impact the platform's scalability, maintainability, security, and user experience. The following deployment models can be considered for the Agora platform:

1. Self-hosted

In the self-hosted model, each Higher Education Institution (HEI) or HEI network creates, manages, and maintains its own instance of the Agora platform. This model provides the highest level of control and customization for individual institutions, allowing them to tailor the platform to their specific needs and security requirements.

2. Centralized

A centralized model involves a single, centrally managed instance of the Agora platform, accessible to all users across the EU. This model simplifies administration and updates, as there is only one instance of the Agora platform to maintain. It ensures consistent user experience and functionality across all institutions but can present challenges in terms of scalability and data sovereignty.

3. Single tenant

In a single-tenant model, centrally managed instances are created for each HEI or HEI network. This approach combines centralized administration with some degree of customization and isolation for individual institutions. Each HEI has its dedicated environment, reducing the risk of data breaches between institutions and allowing for specific configurations.

4. Multi-tenant

A multi-tenant model involves a single, centrally managed instance that, through its specialized software architecture, provides the appearance of separate instances for each HEI or HEI network. This model maximizes resource efficiency and scalability, as multiple institutions share the same infrastructure while maintaining a high degree of data segregation and customization at the user level.

Table 1. Pros and cons of proposed deployment models of the platform.

Deployment model	Pros	Cons
Self-hosted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • full control over customization and security • data sovereignty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high maintenance and operational costs • requires significant IT resources and expertise
Centralized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • simplified management and updates • consistent user experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • potential scalability issues • data sovereignty concerns • less customization for individual institutions
Single tenant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • isolation of data and resources • customization for individual HEIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • higher operational costs than multi-tenant • moderate maintenance burden

Multi-tenant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● efficient resource usage ● scalability ● perceived individual instances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● complex architecture ● potential performance issues during peak usage ● data security and privacy must be meticulously managed
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II.5.2 Maintainability of the Agora platform as software

Ensuring the maintainability of the Agora platform as a software application is critical to its long-term development and the addition of new functionality. Maintainability refers to the ease with which a software system can be modified to correct defects, improve performance, or adapt to a changing environment. The software must be designed and built with future growth in mind, focusing on key aspects that facilitate ongoing maintenance and scalability. The following components related to software and its development should be considered to ensure the sustainability of the solution:

1. Architectural design

A well-defined and modular architecture is fundamental for maintainable software. The Agora platform should adopt a service-oriented or microservices architecture, where components are loosely coupled and can be developed, deployed, and scaled independently. This approach allows for easier updates and additions of new features without affecting the entire system. It also facilitates better fault isolation and resilience.

The modular architecture of the Agora and the different levels of acceleration services integrated with the platform, as outlined in this document, fulfill this characteristic.

2. Use of libraries and third-party software

Using existing libraries and third-party software can speed development and provide robust, tested functionality. However, it is important to choose libraries that are well documented, actively maintained and have a strong user community. Regular updates and monitoring of these dependencies are necessary to ensure compatibility and security. It is also important to avoid unnecessary dependencies and ensure that the libraries chosen are in line with the long-term goals of the platform.

Recommending the use of off-the-shelf plugins, the CRM engine, and the data visualization engine in the Agora platform architecture (see Fig. 4) is an implementation of the guideline to utilize libraries and third-party software, especially well tested and documented open-source projects.

3. Comprehensive documentation

Detailed and up-to-date documentation is essential for the maintainability of the platform. This includes documentation for the codebase, architecture, APIs, and user guides. Good documentation facilitates knowledge transfer, making it easier for new developers to understand the system and for existing developers to troubleshoot issues and implement new features. Automated documentation tools can help keep the documentation consistent with the codebase.

It is recommended that the documentation is created in such a way as to allow the transition from one deployment model of the platform to another (see chapter 5.1). This will streamline the process of transferring the software from one hardware platform to another, should this become necessary as the Agora evolves.

4. Deployment model and infrastructure

The deployment model should support continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) practices, enabling frequent, reliable releases. Containerization technologies like Docker, combined with orchestration tools such as Compose or Kubernetes, can help achieve a consistent and scalable deployment environment. Infrastructure as Code (IaC) practices should be employed to manage infrastructure changes efficiently and reproducibly.

Work on the infrastructure in which Agora will be launched should not depend on the deployment model chosen (see chapter 5.1). It should be assumed that Agora will be built for long-term operation, so initial efforts should be made to properly implement the appropriate technical solutions. In this way, the system can be easily scaled in the event of increased demand for Agora's services.

5. Maintainability metrics

Implementing metrics to measure maintainability can provide insights into the health of the software. Key metrics include code complexity, code churn, test coverage, and technical debt. Regular code reviews and static analysis tools can help maintain code quality and reduce complexity. Automated testing, including unit tests, integration tests, and end-to-end tests, ensures that the software remains robust as it evolves.

It is recommended that appropriate code quality metrics are implemented primarily in those parts of the system where acceleration services are integrated with the core modules of Agora. These components will be particularly sensitive to errors, especially if the platform is built from libraries and third-party software, as recommended in this document. Good software of this type will be constantly evolving, and errors may occur during updates to Agora.

6. Scalability and performance

The platform should be designed to handle increasing loads and a growing number of users. Scalable database solutions, efficient data processing pipelines, and performance monitoring tools are necessary to ensure the platform can grow without performance degradation.

Proactive performance optimization and load testing can help identify and address potential bottlenecks.

It is recommended to adopt a solution where Agora is built as a tool supporting a large number of users, rather than as a prototype solution.

II.5.3 Data interoperability validity and integrity

Ensuring that the data collected and processed by Agora is valid and maintains integrity over time is crucial. This involves implementing robust mechanisms for data verification, validation, and error correction. High-quality data is essential for reliable research outcomes and user trust. Regular audits and updates are necessary to maintain data integrity, and automated tools can help manage data efficiently.

The task of maintaining data consistency will involve both data collected directly on Agora and data integrated from external sources via the API. In the first scenario, Agora operators will be responsible for implementing control mechanisms over the data stored in each acceleration service to ensure its accuracy and consistency. In the second scenario, it will be necessary to monitor whether external data sources are providing up-to-date data and how frequently this data is updated by the external provider. It will also be important to ensure that the technical structure of the API has not changed. This is particularly important in order to maintain the stability of Agora. Changes to the API by an external provider can technically destabilize Agora. It will therefore be crucial to rely on data in an interoperable and stable format. This creates a significant opportunity for regulators, including the EU, to enforce such data formats, especially for data provided by public institutions. Much work in this area has been done by the task forces as part of the work on EOSC. When building Agora, the experiences and solutions developed during the work on EOSC, in particular the reports on EOSC interoperability, should be taken into account ¹.

II.5.4 Access rights and authorization

Managing access rights and authorization is fundamental to protecting sensitive information and ensuring that only authorized users can access specific data and functionalities. This includes implementing role-based access control (RBAC) systems, secure authentication methods, and regular reviews of access permissions. Proper access management not only secures the data but also complies with legal and ethical standards for data protection. Additionally, it can help to protect the interests of HEIs which may only agree to offer some

¹ EOSC interoperability framework - Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture", 2021. "A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework - Capabilities and Gaps", 2023

types of services or resources on the platform if their institutional guidelines and policies are met.

In the case of Agora, the issue of access rights and authorization requires the implementation and maintenance of an effective authorization system that will allow users from different backgrounds to access acceleration services. On the one hand, there will be users from higher education institutions, for whom a single system of authorization (EduGain) has already been implemented. These users will be able to log in to Agora with the usernames and passwords they use every day at their institutions. However, other users (see chapter 3), including business representatives, EU, national or local authorities and citizens, may also wish to use Agora. Ensuring a single authorization system for users from different backgrounds will be challenging as no such authorization system currently exists in the EU. While it is possible to rely on multiple authorization systems, maintaining them within Agora will increase costs and require continuous monitoring of their availability and popularity. This is particularly important when authorization is carried out using services provided by non-European corporations. The availability of such services may be affected by the business decisions of the provider. This underlines the need for EU regulators to monitor this issue and ensure centralized authorization access to services for EU citizens. The rules for authentication and authorization in Agora are thoroughly described *in Part III: Schema of access rights for users in the created system*.

Apart from the above, it is also necessary to consider the needs of users who are considering using Agora but are not yet convinced. A decision will need to be made whether such users will need to create an account on Agora or whether a specific set of acceleration services will be available without logging in. These services could include promotional and educational materials about the benefits of using Agora. It may also be possible to offer other Agora services without requiring users to log in. Such requirement is supported by interviews performed during work on the DS4.2.1 "Policy and roadmap approach".

II.5.5 Procedures for managing acceleration services

In addition to technical factors, the sustainability of Agora will also be influenced by the rules under which it will operate. This means that it is necessary to develop and implement procedures for the operation of acceleration services launched on Agora. These procedures should concern both the acceleration service providers and the Agora platform operator. This type of documentation will determine the sustainability of the solution built, because even the best designed and implemented services will not be successful if they are not operated by people at the level intended during the service design. Only good procedures and their effective implementation can ensure the success of Agora.

It is recommended that the definition of Acceleration Service management procedures is required whenever a new service is implemented on Agora. Maintaining Agora in operation requires joint action by AS providers (including HEI) as well as an institution that is responsible for maintaining Agora as a coherent entity. Agora operator is a role required to ensure AS

durability, good brand, quality of services. The procedures should include the following components on the service provider side:

- listing the personnel responsible for managing the Acceleration Service,
- defining their scope of responsibilities,
- specifying response times to events triggered by service users,
- outlining the type of response expected to user actions,
- compliance statement regarding ethical and legal frameworks (institutional, national and general),
- establishing contingency procedures for unforeseen service management situations including the provision of contact information for the personnel responsible for the service.

Procedures for Agora operators should include:

- control procedures to ensure that the service is offered continuously,
- procedures regarding implementation of mechanisms that allow to verify the accuracy of the information provided in the Acceleration Service,
- procedures to verify that the service is technically offered as intended.

II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora

The appendix illustrates how the requirements gathered from users are mapped to the components of Agora, based on the architecture presented in the main document. The requirements expressed by users are either implemented through Acceleration Services or provided by Agora's core modules.

II.6.1 Mapping User Expectations to Agora Modules

The table below summarizes the needs expressed by system users during the live session held on January 26, 2024, at the workshop *Presenting the Concept and the Implementation of the Agora*. The table lists the needs expressed by users via Padlet.com platform and the Agora modules that address them. In the remainder of the document, the term Padlet will be used to refer to a user-submitted entry provided through this tool. Due to the diversity of user requirements for Agora, a single requirement in the table may be addressed by two different functionalities, or may be met to varying degrees by Acceleration Services of different complexity and types.

User requirement (as written on Padlet)	Module type	Functionality provided by core modules of the platform or Acceleration Service
<i>Question 1: Imagine your institution or workgroup now having access to an Agora platform offering a suite of acceleration services. What specific functionalities would you expect or wish to see in such a platform to enhance your work efficiency?</i>		
P1.1 Match making amongst researchers	Core module Execution module	AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking
P1.2 Use agora to optimize the dissemination and organization of the existing matchmaking events and services provided by IRIS	Relationship module Execution module	AS 3.: Integrated Communication and Follow-up AS 4.1: Event Management and Dissemination

P1.3 Common training offers for faculty and staff	Presentation module	AS 2.2: Centralized Training Offers Directory
P1.4 Access through mobile app	Non-functional	ANFR 1: Accessibility and Mobile Support
P1.5 Match making between IT staff	Core module	AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking
P1.6 A large automatized database of internships and PhD positions (and why not job offerings) offers from all the Unite universities	Exploration module	AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers
P1.7 Emrex ² user group	Core module	AFR 6: User Group Management
P1.8 Presentation of an event together with a registration form.	Execution module Relationship module	AS 4.2: Event Presentation and Registration, Integrated Communication and Follow-up
P1.9 Publications of external events or news share the online and F2F services provided by each institution of the alliance and request	Execution module	AS 4.2: Event Presentation and Registration

² Emrex User Group (EUG) is an independent, international network which unites various actors interested in enhancing student data portability. As such, the network will act as a global platform for connecting expertise, sharing knowledge and enhancing collaboration to expand EMREX footprint and help unlock the full potential of student data and open up data flows globally. (<https://emrex.eu/about-us/>)

both virtual and physical access		
P1.10 Finding universities where to stay for a visiting period, especially for PhD students	Exploration module	AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers
P1.11 A matchmaking space for the Student Activity Seed Fund	Core module	AFR 3: Matchmaking for Funding Programs
P1.12 Funding opportunities for specific topics	Presentation module Relationship module	AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory AS 3.2: Integrated Application and Submission Tools
P1.13 Sharing of best practices/patterns for teaching in JP	Presentation module	AS 1.4: Sharing Best Practices and Teaching Patterns
P1.14 Validating posts on forums by AIDA; only sending to admins in specific situations	Execution module	AS 4.4: Content Management
P1.15 Match making for creating JPs and collaborative course	Core module	AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking
P1.16 Sharing documents for collaborative work. Restricted access for group members.	Execution module	AS 4.5: Collaborative Work and Communication Tools

<p>P1.17 Finding stakeholders and organizations with particular scientific problems to possibly collaborate on and solve with students during their courses</p>	<p>Exploration/Execution module</p>	<p>AS 2.5: Stakeholder Discovery and Engagement</p>
<p>P1.18 Can the Agora platform replace a local Teams channel that is currently used by a community?</p>	<p>Execution module</p>	<p>AS 4.5: Collaborative Work and Communication Tools</p>
<p>P1.19 I want to use AIDA to search for documents like templates, etc. It takes up so much time for me looking for documents</p>	<p>Core module Exploration module</p>	<p>AFR 4: Advanced Document Search and Retrieval AS 2.9: Integration and Accessibility of Existing Resources</p>
<p>P1.20 Visualization of research infrastructures, regional stakeholders, TTOs or other relevant structures/organizations</p>	<p>Exploration module</p>	<p>AS 2.1: Research Infrastructure and TTO Directory</p>
<p><i>Question 2: Imagine your institution or workgroup now having access to an Agora platform offering a suite of acceleration services. Reflecting on your daily professional activities, how could an Agora platform streamline or augment these tasks? Please provide practical examples or scenarios.</i></p>		

P2.1 It would help to connect easier to colleagues from other universities	Presentation/Relationship module	AS 2.6: International Collaboration and Networking
P2.2 Through AIDA finding relevant information much faster (for example legal aspects, support material)	Core module	AFR 4: Advanced Document Search and Retrieval
P2.3 Offering on-line kind of zoom tool built in	Execution module	AS 4.5: Collaborative Work and Communication Tools
P2.4 Ability for collaborative work. Word, excel, pdf, etc.	Execution module	AS 4.5: Collaborative Work and Communication Tools
P2.5 Offer a tool for sending surveys to researchers	Execution module	AS 4.3: Survey Collection Tool
P2.6 Could help to connect many sources of information and skip some unnecessary intermediate points in the process	Core module	AFR 8: Streamlined Information Connectivity
P2.7 I want to use AIDA also for searching the existing documents that we have in our Ushare. Is it possible? For example. I am looking for the PowerPoint presentation by UPC in the last dialogue meeting	Core module Exploration module	AFR 4: Advanced Document Search and Retrieval AS 2.9: Integration and Accessibility of Existing Resources

P2.8 Share courses material and syllabus	Exploration module	AS 2.7: Course Material and Syllabus Sharing
P2.9 Possibility to easily search for and access information and contact and connect with stakeholders, fostering international research collaboration	Presentation/Relationship module	AS 2.6: International Collaboration and Networking
P2.10 Notifications	Core modules	AFR 7: Personalized Notifications
<p><i>Question 3: Considering the diverse needs of your institution or workgroup: Which acceleration services offered by an Agora would be most valuable to you? Please elaborate on why these services stand out</i></p>		
P3.1 Database and visualization of 1) research infrastructures AND 2) regional stakeholders, with multiple search functions and filters	Exploration module	AS 2.1: Research Infrastructure and TTO Directory
P3.2 I want a database of contracts, handbooks, proposal templates, etc. (I am in research support)	Core module	AFR 2.4: Database supporting the preparation of new project proposals
P3.3 Visualization of the educational offer	Exploration module	AS 2.8: Visualization of Educational Offers
P3.4 Matchmaking for possible projects	Exploration/Execution module	AS 2.5: Stakeholder Discovery and Engagement

<p>P3.5 Stakeholder management - It would be very useful to Connect HEIs to stakeholders which can help them in their institutional transformation</p>	<p>Relationship module</p>	<p>AS 3.4: Institutional Support and Transformation</p>
<p>P3.6 Enable supporting documents to the community.</p>	<p>Exploration module</p>	<p>AS 2.7: Course Material and Syllabus Sharing</p>
<p>P3.7 Funding opportunities for research, teaching and mobility</p>	<p>Presentation module Relationship module</p>	<p>AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory AS 3.2: Integrated Application and Submission Tools</p>
<p>P3.8 Finding right people from academia and business to cooperate on given subject/project</p>	<p>Core module</p>	<p>AFR 1: Expert Finder</p>
<p>P3.9 Connecting researchers, students and organizations interested in a given scientific topic</p>	<p>Presentation/Relationship module</p>	<p>AS 2.6: International Collaboration and Networking</p>
<p>P3.10 Registration forms for events / Call for proposals.</p>	<p>Execution module Relationship module</p>	<p>AS 4.2: Event Presentation and Registration AS 3.1 Integrated Communication and Follow-up</p>
<p>P3.11 Funding opportunities, sharing of data</p>	<p>Presentation module Relationship module</p>	<p>AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory</p>

		AS 3.2: Integrated Application and Submission Tools
P3.12 A platform to publish PhD Job offers?	Exploration module	AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers
P3.13 Inter-alliance page connecting data from multiple alliances - e.g. research infrastructures, courses, internships, stakeholders, etc.	Presentation module	AS 1.1: Inter-Alliance Data Integration
P3.14 Platform for offers to students and staff.	Exploration module	AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers
<p><i>Question 4: Data drives innovation: What types of data do you believe are crucial for developing effective acceleration services in an Agora? How would you envision using this data?</i></p>		
P4.1 Up to date :)	Non-functional	ANFR 8: Data Quality and Currency Management
P4.2 Researcher data, infrastructure data, data from cordis	Presentation module	AS 1.5: Research Centralized Link Repository
P4.3 Regional stakeholder data	Exploration/Execution module	AS 2.5: Stakeholder Discovery and Engagement
P4.4 Data from patent databases	Presentation module	AS 1.5: Research Centralized Link Repository

P4.5 Data regarding funding opportunities, ideally from various sources - can this be extracted and combined?	Presentation module	AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory
P4.6 Aggregated	Non-functional	ANFR 7: Data Aggregation
P4.7 Bibliometric data on publications	Presentation module	AS 1.5: Research Centralized Link Repository
P4.8 Easy access to targeted data (AI function within Agora?)	Non-functional	ANFR 7: Data Aggregation
P4.9 How would we keep everything up to date?	Non-functional	ANFR 8: Data Quality and Currency Management
P4.10 Documents from Ushare - so that I can use AIDA to search for a specific document that I am looking for	Core module Exploration module	AFR 4: Advanced Document Search and Retrieval AS 2.9: Integration and Accessibility of Existing Resources
P4.11 Study programs within an alliance	Exploration module	AS 2.8: Visualization of Educational Offers
P4.12 Receive automatic notification on calls, events etc. targeted to my profile	Core module	AFR 7: Personalized Notifications
<p><i>Question 5: If you were to pilot test Agora's services, what criteria would you use to assess their effectiveness and utility? Think about both qualitative and quantitative measures.</i></p>		

P5.1: Easiness to use	Non-functional	ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface
P5.2: Time to find right information	Non-functional	ANFR 3: Efficiency and Accuracy
P5.3: Easy access, it is not clear now.	Non-functional	ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface
P5.4: Compare the output of AIDA and the time it takes to manual search results	Non-functional	ANFR 3: Efficiency and Accuracy
P5.5: Intuitiveness	Non-functional	ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface
P5.6: User friendliness	Non-functional	ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface
P5.7: Access through mobile app	Non-functional	ANFR 1: Accessibility and Mobile Support
P5.8: Access with institutional credentials	Core module	AFR 5: Secure Access Management
P5.9: How accurate are the results	Nonfunctional	ANFR 3: Efficiency and Accuracy
P5.10: Number of users	Nonfunctional	ANFR 5: Scalability of the solution

P5.11 Working links and back access to the agora home.	Non-functional	ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface
P5.12: Not only the quality, but mostly the quantity of useful information	Non-functional	AFNR 7: Data aggregation ANFR 8 Data Quality and Currency Management
P5.13: Enough data (for example more than 4 internships offering)	Non-functional	ANFR 7: Data aggregation
P5.14: Coherence with UI standards	Non-functional	ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface
P5.15: Try out matchmaking functionalities and see if it brings the "right" results	Core module	AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking
P5.16: Easy access: sometimes I am allowed to enter via Edugain, other entries require an agora account or LinkedIn,	Core module	AFR 5: Secure Access Management
P5.17: A link of relevant agora services below the current webpage would be beneficial	Non-functional	ANFR 4: Discoverability of available services
<p><i>Question 6: Identifying obstacles is key to improvement. What potential barriers could hinder the optimal use of Agoras in your context? These could be technical, organizational, cultural, or other...</i></p>		

P6.1: Cognitive barriers (barriers to learn a new tool)	Presentation module	AS 1.2: User Engagement and Training
P6.2: Delay between the query and the actual cooperation/response	Relationship module	AS 3.3: Effective Communication and Support
P6.3: Outdated information	Non-functional	ANFR 8: Data Quality and Currency Management
P6.4: Funding	Non-functional	ANFR 9: Agora funding
P6.5: Some institutions unwilling to share databases	Relationship module	AS 3.3: Effective Communication and Support
P6.6: Endorsement from the organization needed	Presentation module	AS 1.3: Dissemination and Organizational Endorsement
P6.7: If content is not updated/outdated content is not deleted, this would not give me a good impression	Non-functional	ANFR 8: Data Quality and Currency Management
P6.8: Dissemination to wide society	Presentation module	AS 1.3: Dissemination and Organizational Endorsement
P6.9: Different legislations in participating countries	Exploration module	ANFR 6: Integration and Compliance
P6.10: Integrations with local systems / user rights	Exploration module	ANFR 6: Integration and Compliance

P6.11: Not enough of dissemination in the institutions	Presentation module	AS 1.3: Dissemination and Organizational Endorsement
P6.12: It must be diffused in the organization	Presentation module	AS 1.3: Dissemination and Organizational Endorsement
P6.13: Security	Core module Non-functional	AFR 5: Secure Access Management ANFR 6: Integration and Compliance
P6.14: Invalid incorrect data	Non-functional	ANFR 8: Data Quality and Currency Management
P6.15: No reply from "contact"	Relationship module	AS 3.3: Effective Communication and Support
P6.16: Schooling/training of users for each institution	Presentation module	AS 1.2: User Engagement and Training
P6.17: If it is not used by enough users, so its utility to connect many actors is compromised due to the low participation	Presentation module	AS 1.2: User Engagement and Training

II.6.2 Addressing reported user needs in Agora

This section of the document presents a proposal for how Agora can address the needs reported by users and outlined in Chapter 6.1. The following factors influencing the development of Agora as an information system have been analyzed, considering the platform architecture proposed in Chapter 4:

- Agora's core modules,
- Acceleration Services modules,
- Non-functional requirements.

II.6.2.1 Needs addressed by Agora's core modules

This section of the document presents a proposal on how the needs reported by users, as outlined in the table above (Chapter 6.1), can be addressed through Agora's core modules (see Chapter 4.4.1) and the functionalities they provide. The following is an outline of the functional requirements that Agora must meet (Agora Functional Requirements; AFR) to satisfy specific user needs expressed in Padlets (see table above) . For each functionality, the corresponding Agora module responsible for its implementation is specified.

AFR 1: Expert Finder

Padlets: P3.8

Core module: Intelligent Search engine

The platform should include an Expert Finder tool to help users find the right individuals from academia and business to collaborate on specific topics or projects. This tool will allow users to find experts with relevant knowledge and experience, facilitating effective partnerships and collaborations.

It is assumed that the user will use the intelligent search engine to find experts. This will be possible under the assumption that the intelligent search engine will have access to all resources collected in Agora (see chapter 4.4.1). The success of finding experts depends on how the intelligent search engine is constructed (see chapter 4.3).

AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking

Padlets: P1.1 P1.5, P1.15, P5.15

(basic version) Core module: Intelligent search engine

(advanced version) AS module types: relationship

The platform should include matchmaking functionalities to facilitate connections among researchers and university staff. By providing accurate and relevant matchmaking results, Agora will help users establish valuable professional relationships. For example, matchmaking functionality can be used to facilitate the creation of Joint Programs (JPs) and collaborative courses. This allows users to connect based on their interests, expertise, and needs to form partnerships for educational and research projects.

In the basic version it is assumed that the user will only use the intelligent search engine for matchmaking. In this case, the user is solely responsible for formulating queries to Agora and deciding whether the results are what they need. Agora can also operate in an extended version (advanced version), where after finding and selecting the appropriate researcher, the user can contact and maintain communication with them through Agora. This will be facilitated by a CRM engine embedded in Agora for such purposes. (see chapter 4.4). In both cases, the success of matchmaking depends on how the intelligent search engine is constructed (see chapter 4.3).

AFR 3: Matchmaking for Funding Programs

Padlets: P1.11

AS module type: execution

The platform should include a matchmaking space specifically designed for the Student Activity Seed Fund. This feature will connect students with appropriate funding opportunities, helping them to identify and apply for financial support for their projects and activities. By facilitating these connections, the platform will increase the accessibility and utilization of available funding.

It is assumed that the user will use the intelligent search engine for matchmaking. This will be possible under the assumption that the intelligent search engine has access to data about funding programs for students. This data can either be stored in Agora or retrieved from an external data source via API. (see chapter 4.4.1). The success of matchmaking depends on how the intelligent search engine is constructed (see chapter 4.3).

AFR 4 Advanced Document Search and Retrieval

Padlets: P1.19, P2.2, P2.7, P4.10

Core module: Intelligent search engine

The Agora platform will feature advanced document search and retrieval capabilities powered by an intelligent search engine. Users will be able to quickly find and access a wide range of documents, including templates, support materials, and legal information. Intelligent search engine will also facilitate the search for existing documents stored directly in Agora or in external file repositories, making it easy to locate specific items like PowerPoint presentations from previous meetings. In both cases, the provision of the ability to store and share files from a particular data source is considered to be an Acceleration Service (for example AS 2.9: Integration and Accessibility of Existing Resources). The AI-powered search functions will ensure that users can access targeted data efficiently, significantly reducing the time spent on manual searches.

The intelligent search engine should have access to all data from the Acceleration Services integrated into Agora and made available via API (see chapter 4.4). It should also ensure high quality when searching the data (see chapter 4.3).

AFR 5: Secure Access Management

Padlets: P5.8, 5.13, 5.16

Core module: Federated login

The platform should provide access with institutional credentials, enhancing security and ease of use for users accessing the platform. This ensures that only authorized users can access the platform, safeguarding sensitive information and maintaining user trust.

Federated login should be implemented in such a way that it allows all Agora users to log in as easily as possible (see chapter 4.4.1 and 5.4).

AFR 6: User Group Management

Padlets: P1.7

Core module: Federated login

The Agora platform should incorporate features for effective user group management. This includes the ability to manage and support specific user groups such as the Emrex user group. By providing tailored functionalities for different user groups, Agora ensures that the unique needs and preferences of these groups are addressed, fostering a more engaged and satisfied user community.

This requirement is met by the Federated login module, which includes the ability to authorize access to Agora via external authentication systems (see chapter 4.4.1). The issue of selecting the most appropriate authentication systems should be the subject of further in-depth analysis (see Chapter 5.4).

AFR 7: Personalized Notifications

Padlets: P2.10, P4.12

Core module: Notifications module

A notifications system should be implemented on Agora to alert users about relevant updates such as new events, research opportunities, and other important information. It would enable automatic notifications tailored to user profiles. Users will receive timely notifications about

events, calls, and opportunities that match their interests, ensuring they are always up to date with information pertinent to their profiles.

Notifications should be explicitly added at the user's request using the functionalities of the Notifications module and should be displayed on the Dashboard (see chapter 4.4.1). It is also possible to consider a behavior where Agora automatically notifies the user based on a needs analysis. However, this would require the intelligent search engine to integrate not only the data but also information about user profiles.

AFR 8: Streamlined Information Connectivity

Padlets: P2.6

Core module: Personalization module

Agora should streamline the integration of multiple information sources, reducing the need for unnecessary intermediaries. This will simplify access to data and improve the efficiency of information retrieval, helping users to quickly find the resources they need without extra steps.

The selection of what will be presented to the user will be managed by a personalization module that allows for indicating the user's preferences. User-specific information about useful services will be presented on the dashboard.

II.6.2.2 Needs addressed by acceleration services modules

This section of the document contains a proposal on how the needs reported by users, presented in the table above (chapter 6.1), can be addressed through the Acceleration Services modules of Agora (see chapter 4.4.2). Those Acceleration Services are the ones that follow from user requirements gathered on Padlets.com platform and as such they should be treated as potential of even conceptual Acceleration Services. The following is an outline of the Acceleration Services (AS) that must be provided by Agora to satisfy specific user requirements expressed in padlets. For each functionality, the type of Acceleration Service is specified, indicating the level of integration with Agora. The Acceleration Services are presented below according to their level of integration with Agora, using the classification introduced in chapter 4.1 and 4.2 (i.e. Presentation modules, Exploration modules, Relationship modules and Execution modules).

II.6.2.2.1 Presentation modules

AS 1.1: Inter-Alliance Data Integration

Padlets: P3.13

AS module type: presentation

Agora should include an inter-alliance page that links and integrates data from multiple academic and research alliances from European Universities Initiative. This includes information on research infrastructure, courses, internships, stakeholders, and more. By providing a unified view of resources and opportunities across different alliances, the platform will facilitate broader access to valuable data and enhance collaboration between institutions and alliances.

This Acceleration Service is responsible for presenting to the user with an aggregated view of other Acceleration Services available on Agora (such as the Research Infrastructure and TTO Directory or the Database of internships, PhD positions, and job offers, etc.) in one place on the Dashboard (see chapter 4.4.1). In addition to the Acceleration Services built into Agora, this service may also make available external websites, resources, and information systems that contain critical data related to a particular alliance.

AS 1.2: User Engagement and Training

Padlets: P6.1, P6.16, P6.17

AS module type: presentation

The platform should focus on reducing cognitive barriers and improving user engagement through comprehensive training programs and user support. This will include providing training to users at each institution to help them learn and use the platform effectively. In addition, strategies to increase user participation will be employed to ensure the platform's utility in connecting a wide range of stakeholders.

Integrating this Acceleration Service at the presentation level means providing Agora users with promotional and educational materials about the benefits of using Agora. The materials can be in the form of videos and/or e-learning content that demonstrate the benefits of using Agora as a hub that integrates different types of Acceleration Services. These materials will be available to both registered and unregistered users (see chapter 5.4).

AS 1.3: Dissemination and Organizational Endorsement

Padlets: P6.8, P6.11, P6.12, P6.6

AS module type: presentation

Agora should implement dissemination strategies and seek the endorsement of participating organizations. This will include promoting the platform within institutions and to the wider

society to ensure that the platform is widely known and used. Organizational endorsement will further legitimize the platform and encourage greater participation and trust among users.

This Acceleration Service will include providing space on Agora to share important information for each institution about events, projects, achievements, etc.

AS 1.4: Sharing Best Practices and Teaching Patterns

Padlets: P1.13

AS module type: presentation

The Agora platform should provide a dedicated space for sharing best practices and teaching patterns, especially for Joint Programs (JP). This will include detailed descriptions, examples, and methodologies that educators can adopt and adapt to enhance their teaching strategies. By sharing these best practices, the platform will promote quality education across institutions.

The presentation type Acceleration Service refers to a service that will involve presenting best practices to users which will be carefully selected by the service operator . Users will be able to search for this type of service in the AS Directory (see Chapter 4.4.2).

AS 1.5: Research Centralized Link Repository

Padlets: P4.2, P4.4, P4.7

AS module type: presentation

The platform will aggregate information on where to find data related to research and infrastructure, such as links to external systems, databases, and directories, including researcher profiles, infrastructure details, and data from Cordis. Additionally, the platform will provide access to patent databases and bibliometric data on publications. This integration will provide users with a comprehensive view of the research landscape to support their work and collaborations.

The choice of the presentation type for this Acceleration Service refers to an idea that it should include all necessary links to systems, databases and directories supporting research and academia. Users will be able to search for this type of service in the AS Directory (see Chapter 4.4.2).

1.1.1.1 Exploration modules

AS 2.1: Research Infrastructure and TTO Directory

Padlets: P1.20, P3.8

AS module type: exploration

The Agora platform should feature a comprehensive directory of research infrastructures and Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs). This directory should include detailed information about each infrastructure and TTO, such as their capabilities, services, and contact details. Multiple search functions and filters should be available to the user. This will help users identify and access the resources they need for their research and development projects.

The directory can be built directly in Agora as an Internal Data Visualization Module (see chapter 4.4.2). In this case, all data must be entered by operators of the Acceleration Service who are logged in to Agora. Alternatively, the Acceleration Service can be built as an External Data Visualization Module. In this scenario, data would be retrieved from external data sources via API and displayed in Agora. In the first case, it is necessary to implement procedures to ensure that the data is up-to-date in the institutions providing the data (see chapter 5.5). In the second case, it is essential to select external data sources that are consistently updated. This option is only viable if we are confident that the data will be updated regularly.

AS 2.2: Centralized Training Offers Directory

Padlets: P1.3

AS module type: exploration

The Agora platform should provide a centralized repository of shared training opportunities for faculty and staff. This includes a variety of professional development programs, workshops, and courses designed to enhance the skills and competencies of HEI personnel. By centralizing these training opportunities, the platform ensures that faculty and staff have easy access to relevant and high-quality development resources.

The database can be built directly in Agora as an Internal Data Visualization Module (see chapter 4.4.2). In this case, all data must be entered by operators of the Acceleration Service who are logged in to Agora. Alternatively, the Acceleration Service can be built as an External Data Visualization Module. In this scenario, data would be retrieved from external data sources via API and displayed in Agora. In the first case, it is necessary to implement procedures to ensure that the data is up-to-date in the institutions providing the data (see chapter 5.5). In the second case, it is essential to select external data sources that are consistently updated. This option is only viable if we are confident that the data will be updated regularly.

AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers

Padlets: P1.6, P1.10, P3.12, P3.14,

AS module type: exploration

The Agora platform should include a comprehensive database of internships, PhD positions and job offers. The database will collect data from all universities gathered on Agora and will provide an additional boost to development by increasing the exchange of people between institutions.

The database can be built directly in Agora as an Internal Data Visualization Module (see chapter 4.4.2). In this case, all data must be entered by operators of the Acceleration Service who are logged in to Agora. Alternatively, the Acceleration Service can be built as an External Data Visualization Module. In this scenario, data would be retrieved from external data sources via API and displayed in Agora. In the first case, it is necessary to implement procedures to ensure that the data is up-to-date in the institutions providing the data (see chapter 5.5). In the second case, it is essential to select external data sources that are consistently updated. This option is only viable if we are confident that the data will be updated regularly.

AS 2.4: Database supporting the preparation of new project proposals

Padlets: P3.2

AS module type: exploration

The database should provide contracts, handbooks, proposal templates, etc. to assist researchers and research support staff in preparing new project proposals. The documents included in the database should be exemplary documents and best practices developed by the universities supporting the Acceleration Service.

The database should be built directly in Agora as an Internal Data Visualization Module (see chapter 4.4.2). For this service, the documents should be entered by the operators of the Acceleration Service who are logged in to Agora. In order to provide the most current and best documents, it is necessary to implement procedures to ensure that the data is up-to-date and that the best examples are selected (see chapter 5.5).

AS 2.5: Stakeholder Discovery and Engagement

Padlets: P1.17, P3.4, P4.3

AS module type: exploration/execution

The Agora platform should provide robust tools for discovering and engaging with stakeholders and organizations that have specific scientific problems. Users will be able to search for and connect with these stakeholders, facilitating potential collaborations to solve

problems with the help of students during their courses. The platform should also include a matchmaking feature for potential projects, ensuring that users can effectively find and engage with relevant stakeholders effectively. Additionally, it could provide access to regional stakeholder data to enhance local collaborations.

In exploration mode, the Acceleration Service serves as a database of stakeholders and potential projects. In execution mode, the system will provide a matchmaking function.

AS 2.6: International Collaboration and Networking

Padlets: P2.1, P2.9, P3.9

AS module type: exploration/relationship

Agora should support international collaboration and networking by enabling users to easily search for, access information, and connect with stakeholders around the world. This functionality will help users foster international research collaborations, connect with colleagues from other universities, and link researchers, students, and organizations interested in specific scientific topics. The platform will facilitate seamless communication and collaboration across borders.

The exploration type Acceleration Service provides a database of researchers and stakeholders interested in collaboration. In the extended (relationship type) version, Agora can be used to establish and maintain relationships with users of interest.

AS 2.7: Course Material and Syllabus Sharing

Padlets: P2.8, P3.6

AS module type: exploration

Agora should enable users to share Open Educational Resources such as course materials and syllabi, allowing educators to share resources and support documents with the community. This functionality will facilitate collaboration among educators and help them improve their courses by incorporating successful materials and approaches from their peers.

The Acceleration Service should be built as an internal data visualization module (see chapter 4.4.2), which means that an internal database containing course materials and syllabi will be created in Agora. When developing the service, it is necessary to establish guidelines that determine what materials can be included in the database and who will be responsible for it (see chapter 5.5).

AS 2.8: Visualization of Educational Offers

Padlets: P3.3, P4.11

AS module type: exploration

The platform should include tools for the visualizing of educational offers, including programs of study within an alliance. This will provide a clear and accessible way to view the range of educational opportunities available, helping students and educators alike to understand and take advantage of them. By visualizing these programs, the platform will make it easier to navigate and choose appropriate educational paths.

The database of educational offers can be built directly in Agora as an Internal Data Visualization Module (see chapter 4.4.2). In this case, all data must be entered by operators of the acceleration service who are logged in to Agora. Alternatively, the Acceleration Service can be built as an External Data Visualization Module. In this scenario, data would be retrieved from external data sources via API and displayed in Agora. In the first case, it is necessary to implement procedures in the institutions providing the data to ensure that the data is up to date (see chapter 5.5). In the second case, it is essential to select external data sources that are consistently updated. This option is only viable if we are confident that the data will be updated regularly.

AS 2.9: Integration and Accessibility of Existing Resources

Padlets: P1.19, P2.7, P4.10

AS module type: exploration

An Acceleration Service launched on the Agora platform that integrates with external existing document repositories, such as Ushare, to provide users with seamless access to stored resources. Using the advanced search capabilities of the intelligent search engine, users will be able to quickly find and use documents such as PowerPoint presentations and other important materials. This integration ensures that users can efficiently find and use existing resources without having to leave the Agora environment, improving overall accessibility and usability.

The Acceleration Service is based on data retrieved from an external data source integrated via API. When building this Acceleration Service, a strategy can be adopted where it integrates data from a single source, or it can act as a tool to aggregate data from multiple sources i.e. multiple cloud file storage services. It is also possible to consider building this service using a module that stores data directly on Agora.

AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory

Padlets: P3.7, P1.12, P3.11, P4.5

AS module type: exploration

The Agora platform should provide a comprehensive directory of funding opportunities, including those for research, teaching, and mobility. This directory will cover a wide range of specific topics and areas to ensure that users can find relevant funding opportunities tailored to their needs. The platform will also support the sharing of funding data among users to promote transparency and collaboration.

The integration of the Acceleration Service at the exploration level assumes that Agora will provide a catalog of links to external services containing information about funding opportunities. The key advantage of offering this type of service on Agora is that it centralizes this information in one place, making it more accessible to users .

II.6.2.2.3 Relationship modules

AS 3.1: Integrated Communication and Follow-up

Padlets: P1.2, P1.8, P3.10

AS module type: relationship

Agora should integrate communication tools to facilitate interaction between event organizers and participants. This includes automated email notifications, reminders, and post-event follow-up features. These tools will ensure effective communication before, during, and after events, improving the overall experience for participants and organizers alike.

The Acceleration Service should be built using the CRM engine embedded in Agora to handle such processes (see chapter 4.4.2).

AS 3.2: Integrated Application and Submission Tools

Padlets: P3.7, P1.12, P3.11

AS module type: relationship

Agora should integrate application and submission tools to streamline the process of applying for grants and funding. Users will be able to submit their applications directly through the platform, with features such as form autofill, document uploads, and application tracking. These tools will simplify the application process, making it more efficient and user-friendly.

The construction of the Acceleration Service at the relationship integration level should be achieved through the use of the CRM engine embedded in Agora specifically to support such processes (see chapter 4.1.1). This tool will enable the management of the proposal preparation process by specialized experts on the service provider side (e.g. the grant submission office of a given university).

AS 3.3: Effective Communication and Support

Padlets: P6.2, P6.5, P6.15

AS module type: relationship

The platform should enhance communication and support mechanisms to ensure timely responses and cooperation. This includes developing a reliable system for resolving queries, encouraging institutions to share databases, and ensuring that contact points are responsive. Effective communication and support will improve user satisfaction and foster better collaboration.

In all relationship type Acceleration Services, it is necessary to implement and maintain communication procedures to ensure that user requests do not go unanswered (see chapter 5.5). Good communication between the parties involved in such Acceleration Services may also make the service provider more willing to share its resources through Agora. This is especially important for institutions that may not be interested in sharing their resources through Agora in the early stages. As Agora demonstrates its usefulness through relationship type services, these providers may become more inclined to share their other resources. For example, if a university that wants to share its infrastructure finds that there is interest in it because potential users have initiated communication through an Agora relationship type Acceleration Service, the university may be more willing to share its resources through exploration type services. This would allow potential users to search for what they need on their own.

AS 3.4: Institutional Support and Transformation

Padlets: P3.5

AS module type: relationship

The platform should provide stakeholder management tools designed to connect Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with stakeholders who can assist in their institutional transformation. This includes features that help HEIs identify and engage with organizations that offer support, resources, or expertise critical to their development and transformation goals. By facilitating these connections, the platform will help institutions achieve their strategic goals.

The relationship type Acceleration Service enables users to maintain relationships with stakeholders during the institutional transformation process.

II.6.2.2.4 Execution modules

AS 4.1: Event Management and Dissemination

Padlets: P1.2

AS module type: execution

The Agora platform could be used to optimize the dissemination and organization of existing matchmaking events and services (for example provided by IRIS). This includes tools for event planning, promotion, and coordination to ensure that events are efficiently organized and widely publicized to reach the target audience.

Integrating this type of Acceleration Service at the execution level means that Agora will become a fully functional system for managing such events. This will require the development of a dedicated Comprehensive Workflow Management module (see Section 4.4.1). However, this effort could be worthwhile, as such a service could be used by all universities using Agora. Developing a dedicated solution ensures that it includes all the necessary functionalities. It should be noted, however, that building a dedicated IT module can be expensive, and the decision to create such a solution should be closely linked to the rules of use and financing of Agora.

AS 4.2: Event Presentation and Registration

Padlets: P1.8, P1.9, P3.10

AS module type: execution

The platform should provide comprehensive event presentation capabilities, allowing organizers to showcase event details along with integrated registration forms. Users will be able to view event information and easily register for events through user-friendly forms. In addition, this functionality will support calls for proposals, allowing users to submit their proposals for consideration directly through the platform.

Information about the event should be implemented as an Acceleration Service, which requires integration at the presentation level. However, the service also requires integration at the execution level to handle the registration process for the event.

AS 4.3: Survey Collection Tool

Padlets: 2.5

AS module type: execution

Survey collection tool which will be used as a supporting tool in those services where it has significance or independently. Therefore, the scope of access to the tool and the form of results will depend on the context.

Building this Acceleration Service at the execution integration level is necessary because managing it requires integrating a dedicated module into Agora (see chapter 4.4.1)

AS 4.4: Content Management

Padlets: P1.14

AS module type: execution

The Agora platform will include features for effective forum and content management. This includes the use of AI to validate posts on forums, involving administrators only in specific situations to ensure smooth and efficient forum management. This automated validation process will help maintain the quality of discussions while reducing the administrative workload.

Building this Acceleration Service at the execution integration level is necessary because it requires an advanced strategy for the service to perform its tasks.

AS 4.5: Collaborative Work and Communication Tools

Padlets: P1.16, P1.18, P2.3, P2.4

AS module type: execution

The Agora platform will provide a comprehensive suite of integrated communication and collaboration tools. Users will be able to conduct virtual meetings using a built-in tool similar to Zoom which facilitates seamless online interactions. In addition, the platform will enable collaboration on multiple document types, including Word, Excel, and PDFs, allowing multiple users to work together in real time. This integration will eliminate the need for external platforms and increase overall productivity and communication within the community.

Building the acceleration service at the execution integration level is necessary because it requires an advanced strategy for the service to perform its tasks.

II.6.2.3 Non-functional requirements for the core and acceleration service modules that address user-reported requirements

The Agora platform aims to ensure a seamless and efficient user experience by fulfilling non-functional requirements derived from user feedback into cohesive functional areas. The following is an outline of the non-functional requirements that Agora must meet (Agora Non-Functional Requirements; ANFR) in order to satisfy specific user requirements expressed in padlets.

ANFR 1: Accessibility and Mobile Support

Padlets: P1.4, P5.7

Non-functional requirements

The Agora platform should provide access through a mobile app, ensuring that users can engage with the platform conveniently from their mobile devices.

ANFR 2: User Experience and Interface

Padlets: P5.1, P5.3, P5.5, P5.6, P5.11, P5.14

Non-functional requirements

The platform should prioritize ease of use, intuitiveness, and usability. It will adhere to established user interface (UI) standards to ensure a coherent and consistent user interface. This focus on user experience will make the platform more accessible and enjoyable for users, encouraging frequent use and engagement.

ANFR 3: Efficiency and Accuracy

Padlets: P5.2, P5.4, P5.9

Non-functional requirements

Agora should focus on efficient information retrieval, reducing the time it takes to find the right information. The platform will compare the output of the Intelligent Search engine with manual search results to ensure that it provides accurate and reliable information. This will increase user confidence and satisfaction with the platform's performance.

ANFR 4: Discoverability of available services

Padlets: P5.17

Non-functional requirements

The Acceleration Services Directory (AS Directory; see chapter 4.4.2), which contains a list of all available Acceleration Services, should be presented on Agora in an easily accessible and visible location for every user.

ANFR 5: Scalability of the solution

Padlets: P5.10

Non-functional requirements

Agora should be prepared to handle a large number of users. It is necessary to implement mechanisms that allow for scaling the solution.

ANFR 6: Integration and Compliance

Padlets: P6.9, P6.10, P6.13

Non-functional requirements

Agora should facilitate integration with local systems and ensure compliance with the various regulations in participating countries. This includes addressing security concerns, managing user rights, and ensuring that the platform complies with local legal regulatory requirements. By focusing on integration and compliance, the platform provides a seamless and secure user experience across different regions.

Compliance with local regulations must be ensured during the preparation phase for the implementation of each Acceleration Service. This should be done either by confirming that the service complies with Agora's general rules or, in exceptional cases, by introducing new rules for the use of the service on Agora. In cases of non-compliance with local regulations, these rules may limit or prohibit the use of certain services in certain locations.

ANFR 7: Data Aggregation

Padlets: P4.6, P4.8, 5.12, 5.13

Non-functional requirements

The Agora platform should aggregate data from multiple sources, providing users with a centralized location for accessing and analyzing information. By integrating AI functions, the

platform will enable users to manage data more effectively, allowing for precise targeting and retrieval of specific information. This functionality will enhance the decision-making process by providing comprehensive and easily accessible data, improving overall efficiency and productivity.

The data will be made available to the users of Agora as an exploration type of acceleration services. Data is either stored directly on Agora or retrieved from external databases via an API (see chapter 4.4.2).

ANFR 8: Data Quality and Currency Management

Padlets: P4.1, P4.9, P5.12, P6.3, P6.7, P6.14

Non-functional requirements

The Agora platform must prioritize the management of data quality and currency to ensure that information remains accurate and up to date. This includes implementing mechanisms for regular data updates, validation processes to eliminate outdated or incorrect data, and systems to remove obsolete content. By maintaining high data quality, the platform will enhance user trust and reliability.

Ensuring the quality of data stored on Agora will be achieved by implementing technical processes to ensure high data quality (see chapter 5.3) and by establishing management procedures for acceleration services (see chapter 5.5). When properly implemented, these procedures will ensure that the services operate continuously, providing users with up-to-date data at all times.

ANFR 9: Agora funding

Padlets: P6.4

In order to ensure the operation of Agora, it is necessary to provide financing on the part of the Agora operator to cover the technical, administrative and operational costs of the services supported as well as the costs of the AS provider in order to ensure its ongoing operation.

II.6.3 aUPaEU Acceleration Services

Below is an example of how to build aUPaEU Acceleration Services defined in D2.1 "Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue" using the functionalities defined in chapter 6.2. These functionalities indirectly address the needs identified by users during the workshop *Presentation of the concept and implementation of the Agora* on January 26, 2024, and expressed through Padlets (see chapter 6.1).

aUPaEU Acceleration Services	Agora's modules that address identified user needs expressed through Padlets
Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and TTOs	AS 2.1: Research Infrastructure and TTO Directory AFR 1: Expert Finder
Events, Conferences, and Workshops	AS 4.1: Event Management and Dissemination AS 4.2: Event Presentation and Registration AS 3.1: Integrated Communication and Follow-up
Accessing Grants and Funding	AS 1.1: Inter-Alliance Data Integration AS 1.5: Research Centralized Link Repository AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers AS 2.4: Database supporting the preparation of new project proposals AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory AS 3.2: Integrated Application and Submission Tools AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking AFR 3: Matchmaking for Funding Programs
Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs	AS 2.2: Centralized Training Offers Directory AS 4.3: Survey Collection Tool AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking

<p>Methodology for an Investment Strategy</p>	<p>AS 1.2: User Engagement and Training</p> <p>AS 1.3: Dissemination and Organizational Endorsement</p> <p>AS 3.3: Effective Communication and Support</p> <p>AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking</p>
<p>Stakeholders' management</p>	<p>AS 2.5: Stakeholder Discovery and Engagement</p> <p>AS 2.6: International Collaboration and Networking</p> <p>AS 3.4: Institutional Support and Transformation</p> <p>AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking</p>
<p>Showcases</p>	<p>AS 1.4: Sharing Best Practices and Teaching Patterns</p> <p>AS 2.7: Course Material and Syllabus Sharing</p> <p>AS 2.8: Visualization of Educational Offers</p> <p>AS 4.4: Content Management</p>

II.7 Appendix 2: Integration levels of Acceleration Services

Acceleration Services	Acceleration Services Results	Agora integration level
Supply of Agoras		Not applicable
Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and TTOs	Unite! Research Infrastructures	1+2
	aUPaEU Aida - AI assistant on EOSC Services	3 or 4
Events, Conferences, and Workshops	Unite! Events	1 or 1+2
Accessing Grants and Funding	Unite! European Funding Opportunities Catalogue	1+2
	Unite! Student Seed Funds Catalogue	1+2
	aUPaEU Aida - AI assistant on EU Fundings	3 or 4
Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs	Unite! Well-being Buddies Catalogue	2 or 3 or 4
	Unite! Research and Innovation Proposals	1+2
	Unite! Find Partners Collaboration	1+2
	Unite! Joint Programmes guidelines Catalogue	2 or 3 or 4
Methodology for an Investment Strategy	Open Experts on acceleration services	1+2
Stakeholders management	aUPaEU Unite! Epicur X Agritech CRM platform	2 or 4
	aUPaEU Stakeholder Management	2 or 4
Showcases	Unite! Faculty and Staff Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! Online Toolkit Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! Speech, Language and AI Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! Community 3 Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! Internships Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! Space Tech Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! SURE Showcase	3 or 4
	Unite! Welcome Centre Showcase	3 or 4

Part III: Schema of access rights for users in the created system

III.1 Introduction

The purpose of Part III of the report is to gather and analyze available methods of authentication and authorization that provide access to IT systems and to identify those most suitable for the Agora of Acceleration Services. The issue of providing a convenient authentication and authorization method in an IT environment is a challenge in the development of any system designed to provide services to users in situations where it is required that these services be available only to specific users with appropriate permissions. In the case of systems such as the Agora of Acceleration Services, where the users represent different actors in the process of enhancing the potential of universities – including researchers, university staff, and representatives of companies collaborating with universities – the development of an authentication system that ensures the sustainability of the solution over the years is crucial. Similarly, the granting of access rights to the acceleration services offered through the Agora must be implemented in a consistent manner that gives service providers full assurance that access is granted only to authorized users.

Part III Schema of access rights for users in the created system refers to the architecture of the Agora of Acceleration Services proposed in *Part II Outline of the intended platform scope*. The discussion and the proposed solution regarding authentication and authorization for acceleration services are consistent with the concept in which the Agora clearly separates the so-called core modules and the acceleration service modules. The core modules are responsible for the functions of the created Agora that should be identical for all users. In this context, the authentication module will be fully part of the core modules. This means that all users of Agora should log in using a single, unified solution. For authorization of access to acceleration services implemented by the acceleration service modules, the scope of access permissions for each service will be defined independently. However, the access rights scheme will be defined within the core modules as a binding template to be applied to all acceleration services integrated into Agora.

III.1.1 Scope of the document

Part III Schema of access rights for users in the created system outlines how users should be authenticated in Agora and how access to acceleration services offered through Agora should be authorized. The document recommends to use existing common identity layers, such as MyAccessID, OpenAIRE AAI, and EOSC AAI, as the authentication methods. Due to sustainability concerns, it is not recommended to directly use Identity Providers (IdP) of institutions acting as providers of acceleration services for Agora but rather to access them through federated services such as EduGain. It is also recommended not to implement proprietary authentication services within Agora but to rely on external IdPs instead. The document also includes a proposal for an authorization system for access to acceleration services, inspired by the method introduced in the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud).

III.1.2 Purpose

The purpose of *Part III Schema of access rights for users in the created system* is to propose a method for authentication and authorization of services within the Agora of Acceleration Services. The solution refers to existing authentication and authorization frameworks, while taking into account the specific needs of the Agora's end users, including researchers and university staff, business representatives, and citizens. The objective of this document is to outline a framework that defines the principles for managing access to services within the Agora. The primary assumption of the proposed approach is to delegate the rules for determining access rights to individual services while maintaining the coherence of the overall solution. This is achieved by ensuring that the Agora provides a unified authentication system and enforcing consistency in access rights management through a unified authorization system imposed by the Agora.

III.2 General problem description

Based on the terminology introduced by Wilson et al. (2022), the events in the lifecycle of an identity are depicted on Figure 1. An identity represents a collection of attributes associated with a specific person or entity in a particular context. For example, an identity might include a name, age, address, or job title for a person, or an IP address, owner, and model number for a device. Identities can include one or more identifiers and provide the basis for authentication (proving who you are) and authorization (determining what you can do). They can vary by context, just as individuals assume different roles in different social or work scenarios.

Figure 1. Events in the Life of an Identity. Source: Wilson et al. (2022).

The challenge of assigning access rights in information systems fundamentally revolves around two distinct activities: authentication and authorization. Authentication verifies a user's identity by requiring credentials, such as a password, security key, or biometric data, that are validated against information provided during account setup. This process ensures that only authorized users can access protected resources. Authorization, on the other hand, determines what an authenticated user can do within the system by granting specific privileges based on attributes such as team membership or subscription level. These permissions can be assigned at the time of account creation or dynamically updated during interactions, especially when accessing data across multiple applications. Both authentication and authorization have been central to the design of information systems and have evolved to meet modern security and usability requirements.

III.2.1 Authentication

Authentication is the process of confirming the identity of a person, device, or entity to ensure that it is who or what it claims to be. In simpler terms, it's a way to make sure that the person or system trying to gain access has the right credentials or proof of identity, such as a

password, fingerprint, or security key. This is a critical step in protecting sensitive information, maintaining security, and ensuring that only authorized individuals or systems have access to certain resources or data.

For example, when you log in to an email account, the system asks for your username and password to verify your identity. If the information matches what is stored in its database, access is granted. Without authentication, anyone could potentially gain unauthorized access to secure systems or data. In IT systems, authentication can range from simple password checks to advanced methods such as biometric scans (e.g., fingerprints, facial recognition) or multi-factor authentication (MFA), which combines two or more verification methods for enhanced security. This document examines various authentication mechanisms and their importance in securing IT systems.

III.2.1.1 Authentication in IT system

Authentication in information systems refers to the process of verifying and confirming the identity of users, devices, or systems attempting to access a network, application, or data. The process ensures that only legitimate entities can interact with protected resources by requiring proof of identity, which can take forms, such as passwords, biometrics, or digital certificates. Authentication is a fundamental layer of security in IT systems that helps maintain integrity, privacy, and controlled access to sensitive information. It is the first step in access management and forms the basis for further authorization processes (see section 2.2).

Although widely used, passwords pose significant security challenges for authentication due to their vulnerability to theft, reuse, and weak password practices. Many users create easily guessable passwords or reuse them across multiple platforms, increasing the risk of unauthorized access through phishing or brute-force attacks. Developers have created solutions like One-Time Passwords (OTPs), Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA), and Step-Up Authentication to tackle these issues. OTPs provide a temporary code for single-use access, making it more difficult for attackers to reuse stolen credentials. MFA adds a layer by requiring multiple forms of verification (such as passwords and biometric scans), significantly increasing security. Step-Up Authentication, meanwhile, dynamically increases the level of authentication based on risk factors, such as unusual user behavior or high-value transactions, providing flexible contextual security that adapts to potential threats. For example, a banking application may allow users to view their account balance with just a password, but if the user attempts to transfer a large amount of money or log in from an unfamiliar device, the application may require additional authentication steps, such as entering an OTP sent to their registered phone or performing a biometric scan. Together, these solutions help reduce password-related vulnerabilities and improve overall system security.

III.2.1.2 Existing approaches

Authentication methods can be categorized by how and where user identity data is created and stored, either internally within the system or externally through federated login and single

sign-on solutions. This section briefly summarizes categorization described by Wilson et al. (2022).

With **internal authentication**, user accounts are managed within the system, with data controlled directly by the organization. There are several ways (not all feasible in case of Agora) to create these accounts, including:

- **Self-registration:** Users independently register, typically by providing basic personal information and creating login credentials.
- **Invitations:** Users receive an invitation from the system or organization, allowing them to create an account and access specific resources.
- **Administrator account creation:** Administrators manually create user accounts, which is common in systems that require centralized management or verification before access.
- **Migration from other systems:** User data is imported from legacy or other systems, allowing seamless transition without individual re-registration.

The Identity Provider (IdP) is a service that creates, maintains, and manages user identity information while authenticating users on behalf of connected applications and services. Acting as a trusted authority, an IdP verifies user credentials and enables secure access to systems without requiring each service to manage identity information independently. This identity management approach simplifies the login process, improves security, and supports authentication mechanisms such as single sign-on (SSO).

The **external authentication** approach uses third-party identity providers to authenticate users, facilitating access across multiple platforms without creating separate accounts for each service. This approach supports single sign-on (SSO) and federated login, increasing convenience and security. Common methods include:

- **Self-registration via social portals:** Users authenticate using existing accounts on social platforms like Facebook or LinkedIn, reducing the need for new credentials.
- **Organizational or company-level authentication:** Within organizations, users can authenticate using services like eduGAIN³ or corporate user repository, centralizing identity management across multiple educational institutions.

³ <https://edugain.org> Accessed: 2024-11-28

- **Governmental authentication:** National or governmental IdPs, such as eIDAS eID^{4,5}, provide verified identities that ensure high security and compliance, particularly useful in systems requiring strong identity assurance.

A significant challenge arises when a system requires integration with multiple IdPs at once. A common identity layer can be implemented, enabling a single access point while preserving individual IdPs' autonomy, enhancing security and user experience, and reducing the complexity of managing multiple identity providers within a single system. An example of such common identity layer is (see also Appendix 3):

- MyAccessID⁶,
- OpenAIRE AAI⁷,
- EOSC AAI⁸.

The common identity layers mentioned above are at varying levels of technological maturity and implementation. The purpose of this document is not to determine their suitability for Agora but to outline the technological frameworks that should be considered when building an authentication system in Agora. It is expected that these common identity layers will evolve dynamically in the near future, making it currently impossible to definitively determine which one will be used in the development of Agora.⁹ MyAccessID is described as a reference point in section 3.1.1, while OpenAIRE AAI and EOSC AAI are detailed in Appendix 3.

In authentication contexts, user identities are often classified based on their level of assurance and security as either strong or weak identities:

- **Weak identities:** Weak identities provide lower levels of security, often relying only on basic credentials such as passwords without additional verification steps. These identities are suitable for low-risk applications where extensive verification is not required.
- **Strong identities:** Strong identities provide high assurance that the user is who they say they are, often through rigorous verification processes and secure credentials.

⁴ <https://eidas.ec.europa.eu/> Accessed: 2024-11-28

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/display/DIGITAL/eIDAS+eID+Profile> Accessed: 2024-11-28

⁶ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID> Accessed: 2024-11-28

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/our-authentication-and-authorisation-infrastructure> Accessed: 2024-11-28

⁸ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8702> Accessed: 2024-11-28

⁹ <https://trustidentity.geant.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Trust-and-Identity-Strategy-2025-2027.pdf> Accessed: 2024-11-28

These are often used for sensitive or high-risk systems and may include MFA, biometric verification, or government-issued digital identities.

It is difficult to assign the system to one of the above classes. For example, authentication through social networks (e.g., LinkedIn) can have features of weak authentication (self-registration and remaining anonymous) as well as strong authentication (MFA). The emphasis on one of these two possible variants should depend on the context and application of the implemented information system.

This structured approach to identity management and authentication enables organizations to tailor their security levels based on the needs of different applications, ensuring both user convenience and robust access control across IT systems.

III.2.2 Authorization

Managing what a user or application can do involves two distinct functions: authorization and access policy enforcement. Authorization refers to the granting of privileges, while access policy enforcement ensures that those privileges are checked and validated before access to a protected resource is allowed.

Authorization can be done in advance or at the time access is requested. It can be handled directly by the resource owner or by a trusted third party, with authorization details securely transmitted to the enforcement point. Enforcement of the access policy occurs at the time of the request and is ideally located close to the resource being protected to prevent evasion. If enforcement is managed separately, the system must be designed so that the protected resource can only be accessed through the enforcement mechanism.

Because policy enforcement is a technical aspect related to system implementation, it is outside the scope of this document. The purpose of this document is to define the principles for granting access rights to resources.

III.2.2.1 Authorization in IT system

Authorization is the process of granting or verifying permissions for users to perform actions within a system. Different approaches to authorization provide different levels of control, flexibility, and security depending on the use case and organizational needs. Wilson et al. (2022) outlines a three-level framework for specifying and applying authorization and access policy enforcement. These are:

Level 1 – Application or API Access:

At this level, the focus is on determining whether an entity should have access to an application or API at all. For example, in an enterprise environment, marketing employees may not have permission to access the accounting system. This level of enforcement is often done externally through mechanisms such as authentication brokers, reverse proxies, or API

gateways that work with identity and access management (IAM) systems to block unauthorized users before they interact with the application.

Level 2 – Functional Access:

This level determines what tasks or functions an entity can perform within an application or API. For example, a junior accountant might be authorized to enter journal entries but not to perform a month-end close, a task reserved for senior staff. Functional access policies, often referred to as "coarse-grained" controls, are typically application-specific and may leverage user roles or groups stored in directory services. These policies are typically enforced within the application or API itself.

Level 3 – Data Access:

This level, also known as "fine-grained" or "granular" access control, determines which specific subsets of data or resources an entity can access. For example, a regional sales manager may have the functional privilege to view sales orders but is restricted to viewing orders for his or her assigned region, as defined by attributes in his or her user profile. Data-level access can be enforced at the application layer or through storage-layer capabilities, such as restricting access to database views or tablespaces.

Authorization in modern systems is accompanied by several challenges, each relevant to different levels of access control:

1. Complexity of Policy Management (Applies to all levels):

Managing policies and roles becomes increasingly difficult as systems scale, especially when dealing with multiple levels of access. For example, defining and maintaining consistent rules for Level 1 (application access), Level 2 (functional access), and Level 3 (data access) can result in complex configurations. This complexity increases the risk of potentially exposing systems to security vulnerabilities, potentially requiring semi or unsupervised audit strategies.

2. Performance Overhead (Primarily Level 2 and Level 3):

Implementing fine-grained controls at Level 3 (data access) or continuous, dynamic checks for Level 2 (functional access) can strain system performance. Efficient mechanisms are essential to balance robust access controls with maintaining seamless user experience.

3. Dynamic and Contextual Access Requirements (All levels, with emphasis on Level 2 and Level 3):

In environments with variable conditions, such as multi-cloud platforms or geographically dispersed teams, Level 2 (functional access) and Level 3 (data access) authorization must adapt in real time. Policies may need to take into account dynamic

attributes such as location, device, or time of access to ensure secure yet flexible operations.

4. Auditing and Compliance (All levels):

Clear records of access activity are critical at all levels, from Level 1 (application access) to Level 3 (data access). Organizations need robust logging and monitoring mechanisms to track who has accessed specific applications, performed specific actions, or retrieved sensitive data. These capabilities are essential for ensuring compliance with regulations and maintaining accountability.

III.2.2.2 Existing approaches

From the perspective of the Agora platform, we should consider the following approaches to authorization:

1. Role-based access control

Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) is a widely used authorization strategy in which users are assigned roles, and each role is granted specific permissions within a system. This model simplifies access management by grouping permissions based on job functions, rather than assigning them individually to each user. When an individual is assigned a role, he or she automatically inherits all associated permissions, ensuring consistency and making onboarding and offboarding processes more efficient. RBAC is typically implemented in organizations with clear hierarchies, such as enterprise environments, where each role is aligned with an employee's responsibilities. For example, an "editor" role in a content management system may have permissions to create, edit, and delete content, while a "viewer" role may only have access to read content.

However, while RBAC's structure is convenient, it can sometimes lack flexibility for complex authorization needs. As organizations grow and diversify, creating roles for every unique responsibility can lead to "role explosion," where an excessive number of roles are needed to cover all scenarios, increasing management complexity. RBAC also may not effectively handle dynamic, attribute-based permissions because it does not natively account for real-time attributes such as location or time. Nonetheless, RBAC remains an effective and manageable approach for many systems, particularly in environments where the tasks and responsibilities associated with each role are well-defined and stable over time.

2. Access control lists

Access Control Lists (ACLs) are another foundational approach to authorization, where permissions are assigned to specific resources, and each resource maintains a list of users or groups that are authorized to access it. In this model, permissions are granted at the resource level, allowing for very granular control over who can interact with each asset. ACLs can be set to allow or deny access based on user identity or group membership, making it possible to

specify exactly who can view, modify, or delete a particular resource. This approach is especially common in systems where resource ownership is critical, such as file systems, where each file or directory has its own ACL defining user access rights.

The main advantage of ACLs is their granularity, which allows administrators to specify access with precision. However, as systems and user bases scale, ACL management can become cumbersome due to the need to maintain permissions at the resource level. Large organizations may need to employ automated tools or maintain role-based policies to streamline ACL management and reduce the administrative overhead. In addition, ACLs do not inherently support dynamic attributes, which can limit their effectiveness in environments that require context-aware access controls, such as those based on location or time of access. Despite these limitations, ACLs are still highly valued for their precision and are widely used in systems where individual resource control is required.

3. Lattice-based access control (label based)

Lattice-Based Access Control, also known as label-based access control, organizes access permissions according to a hierarchy or lattice of security labels. Each user and resource are assigned a label, often denoting a level of classification, such as "Confidential" or "Top Secret," and access is granted based on the relationship between these labels. This model is common in environments that require strict security classifications, such as government or military systems, where resources are sensitive, and only certain people should have access to them. For example, a user with a "Top Secret" label would typically be granted access to lower levels, such as "Confidential" or "Restricted," but not vice versa.

The label-based approach ensures that only authorized users have access to information appropriate to their security clearance, reducing the risk of accidental or unauthorized data exposure. While this model is robust for secure environments, its rigid structure can make it difficult to manage in dynamic, fast-paced systems. Labels must be carefully assigned and maintained, and any mislabeling can compromise security. In addition, lattice-based control does not inherently support context-specific attributes, which limits its flexibility compared to more dynamic models such as ABAC. Nevertheless, lattice-based control remains a staple in high-security environments where hierarchical classification is paramount.

4. Attribute-based access control (policy-based)

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), also known as policy-based access control, determines access based on attributes associated with users, resources, and environmental factors, rather than static roles or lists. In ABAC, policies are written using logical statements that evaluate these attributes to grant or deny access, making it a highly flexible approach. For example, a policy might allow access to a document only if the user is in a particular department, accessing from an approved location, and during working hours. By relying on attributes, ABAC can adapt to different conditions in real-time, making it ideal for today's dynamic environments such as cloud-based applications or multi-tenant systems where users have unique contexts.

The flexibility of this model allows organizations to fine-tune their security policies to ensure that access is appropriate and meets specific requirements. However, this versatility can also make ABAC complex to implement, as administrators must carefully define and test each policy to prevent unintended access. In addition, without proper management, the extensive use of attributes can lead to performance issues when the system must continuously evaluate complex conditions. Despite these challenges, ABAC is highly effective for organizations that require granular, context-aware control, especially in environments where static roles or ACLs do not provide sufficient customization.

Implementations

There are numerous known IT systems that use each of the above approaches, as well as some that employ several of them simultaneously. A sample implementation of a diverse authorization system is presented in Appendix 2, using Odoo – an open source CRM system – as a case study.

III.3 Access rights in Agora platform

When defining how to implement access rights in the Agora platform, two complementary components should be considered:

1. User authentication rules within the system that allow users to log in to the Agora.
2. Access authorization rules for the acceleration services provided through the Agora, allowing users to use the services within the scope defined by the service provider's intentions and the user's needs, as determined by the user's role in the system.

III.3.1 Recommendations for authentication design

When considering the issue of authentication on the target Agora platform, a first point of reference for further consideration is the European solution that has already been developed for the provision of broadly defined digital services. A new iteration of the European Open Science Cloud – EOSC EU Node¹⁰ – was launched in October 2024, providing the academic community and EU citizens with services such as file sync and share, interactive notebooks, large file transfer, virtual machines, cloud container platform, and bulk data transfer. MyAccessID Identity and Access Management Service¹¹ is used as a part of the authentication step. Below on Figure 2 is a logic diagram of MyAccessID:

¹⁰ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu> Accessed: 2024-11-28

¹¹ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID> Accessed: 2024-11-28

Figure 2. MyAccessID schema. Source: <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/> (accessed: 2024-11-28)

MyAccessID is a common Identity Layer, being an intermediary between Identity Providers (IdPs) such as eduGAIN¹², eIDAS eIDs^{13,14} and other IdPs and infrastructure services. During authentication, a user can select their IdP, which allows the creation of a unique and persistent account on the target platform with the appropriate permissions based on the selected IdP.

¹² <https://edugain.org> Accessed: 2024-11-28

¹³ <https://eidas.ec.europa.eu/> Accessed: 2024-11-28

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/display/DIGITAL/eIDAS+eID+Profile> Accessed: 2024-11-28

Considering the case of EOSC EU Node, selecting the appropriate IdP (or remaining unauthenticated) involves automatic assignment to one of four Access Groups¹⁵ with a hierarchical structure. Remaining a non-authenticated user provides the ability to view general information about the platform and services; authentication through one of the eIDAS eIDs or self-registration through EU Login¹⁶ provides the ability to personalize the user space, while institutional or academic group affiliation derived from domain attributes and affiliations in eduGAIN and EU Login allows use of EOSC EU Node services (the researchers have the most privileges). **A technological solution using the common identity layer, e.g. multi-tenant authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI) such as MyAccessID or other like OpenAIRE AAI or EOSC AAI, is recommended as a basis for future Agora implementations,** as it also solves the typical problem of choosing the attribute used to identify a user (see Appendix 3). These systems may evolve and change in the future.¹⁷ Therefore, for the sake of sustainability, it is recommended that when building the authentication system in Agora, the currently developed common identity layers be analyzed and considered.

Different ways of authentication by IdPs in the EOSC EU Node lead to the creation of unlinked accounts of the same person. The hierarchical privilege structure solves this problem, as the user always authenticates through the IdP, which provides the most privileges. Suppose a particular Agora deployment does not use a hierarchical privilege structure. In that case, it is necessary to add functionality to link authenticated accounts together to increase the usability of the system since it is likely that a user will appear on Agora in different roles with disjointed privileges. The prospect of additional programming overhead is an argument for using a hierarchical privilege structure.

If acceleration services rely on sophisticated user roles that cannot be derived from IdP (e.g., eduGAIN¹⁸), one should expect that in a given Agora deployment, there will be an increased workload for administrators to assign permissions/roles manually. It is recommended that user roles can be derived automatically during the authentication process.

From the point of view of the target Agora platform, the solution used in the EOSC EU Node covers authentication well from stakeholder groups such as academia, EU authorities, and EU citizens. The challenge is to include business and local/national authorities. Manual handling of role assignments may be sufficient for a few users or serving only representatives within these groups. For acceleration services aimed toward a high number of users from these

¹⁵ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/system/files?file=2024-10/EOSC-EU-Node-User-Access-Policy-v1.0.pdf> Accessed: 2024-11-28

¹⁶ https://trusted-digital-identity.europa.eu/index_en Accessed: 2024-11-28

¹⁷ <https://trustidentity.geant.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Trust-and-Identity-Strategy-2025-2027.pdf> Accessed: 2024-11-28

¹⁸ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/eduGAIN/IDP+Attribute+Profile+and+Recommended+Attributes> Accessed: 2024-11-28

groups, it may be necessary to incorporate external IdPs, which may incur programming costs. It is recommended that such target forms of authentication be chosen to minimize implementation costs on Agora's part.

Particular attention should be given to the problem of self-registration of individuals. Allowing authentication through community platforms (such as Facebook, Google, LinkedIn, etc.) will result in de facto anonymous use of Agora. This could threaten Agora's sustainability due to the increased cost of moderation of acceleration services intended for citizens who anonymously could lead to abuse. The decision to make community platforms IdPs available must be made within a given Agora deployment. If such an option is made available, it is recommended that it be integrated with the EU Login service.¹⁹ **In general, it is discouraged to include community platforms IdPs and choosing IdPs providing the most elements related to the strong identity is recommended.**

Since the Agora may contain data of unique intellectual value, additional layers of authentication such as OTP, MFA, or Step-Up Authentication are recommended as part of the specifics of a given acceleration service. A good reference example of implementing an MFA solution in an HEI environment is the MySCC platform (see Appendix 1).

One possible approach is to implement proprietary authentication services within Agora, such as an internal Agora IdP, or to use local authentication services provided by HEIs. However, **implementing proprietary authentication services within Agora is not recommended** due to sustainability concerns related to the solution being developed. This is due to the different life cycles of these systems (i.e., Agora instances and local HEI systems). In addition, there are already existing systems that provide federated authentication, and there will be multiple such systems available rather than relying on a single one.

III.3.2 Recommendations for access authorization design

Due to the architecture of Agora, where all acceleration services are separated, it is assumed that access authorization rights for individual services will be defined independently for each acceleration service. Given the user hierarchy that emerges from the analysis of the personas defined in document "Part II: Outline of the intended platform scope", it is assumed that a lattice-based access control model will be used to describe access authorization rights for acceleration services in Agora. This approach is based on the belief that the hierarchy of user categories using Agora will remain stable and that the lattice-based access model will be relatively easy to implement. The policy for granting permissions is inspired by the EOSC EU Node User Access Policy. To provide a clear and structured approach, access groups and their corresponding access rights will be defined in detail. These groups will distinguish between

¹⁹ Cf. <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/cas/userdata/myAccount.cgi> Accessed: 2024-11-28

regular users on the one hand, and acceleration service providers and administrators on the other, reflecting the different roles and responsibilities within the platform.

1. Access groups (users)

The following sub-sections define the access groups used within the Acceleration Services embedded in Agora, and the corresponding access rights that apply specifically to Agora users. These are collectively referred to as "Acceleration Service Users" (ASU-x).

1.1. Access group ASU-0 (Public View)

Access group ASU-0 includes all users who are not authenticated (i.e., not logged in). This group has open access to publicly available content on Agora.

1.2. Access group ASU-A (Citizen View)

The ASU-A access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been identified as EU citizens. They are granted access to those acceleration services where specific services are indicated as available to users with ASU-A access rights.

1.2.1. Access Group ASU-A-CDA (Citizen Credit Driven Access View)

The ASU-A-CDA access group is assigned the same rights as the ASU-A group, except that access to services is restricted only if the user has the appropriate credits. The credit access policy is defined by the acceleration service provider.

1.3. Access Group ASU-A1 (Administration Authority View)

The ASU-A1 access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been identified as an administration authority. They are granted access to those acceleration services where specific services are indicated as available to users with ASU-A1 access rights.

1.3.1. Access Group ASU-A1-CDA (Administration Authority Credit Driven Access View)

The ASU-A1-CDA access group is assigned the same rights as the ASU-A1 group, except that access to services is restricted only if the user has the appropriate credits. The credit access policy is defined by the acceleration service provider.

1.4. Access Group ASU-A2 (Business View)

The ASU-A1 access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been identified as a business user. They are granted access to those acceleration services where specific services are indicated as available to users with ASU-A2 access rights.

1.4.1. Access Group ASU-A2-CDA (Business Credit Driven Access View)

The ASU-A2-CDA access group is assigned the same rights as the ASU-A2 group, except that access to services is restricted only if the user has the appropriate credits. The credit access policy is defined by the acceleration service provider.

1.5. Access Group ASU-B (Academia View)

The ASU-B access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been identified as HEI staff, but not researchers or authorities. They are granted access to those acceleration services where specific services are indicated as available to users with ASU-B access rights.

1.5.1. Access Group ASU-B-CDA (Academia Credit Driven Access View)

The ASU-B-CDA access group is assigned the same rights as the ASU-B group, except that access to services is restricted only if the user has the appropriate credits. The credit access policy is defined by the acceleration service provider.

1.6. Access Group ASU-B1 (Researcher View)

The ASU-B1 access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been identified as HEI researchers. They are granted access to those acceleration services where specific services are indicated as available to users with ASU-B1 access rights.

1.6.1. Access Group ASU-B1-CDA (Researcher Credit Driven Access View)

The ASU-B1-CDA access group is assigned the same rights as the ASU-B1 group, except that access to services is restricted only if the user has the appropriate credits. The credit access policy is defined by the acceleration service provider.

1.7. Access Group ASU-B2 (Academia Authority View)

The ASU-B2 access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been identified as HEI authorities. They are granted access to those acceleration services where specific services are indicated as available to users with ASU-B2 access rights.

1.7.1. Access Group ASU-B2-CDA (Academia Authority Credit Driven Access View)

The ASU-B2-CDA access group is assigned the same rights as the ASU-B2 group, except that access to services is restricted only if the user has the appropriate credits. The credit access policy is defined by the acceleration service provider.

2. Access groups (acceleration service providers and administrators)

The following sections define the access groups used within the Acceleration Services embedded in Agora, and the corresponding access rights that apply specifically to Acceleration Service providers and Agora administrators. These are collectively referred to as "Acceleration Service Administrators" (ASA-x).

2.1. Access Group ASA-A (Acceleration Service Provider View)

The ASA-A access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been granted the right to manage a specific acceleration service. The scope of actions that a user can perform under this right is defined independently for each acceleration service. For each Acceleration Service, these permissions will vary.

2.2. Access Group ASA-A-API (Acceleration Service API Provider View)

The ASA-A-API access group includes a specific and specially designated situation where an acceleration service is fully automated and involves presenting data on Agora obtained through an external API. In most cases, such services will relate to acceleration services of the Exploration type. In the case of such services, the scope of permissions will depend on the configuration of the API used and the decisions made by the provider of that API.

2.3. Access Group ASA-B (Agora Administrator View)

The ASA-B access group includes users who have successfully authenticated and have been granted the right to manage all acceleration services provided by Agora. This permission is reserved for users who act as Agora administrators, allowing them to manage everything available on the platform.

3. Access rights

The modular architecture of Agora ensures that permissions for different user groups vary depending on the type of acceleration service they wish to use. Permissions will differ based on the technical module upon which each acceleration service is built.

3.1. Access rights for acceleration services built using Agora's presentation modules (acceleration service integration level 0)

Presentation type acceleration services are designed to display all the acceleration services available to the user on the Agora platform. Two predefined modules embedded in Agora serve this purpose: the Dashboard and the Acceleration Service Directory (AS Directory). The Dashboard is the main access point to the Agora and allows the user to personalize his or her interaction with the platform. The AS Directory is a module that contains a list of all the acceleration services available on the Agora. In each of these tools, the user can only access information about acceleration services hosted on the Agora if he or she has been assigned the appropriate permissions for a specific acceleration service.

Table 1. *Access rights to present acceleration services to the user in the Dashboard module.*

Access right	Access group	Description
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Acceleration service integration level 1 (Exploration modules)		
Create / Delete / Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA /ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B /ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ ASU-B2-CDA	Display Acceleration Services built using Internal Data Visualization or External Data Visualization modules that contain at least one piece of data shared by the Acceleration Service that the user has the right to retrieve.
Acceleration service integration level 2 (Relationship modules)		
Create / Delete / Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA /ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B /ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ ASU-B2-CDA	Display Acceleration Services built using Relationship Management module that contain at least one AS relationship process that the user has the right to retrieve.
Acceleration service integration level 3/4 (Partial workflow management modules)		
Create / Delete / Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA /ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B /ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ ASU-B2-CDA	Display Acceleration Services built using Partial Workflow Management module or Comprehensive Workflow Management module that contain at least one AS workflow process that the user has the right to retrieve.

Table 2. Access rights to present acceleration services to the user in the AS directory module:

Access right	Access group	Description
Acceleration service integration level 1 (Exploration modules)		

Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA /ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B /ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ ASU-B2-CDA	Display Acceleration Services built using Internal Data Visualization or External Data Visualization modules that contain at least one piece of data shared by the Acceleration Service that the user has the right to retrieve.
Acceleration service integration level 2 (Relationship modules)		
Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA /ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B /ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ ASU-B2-CDA	Display Acceleration Services built using Relationship Management module that contains at least one AS relationship process that the user has the right to retrieve.
Acceleration service integration level 3/4 (Partial workflow management modules)		
Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA /ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B /ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ ASU-B2-CDA	Display Acceleration Services built using Partial Workflow Management module or Comprehensive Workflow Management module that contain at least one AS workflow process that the user has the right to retrieve.

3.2. Access rights for acceleration services built using Agora's Exploration modules (acceleration service integration level 1)

Acceleration services of the Exploration type are built using either the internal data visualization module or the external data visualization module. In the first case, the data provided by the acceleration service is stored directly on the Agora, while in the second case it is retrieved in real time from an external IT system via an API. Permissions for these types of acceleration services therefore involve determining who has access to the data provided by a given acceleration service and to what extent.

Table 3. Access rights for data provided through acceleration services built using Internal Data Visualization modules.

Access right	Access group	Description
Create	ASA-A/ASA-B	Creation of data provided within the Acceleration Service
Edit	ASA-A/ASA-B	Modification of data provided within the Acceleration Service
Delete	ASA-A/ASA-B	Deletion of data provided within the Acceleration Service
Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Browse the resources of the Acceleration Service, i.e., access the data made available by the Acceleration Service
Read A1	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Access to the metadata of the data provided by the Acceleration Service
Read A2	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Access to the metadata of the data provided by the Acceleration Service and full access to the data
Execute	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-	Ability to activate links embedded in the data

	CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2- CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B- CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1- CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	provided by the acceleration service. Optionally, access authorization to the services provided through the link can be considered according to the permissions assigned to the access group to which the user belongs in Agora.
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Table 4. Access rights for data provided through acceleration services built using External Data Visualization modules.

Access right	Access group	Description
Create	ASA-A/ASA-A-API/ASA-B	Creation of data provided within the Acceleration Service
Edit	ASA-A/ASA-A-API/ASA-B	Modification of data provided within the Acceleration Service
Delete	ASA-A/ASA-A-API/ASA-B	Deletion of data provided within the Acceleration Service
Retrieve	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A1/ASU-A2/ASU-B/ASU-B1/ASU-B2	Browse the resources of the Acceleration Service, i.e., access the data made available by the Acceleration Service
Read A1	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Access to the metadata of the data provided by the Acceleration Service

Read A2	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Access to the metadata of the data provided by the Acceleration Service and full access to the data
Execute	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Ability to activate links embedded in the data provided by the acceleration service. Optionally, access authorization to the services provided through the link can be considered according to the permissions assigned to the access group to which the user belongs in Agora.

3.3. Access rights for acceleration services built using Agora's Relationship modules (acceleration service integration level 2)

Acceleration services of the Relationship type are built using the AS Relationship Management module. This module makes use of the functionality provided by the CRM Engine module. This means that in this type of acceleration service, users have access to processes that are defined based on the CRM approach, such as, but not limited to, managing the process of establishing and maintaining communication between the service provider and its beneficiary. This relationship is a response to a real need that the acceleration service is designed to address.

Table 5. Access rights for Acceleration service relationship processes (AS relationship processes) provided through acceleration services built using AS Relationship Management modules.

Access right	Access group	Description
Create	ASA-A/ASA-B	Creation of AS relationship process provided within the Acceleration Service

Edit	ASA-A/ASA-B	Modification of AS relationship process provided within the Acceleration Service
Delete	ASA-A/ASA-B	Deletion of AS relationship process provided within the Acceleration Service
Retrieve / Read / Execute	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Ability to search/read/execute the AS relationship process

3.4. Access rights for acceleration services built using Agora's Execution modules (acceleration service integration level 3 and level 4)

Acceleration services of the Execution type are created using either the Partial Workflow Management module or the Comprehensive Workflow Management module. In the first case, the Agora is used to handle some of the business processes defined for a given Acceleration Service, while in the second case all business processes are managed on the Agora. Regardless of the level of immersion (integration) of a given acceleration service within the Agora (level 3 or level 4), it is assumed that the services are implemented using custom modules, i.e. modules that have been completely developed to support the given acceleration service. In any case, users of such an acceleration service will have access to one or more acceleration service workflows (AS workflows) that are defined within that specific acceleration service setup.

Table 6. Access rights for Acceleration service workflow processes (AS workflow processes) provided through acceleration services built using Partial Workflow Management module or Comprehensive Workflow Management module.

Access right	Access group	Description
Create	ASA-A/ASA-B	Creation of AS workflow process provided within the Acceleration Service

Edit	ASA-A/ASA-B	Modification of AS workflow process provided within the Acceleration Service
Delete	ASA-A/ASA-B	Deletion of AS workflow process provided within the Acceleration Service
Retrieve / Read / Execute	ASU-0/ASU-A/ASU-A-CDA/ASU-A1/ASU-A1-CDA/ASU-A2/ASU-A2-CDA/ASU-B/ASU-B-CDA/ASU-B1/ASU-B1-CDA/ASU-B2/ASU-B2-CDA	Ability to search/read/execute the AS workflow process

4. Management of acceleration services and data by users

To manage access to acceleration services in Agora, it is worth considering the introduction of a component that allows users to decide which of the available acceleration services (based on their granted permissions) they want to activate and use. This module could be based on the philosophy proposed in MySCC (see Appendix 1), which allows users the ability to visualize and manage the services offered on the platform. For Agora, such a module would support the customization of service presentation in the Dashboard and AS Directory (see: “Part II: Outline of the intended platform scope”).

This module should also be used to allow users to consent to the processing of the data they generate in other Agora modules, including by the intelligent search functionality. According to GDPR, system users in the European Union have the right to decide about the visibility of the data they generate. For more information on this topic in the context of intelligent search can be found in section 3.1.3.

III.3.3 Intelligent search considerations

Intelligent Search on the Agora platform refers to an advanced search capability designed to enhance the user experience by delivering accurate, relevant, and context-aware results. Intelligent Search enables users to efficiently locate information, services, or resources across the platform. This feature is particularly valuable for navigating complex data sets, connecting users to the most relevant acceleration services, and facilitating seamless collaboration within the Agora ecosystem. By understanding user intent and adapting to individual needs,

Intelligent Search plays a critical role in maximizing the accessibility and functionality of the platform.

As the Agora platform includes an Intelligent Search component, it is necessary to take into consideration authorization requirements arising from:

3. the access restrictions imposed by the data suppliers,
4. the platform being used as an information retrieval system,
5. the intelligent search capabilities being implemented with the use of AI models.

In order to maintain information security, it is crucial that all access restrictions imposed by the data providers are preserved during searches. However, given that the data that populates the Agora platform comes from a diverse range of providers that implement different and potentially incompatible authorization schemes, it is not feasible to assume that peculiarities of a particular data supplier's access rights organization will be directly incorporated in the Intelligent Search component. Therefore, we recommend that the data providers define access rights for their data according to the authorization scheme of the Agora platform in order to be present in the search results. In addition, to ensure accountability and auditability the records of access rights being granted or revoked by the data provider should be maintained.

As an information retrieval system, Agora's Intelligent Search component must control access rights at the document level. In terms of information retrieval a document is any piece of information that can potentially be indexed by the search engine, so if the data provider wants to split the complex "document" such as a grant proposal into separate parts to gain more fine-grained control over the indexing or access control it should be possible but the relationship between the origin and its parts should be specified by the data provider. Considering that the data access rights granted by the supplier and the authorization rules maintained by the Agora platform may change dynamically the Intelligent Search component must respect both at the time of populating the search index with the data from the supplier and at the time of submitting a query by the user.

Since intelligent search capabilities rely on the integration of AI models into the platform, it is necessary to determine if and how the models access the data provided. Semantic search engines rely on the use of a single word embedding model to index and retrieve documents. Modern intelligent search systems that follow the Retrieval Augmented Generation (Lewis et al.; 2020) architecture use two neural models to perform the retrieval task: an embeddings model for the retrieval phase and a large language model for the response generation phase. Each AI model to be incorporated into the Intelligent Search component must be analyzed separately and, depending on its origin, different authorization rules must be considered. There are three main categories of the models to be investigated:

1. The models that are accessible via API.
2. The models from external vendors hosted internally as an integral part of the Agora platform.

3. The models trained or fine-tuned internally on the basis of the data provided by the suppliers.

The first category requires careful consideration, as it involves sending the data provided by the suppliers outside of the Agora platform. Models in this category must comply not only with the access restrictions imposed by the data suppliers, but also with the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)²⁰. We therefore recommend that data suppliers specify on a case-by-case basis whether and which data can be made available to externally hosted models.

Models from external vendors that comply with the AI Act²¹, are hosted internally, and have not been modified using data provided by the suppliers are safe to use. However, any data provided to the model should be authorized as in the case of any ordinal information retrieval system.

The third category requires a fine-grained control of access rights. First, the data suppliers should specify if and what data, if any, can be used to improve Agora's Intelligent Search. Second, all data that were used to train or fine-tune the model must be tracked individually so that access to the model can be prohibited, if the data supplier revokes access to the data. Finally, the architecture and purpose of the model should be recorded on the Agora platform and preserved in the form of a model card. If the access to the data is revoked by the user, then there is a potential risk of data leakage from the language generation model, but there is no such a risk in the case of the fine-tuned embedding model which is used only to retrieve documents from the index, which are then checked for access rights afterwards. Thus, the decision to revoke user access to the model depends not only on the data authorization status, but also on the model architecture and purpose.

III.4 Conclusions

A key takeaway from this text is the strong recommendation to use a common identity layer (e.g., MyAccessID, OpenAIRE AAI, EOSC AAI) when building authentication system of the Agora platform, as it ensures sustainability, reduces maintenance overhead, and accommodates different user groups (academic, business, authorities, citizens). Adopting a hierarchical privilege structure helps unify multiple IdP-based accounts, while additional features such as MFA or Step-Up Authentication can be introduced for sensitive use cases. Although self-registration or community platform IdPs (e.g., Facebook, Google, LinkedIn) can expand user access, they risk increased anonymity and potential abuse, thus making strong identity providers (e.g. eIDAS eIDs or institutional IdPs federated under eduGAIN) preferable. Ultimately, the implementation of a proprietary Agora IdP is discouraged due to mismatched

²⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj> Accessed: 2024-11-28

²¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai> Accessed: 2024-11-28

lifecycles and higher maintenance costs, reinforcing the value of existing federated solutions for secure and scalable authentication.

Agora's acceleration services are recommended to use the lattice-based access control model, which allows for differentiated access rights according to user roles and hierarchies, including credit-based permissions where applicable. This model supports the platform's modular architecture, ensuring that each service can independently define its own authorization rules while maintaining consistency across all services. The introduction of structured access groups – for both end users (ASU) and service administrators (ASA) – highlights the need for granular controls, from unauthenticated users (ASU-0) up to full Agora administrators (ASA-B).

Intelligent Search on the Agora platform must respect data provider access restrictions during document indexing and retrieval, and incorporate authorization checks at both indexing and query time. Because suppliers may define different and potentially incompatible authorization schemes, they should align their data access rights with Agora's framework to ensure proper document-level control. In addition, the integration of AI models—whether accessed via external APIs, hosted internally, or trained/fine-tuned using supplier data—requires careful governance to ensure GDPR compliance and respect for rights revocation. Suppliers must specify whether their data can be transferred to external models, and any internally fine-tuned model should be accompanied by a clear record of what data contributed to its training, allowing access to be revoked if necessary.

III.5 Appendix 1: MySCC as an example of a permission management system implementation in HEI

The KIT MySCC platform²² is a self-service portal for students, employees, guests, and partners. It is a good practice model of IT management that enhances security and user autonomy. After activating their KIT account, users can access self-service functions through a centralized login page for IT services, using the SSO system. This centralized access simplifies administration and ensures secure authentication across multiple services.

MySCC provides users with personalized features, including detailed information about their KIT account and associated services, the ability to change their account password, set up email forwarding, and configure multi-factor authentication (MFA). The password change feature is critical to maintaining account security, as it enables users to regularly update their credentials on their own, reducing the risk of unauthorized access. In addition, the MFA

²² <https://my.scc.kit.edu> Accessed: 2024-11-28

configuration option adds an extra layer of protection by requiring a second form of verification, further securing user accounts against potential threats.

This combination of self-managed security features and data transparency allows users to protect their accounts and actively control their data. By reducing the need for administrative intervention, MySCC lowers operating costs and supports a sustainable IT environment.

III.6 Appendix 2: Permission system in Odoo as an example of a technical approach to permission model implementation

Odoo is a comprehensive business management software that integrates various applications to help organizations streamline their operations. One of the critical components of such a system is the permissions model, that governs how users access data and perform actions within the software. Odoo's permissions system is an excellent example of a technical approach to implementing a robust and flexible permissions model.

At its core, Odoo's permissions system is designed to control user access at multiple levels, ensuring that each user has the appropriate rights to perform their duties without compromising the integrity or security of the system. The framework is hierarchical and consists of several key elements:

User Groups (RBAC)

Users in Odoo are organized into groups based on their roles and responsibilities within the organization. These groups simplify permission management by allowing administrators to assign permissions to groups rather than individual users. For example, all members of the sales team can be part of a "Sales" group with specific access rights relevant to their roles.

Access Rights (ACL)

Access rights determine what actions users can perform on different types of records or data models in the system. These rights include the ability to create, read, write, or delete records. By setting access rights at the group level, Odoo ensures that users have the necessary permissions according to their job functions.

Record Rules (ABAC)

While access rights control general permissions, record rules provide more granular control by specifying which individual records a user can access within a model. For example, a salesperson may only be able to view the sales orders for which he or she is responsible, rather than all sales orders in the system. Record rules use conditions to dynamically filter data based on user-specific criteria.

Field-Level Security (ABAC)

Odoo's permissions system also allows administrators to control access to specific fields within a record. This means that sensitive information, such as financial details or personal data, can be restricted to certain groups or made read-only, even if users have access to the entire record.

Odoo's permissions system provides a comprehensive and flexible approach to managing user access in complex software applications. By combining group-based permissions, access rights (ACL), record rules, and field-level security, it ensures that users have the appropriate access to perform their roles effectively while maintaining strict control over sensitive data.

III.7 Appendix 3: OpenAIRE AAI and EOSC AAI as an example of common identity layer

Integrating multiple Identity Providers (IdPs) into a single system presents significant challenges, primarily due to the different protocols, standards, and security policies that each IdP may employ (AARC, 2019). This complexity can lead to fragmented user experiences, increased security vulnerabilities, and the administrative overhead of managing disparate authentication mechanisms. Organizations often struggle to provide seamless access to resources while maintaining the autonomy and specific configurations of each IdP.

Implementing a common identity layer addresses these challenges by acting as an intermediary between the system and the multiple IdPs (Figure 3). This layer consolidates authentication protocols and standardizes the interaction, allowing users to access resources through a single access point regardless of their original IdP. It preserves the autonomy of individual IdPs by accommodating their unique attributes and security policies within a unified framework. This approach not only streamlines authentication processes but also simplifies the management of user identities and access rights.

By adopting a common identity layer, systems improve security through centralized monitoring and consistent enforcement of access policies. Users benefit from an improved experience through simplified login procedures and reduced need to manage multiple credentials. In addition, administrators experience reduced complexity in managing the system because the common identity layer abstracts the intricacies of interfacing with multiple IdPs. Overall, this solution promotes a more secure, efficient, and user-friendly environment for integrating multiple identity providers.

Figure 3. Integrating multiple Identity Providers (IdPs) into a single system. Source: European Commission (2021).

OpenAIRE AAI implements a common identity layer by integrating multiple Identity Providers (IdPs) into a single, cohesive authentication and authorization infrastructure (Figure 4). It leverages eduGAIN, the global network of academic identity federations, to provide researchers with seamless access using their institutional credentials. For those outside of academia – such as industry professionals or citizen scientists – OpenAIRE AAI extends support to other trusted authentication providers such as social networks, community identity providers, and platforms like ORCID. This inclusivity ensures that users from diverse backgrounds can access resources through a unified system without compromising the autonomy of their preferred IdPs.

The infrastructure uses widely adopted protocols such as OpenID Connect and SAML to facilitate secure communication between services and IdPs. In this way, OpenAIRE AAI standardizes the authentication process, allowing services to authenticate and identify users through a single access point. It respects the unique attributes and security policies of each IdP, effectively preserving their autonomy within the unified framework. Users are organized into groups, assigned roles, and their access rights are centrally managed, simplifying the complexity typically associated with dealing with multiple identity providers.

OpenAIRE AAI also enhances security by enabling centralized monitoring and consistent enforcement of access policies across all connected IdPs. This centralization reduces potential security gaps that can arise from managing disparate authentication systems. Users enjoy an improved experience through streamlined sign-on procedures, using only their existing credentials to access multiple services. Administrators benefit from reduced complexity in managing user identities and access rights, as the common identity layer abstracts the intricacies of interfacing with multiple IdPs. Overall, OpenAIRE AAI effectively realizes a secure, efficient, and user-friendly environment by implementing a common identity layer that integrates multiple identity providers.

Figure 4. OpenAIRE approach to providing a common identity layer. Source: Liampotis (2022).

The OpenAIRE AAI must support horizontal access across different research and e-infrastructures in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The challenge is to find a way to integrate AAI services across different infrastructures and to provide research communities with the support they need to securely share data and resources.

The OpenAIRE AAI has already been connected to the EOSC Portal AAI which is the Infrastructure Proxy service for the EOSC Core (EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy).

The integration of the OpenAIRE AAI with the EOSC AAI reflects a joint effort to create a seamless authentication and authorization infrastructure within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The EOSC AAI serves as a federated system designed to unify various research and e-infrastructure services under a single access framework. As a Community AAI, the OpenAIRE AAI, functions to manage community-specific attributes, allowing researchers to

authenticate and access resources using institutional or community-provided credentials. This alignment with the EOSC AAI ensures that the OpenAIRE services are interoperable with other EOSC services, fostering broader collaboration and simplifying user access to distributed resources.

The relationship between the two is facilitated by the EOSC Portal AAI, which acts as an Infrastructure Proxy. This proxy enables OpenAIRE AAI to securely integrate with other EOSC Core services. In this way, OpenAIRE AAI leverages the centralized governance and interoperability standards of the EOSC AAI while retaining the ability to manage community-specific identities and access protocols. This integration reduces administrative complexity for users, increases security through standardized policies, and enables scalable access to a wide range of services within the EOSC ecosystem.

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Part IV: Idea of intelligent search approach for effective collaboration

IV.1 Introduction

Providing intelligent search capabilities as part of the Agora platform is crucial for fostering collaboration between Higher Education Institutions in the European Union. The goal of this document is to provide an overview of methods of intelligent information search that can be integrated into the platform to improve the process of building international research teams and effectively searching the Agora's resources to meet individual needs. To assure that the methods incorporated into Agora lead to effective collaboration we characterize key usage scenarios for intelligent search and analyze feasible search architectures. We discuss regulatory considerations and formulate recommendations for integrating search systems into the platform.

IV.2 Requirements Analysis

IV.2.1 Search scenarios

The goal of Intelligent Search in the Agora platform is to enable effective collaboration and help users efficiently search Agora's resources to meet their individual needs. In pursuit of this objective, we identified a set of usage scenarios that have to be realized by the search engine to qualify for integration into Agora. This section presents a high-level description of the scenarios along with the justification to include them and the characterization of the stakeholders. The scenarios address diverse user needs resulting from the varied nature of acceleration services embedded in Agora. The division takes into account the nature of the acceleration services expressed by their level of integration within Agora (see *Part II: Outline of the intended platform scope*). The operationalization of the presented scenarios is discussed in Section 5 Recommendations.

IV.2.1.1 Search scenarios for acceleration services built using Agora's Presentation modules (acceleration service integration level 0)

SS 1.1: Surface search in the acceleration services catalog

Summary: Searching the acceleration services catalog at a basic Level.

Description: The search includes situations where a user with a minimal set of access permissions for a given acceleration service should receive information in the search results indicating that such a service is offered on Agora. This means that the metadata describing the acceleration service should contain as much information as possible about the scope of the service, so that the search engine can retrieve this service based on a variety of user queries.

Data involved: Metadata of acceleration services.

SS 1.2: In-depth search in the acceleration services catalog

Summary: Searching the acceleration services catalog with full data access.

Description: The search applies to users who have full access rights to the data collected within an acceleration service. This means that in addition to having access to the metadata describing a given service, the requesting user also has the right to retrieve any data that he or she has participated in collecting within the given acceleration service.

A variant of this scenario includes acceleration services where the user, while searching for an acceleration service, also has access to data generated by other users. However, this variant may lead to violations of the GDPR and the AI Act, which makes its implementation in the EU challenging.

Data involved: Metadata and all collected data within acceleration services

IV.2.1.2 Search scenarios for acceleration services built using Agora's Exploration modules (acceleration service integration level 1)

SS 2.1: Surface Search of the Data Catalog Constituting an Acceleration Service

Summary: Basic-level search of a data catalog that constitutes an acceleration service.

Description: The search applies to scenarios where a user wants to browse a catalog that is an integral part of an exploration-type acceleration service. In the basic case considered, the user has permissions limited to searching the metadata of entities stored in the catalog.

Therefore, the metadata describing the stored data should be as detailed as possible to accurately reflect the content of the core data associated with a given entity. This ensures that

users with restricted data access can still obtain the necessary information when searching the Agora

Data involved: Metadata of the data stored in the catalog.

SS 2.2: In-depth Search of the Data Catalog Constituting an Acceleration Service

Summary: Full-access search of a data catalog that constitutes an acceleration service.

Description: The search applies to scenarios where a user wants to browse a catalog that is an integral part of an exploration-type acceleration service. In the extended case, the user has access not only to the metadata of entities stored in the catalog but also to all data associated with each entity.

Since the search engine has full access to all data in the catalog, the user is guaranteed to find the desired information. In this approach, the quality of metadata descriptions is less critical than in the simplified case. Instead, the effectiveness of the search depends entirely on the quality of the information stored in the catalog.

Data involved: Metadata and data stored in the catalog.

IV.2.1.3 Search scenarios for acceleration services built using Agora's Relationship modules (acceleration service integration level 2)

SS 3.1: In-depth Search within the Relationship Processes of the Acceleration Service

Summary: Full-access search of data appearing in the relationship process.

Description: The search applies to scenarios where a user wants to browse the relationship process they are involved in during an Acceleration Service. This process follows a CRM approach and typically involves managing communication between the service provider and the beneficiary. During this communication, messages and documents are exchanged and searched in response to user queries.

In this scenario, it is assumed that the search engine has full access to the messages and documents collected within a single relationship process (i.e. it has the right to retrieve them). This means that during a search, the search engine should not access messages and documents from other relationship processes that are stored in the Agora as part of the given acceleration service, as they belong to other users.

This scenario is designed to improve the user experience when interacting within the Agora platform. Such queries are expected to be generated as part of user-initiated requests while working within the relationship process associated with the Acceleration Service - for example, when drafting another message to the other party in a communication exchange.

Data involved: Messages and documents related to the relationship process.

IV.2.1.4 Search scenarios for acceleration services built using Agora's Execution modules (acceleration service integration level 3 and level 4)

SS 4.1: In-depth Search within the Workflow Processes of the Acceleration Service

Summary: Full-access search of data appearing in the workflow process.

Description: The search applies to scenarios where a user wants to browse the workflow process they are involved in during an Acceleration Service. This process follows a logic that results from the way the acceleration service has been built and integrated into the Agora at the highest levels, i.e. level 3 or 4. Services at this level of integration are highly advanced and have been embedded into Agora to handle complex business processes. These processes may include submitting documents to the system, commenting on them, assigning different statuses, adding different types of reviews, and exchanging them between process participants. During this communication, all workflow-related notes and documents are searched in response to user queries.

In this scenario, it is assumed that the search engine has full access to the notes and documents collected within a single workflow process (i.e. it has the right to retrieve them). This means that during a search, the search engine should not access notes and documents from other workflow processes that are stored in the Agora as part of the given acceleration service, as they belong to other users.

This scenario is designed to improve the user experience when interacting within the Agora platform. Such queries are expected to be generated as part of user-initiated requests while working within the workflow process associated with the Acceleration Service - for example, when new documents are added to the system and new notes are edited.

Data involved: Notes and documents related to the workflow process.

IV.2.2 Examples of using search scenarios

IV.2.2.1 Examples of using search scenarios for acceleration services integrated into Agora at level 0

Example 1: Searching for Acceleration Services that Facilitate Grant Applications

Addressed user needs: AFR 2: Matchmaking and Networking, AFR 3: Matchmaking for Funding Programs (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 1.1 or SS 1.2

Summary: A researcher wants to search for information on acceleration services that facilitate accessing available funding sources, building a research team, and submitting grant applications.

Description: In the basic case, queries will be submitted by users who have learned that Agora is a tool supporting the formation of project teams and grant applications but does not know the structure of the platform or how Agora can assist in this process. The user's queries will be very general and may include questions about Agora's capabilities in securing grant funding and building project teams.

As a result of their query, the user should receive information about acceleration services that can assist them in this process. The search should focus on acceleration services that contain information about project calls and descriptions of researchers, which can be used to determine whether they match the profile of the desired collaborators.

In a more advanced version, the system should support the user in identifying grant proposals being prepared on Agora that they could join. This process should be based on an analysis of the research profile of the user submitting the query to determine whether it aligns with the required researcher profile for the project.

Users: Researchers with diverse needs and limited knowledge of Agora's structure and the acceleration services available on the platform.

Searched data: Acceleration services catalog

Note: To search for acceleration services that facilitate grant applications, it is possible to search either metadata only (SS 1.1 Surface search in the acceleration services catalog) or metadata along with all data associated with a given acceleration service (SS 1.2 In-depth search in the acceleration services catalog) .

Example 2: Searching for Best Practices and Teaching Patterns

Addressed user needs: AS 1.5: Sharing Best Practices and Teaching Patterns (see II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora)

Search scenario: SS 1.2

Summary: A faculty member using the platform wants to find best practices or teaching patterns in his or her area of interest.

Description: Users who have heard that Agora offers best practices and teaching patterns will want to submit queries to gain access to relevant educational practices.

As a result of the query, the user should receive information about educational practices described in the acceleration service. The search should focus on services that explicitly describe educational practices that have proven effective in other educational contexts or at other universities.

Users: Users interested in educational practices

Searched data: Acceleration services catalog

Note: In the example, it is assumed that this includes only In-depth search in the acceleration services catalog (SS 1.2), as searching metadata and all collected data within acceleration services is the only way to retrieve efficiently static data contained in the Agora for acceleration services, such as the Acceleration Service Sharing Best Practices and Teaching Patterns (AS 1.5).

IV.2.2.2 Examples of using search scenarios for acceleration services integrated into Agora at level 1

Example 3: Searching for a project call

Addressed user needs: AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 2.1 or SS 2.2

Summary: The user wants to find project calls that meet the specified criteria.

Description: Searching for project calls is a basic scenario that allows users to identify funding opportunities. The ability to specify the criteria for searching for project calls is critical to identify funding opportunities that match their expertise and institutional goals. Professionals across disciplines need access to specific opportunities tailored to their fields.

Based on the user's query, the most relevant project calls from the catalog will be displayed, aligning with the specified criteria.

Users: Scientists and research management personnel

Searched data: Metadata and data stored in the data catalog, serving as an acceleration service that maintains information about project calls.

Note: The example includes queries from users with specific needs, i.e., experts in their field who know exactly what type of project they seek funding for. These queries are precise and directly related to the subject areas defined by the user.

Example 4: Searching for collaborators

Addressed user needs: AS 2.10: Comprehensive Funding Opportunities Directory (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 2.1 or SS 2.2

Summary: Assist the user in the search for partners for joint submission of EU or national project proposals.

Description: The role of the intelligent search is to allow Agora users to search for EU and national calls and to find partners among Agora users. The intelligent search should allow users to select partners from among those Agora users who meet the criteria set by the searcher and match the specifics of a given call. For this functionality to work, Agora needs to be provided with data on the scientific and organizational potential of Agora users, such as their scientific achievements, participation in previous grants, and the profile of the HEI where they work.

Based on the user's query, the most relevant researcher profiles from the catalog will be displayed, aligning with the specified criteria.

Users: Scientists and research management personnel

Searched data: Metadata and data stored in the data catalog constituting an acceleration service containing information about researchers' scientific profiles.

Note: The example concerns queries from users with specific needs, i.e., experts in their field who know exactly what profile of researchers they are looking for in their planned grant proposal. These queries are precise and directly related to the subject areas defined by the user.

Example 5: Searching for student seed funds

Addressed user needs: AFR 3: Matchmaking for Funding Programs (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 2.1 or SS 2.2

Summary: The user wants to find funding opportunities for incubation of a student project.

Description: Access to seed funding for students enables the development of innovative projects that can become viable solutions with scientific and market value. Early financial support allows students to experiment, test hypotheses, and build prototypes without the pressure of commercial success.

In response to the query, the user will receive a list of funding opportunities for student projects.

Users: The user can be a student or a student mentor who is an academic or business mentor.

Searched data: Metadata and data stored in the data catalog constituting an acceleration service containing information about student seed funds.

Note: In the simplest case, the example refers to queries where the user, knowing the project's topic, knows exactly which kind of funding sources they are looking for. However, it can also apply to more general questions, where the user, by providing a general profile of the student project, allows the system to suggest funding sources that cannot be directly used to finance the project in its current scope but would require modifications. This case applies to situations where a mentor determines that obtaining funding and implementing the project is more important than carrying it out within its originally defined scope.

Example 6: Searching for research infrastructure

Addressed user needs: AS 2.1: Research Infrastructure and TTO Directory (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 2.1 or SS 2.2

Summary: The user wants to find research infrastructure that meets the specified criteria.

Description: Access to appropriate research infrastructure allows for advanced experiments and analyses using the latest standards. Many research units have unused infrastructure that can be used, e.g., commercially by companies or by graduate students.

In response to the query, the user will receive a list of research infrastructure corresponding to their needs.

Users: A user looking for research infrastructure can be a researcher, student, or company representative.

Searched data: Metadata and data stored in the data catalog constituting an acceleration service containing information about research infrastructure.

Note: Searches can be performed only on the metadata of entities stored in the catalog (SS 2.1). However, a more desirable solution is one in which the user receives results after searching both the metadata and all the data stored in the catalog (SS 2.2). Therefore, when designing such acceleration services, it is essential to properly manage access permissions to ensure that users who are truly interested in searching for the research infrastructure they need have the appropriate set of permissions in the Agora (e.g., so that they do not have the default permissions assigned to users with the lowest level of access).

Example 7: Searching for internships, postdocs or other job opportunities

Addressed user needs: AS 2.3: Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 2.2

Summary: The user wants to find job-related opportunities that are relevant to his career development and meets the specified criteria.

Description: The ability to find internships, postdoctoral positions, and other job opportunities is critical to advancing a research career and enabling them to gain valuable experience in academia or industry. Facilitating access to job opportunities increases the mobility of researchers and students and strengthens networking, and helps them find a career path that matches their interests and skills. Administrative staff can take advantage of external internships and training programs to develop skills in managing research projects, academic finances, and other key areas in their home units.

In response to the query, the user will receive a list of internships, postdocs or other job opportunities corresponding to their needs.

Users: The user can be a researcher, doctoral student, student, or administrative employee of the academy.

Searched data: Metadata and data stored in the data catalog constituting an acceleration service containing information about internships, postdocs or other job opportunities.

Note: In the example, it is assumed that this includes only In-depth Search of the Data Catalog Constituting an Acceleration Service (SS 2.2), as it has been assumed that searching metadata and all collected data within acceleration services is the only way to retrieve efficiently data contained in the Agora for acceleration services, such as the Acceleration Service Database of internships, PhD positions and job offers (AS 2.3).

A possible variant of the described system behavior is initiating a search on user demand, along with a regular intelligent contextual search running in the background, which notifies the user of results (e.g., via email)

IV.2.2.3 Examples of using search scenarios for acceleration services integrated into Agora at level 2

Example 8: Ongoing search while preparing a grant application

Addressed user needs: AS 3.2: Integrated Application and Submission Tools (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 3.1

Summary: The user wants to prepare an application for a project call and monitor the submission process.

Description: The process of submitting a grant proposal involves multiple people, each taking on different roles. During the preparation process, documents are uploaded to the system and messages are exchanged between participants. A CRM system is used to manage the entire process, providing access to messages and prepared documents.

While working on the application, the user can ask Agora for information from the submitted documents or check the progress of the work by browsing the messages exchanged between users.

Users: Scientists and research management personnel who are working on submitting the application.

Searched data: Messages and documents gathered during the grant application process.

Note: It is considered that in response to a query, all messages and documents submitted as part of the grant application process will be searched.

IV.2.2.4 Examples of using search scenarios for acceleration services integrated into Agora at level 3 and 4

Example 9: Ongoing search while organizing the event

Addressed user needs: AS 4.2: Event Presentation and Registration (see *II.6 Appendix 1: Fulfilling User Needs in Agora*)

Search scenario: SS 4.1

Summary: The user wants to organize an event and manage registrations for it.

Description: The process of organizing an event includes publicizing the event on Agora and managing registrations. The organizer may need to access details about the event itself to see how it is presented to potential participants. They will also want to monitor the registration process, including who has already registered.

In response to specific queries, the user will receive information about the event, the attendees who have registered so far, and whether the registration criteria has been met (e.g., the number of users who have already registered).

Users: Event manager

Searched data: Information about the event and the database of registered participants.

Note: Since the data of registered users will be searched, it is necessary to address data access issues in compliance with GDPR.

IV.3 Intelligent Search Methods

The analysis of intelligent search and recommendations methods presented below was conducted in the context of searching for grant programs and researchers that could be potential collaborators in the process of preparing grant proposals. This is the central problem that has to be addressed by the intelligent search component of the Agora platform in order to foster the process of building international research teams which is the goal of Task 3.4 of the project. It is also a demanding task that is encompassed by search scenarios SS 2.1 and SS 2.2 and comprises simpler search problems that consider different kinds of entities such as project calls or researchers in separation.

IV.3.1 Matching methods

IV.3.1.1 Collaborative filtering

Collaborative filtering is a technique used in recommendation systems to predict a user's interests by collecting preferences from many users (Schafer et al., 2007). It assumes that if two users agree on one issue, they are likely to agree on others. Collaborative filtering can be used to match scientists with relevant project calls by leveraging information about their previous or preferred project applications.

Collaborative filtering does not require detailed information about the recommended items, thus it can be applied to a wide variety of project calls without imposing any requirements on the call structure or its level of detail. Taking into account that it can be used to model scientific interests solely on researcher preferences, it can foster international and interdisciplinary collaboration as it provides outcomes that cannot be reduced to the membership of the network of former professional contacts or constrained by institutional preferences.

However, it has to be taken into consideration that for researchers who do not specify their preferences or lack the history of successful grant applications the generated recommendations will be inadequate. This can affect researchers at the early stage of their career in a negative way while favoring senior scientists. Furthermore, well recognized grant programs with long history of applications will be recommended by collaborative filtering more frequently than domain specific calls in specialized fields of expertise although the latter can offer better opportunities for some researchers.

As a method that relies solely on preferences and does not assume any particular organization of research metadata or project call structure, collaborative filtering is a technique sustainable to the future changes in the organization of research-oriented data. In terms of deployment, storage and computational costs have to be carefully analyzed as they are dependent on the choice of underlying algorithms and technological solutions. Collaborative filtering algorithms that rely on matrix factorization require considerable amount of storage to be deployed and

their newer neural counterparts result in higher computational costs and may have limited practical value (Rendle et al., 2020).

IV.3.1.2 Content-based filtering

Content-based filtering is a recommendation technique that relies on feature extraction and preference modelling (Mooney and Roy, 2000). It assigns attributes to items and creates user profiles on the basis of past interactions. Using similarity metrics, the system recommends new items that closely match the user's preferences. Content-based filtering can be used to match scientists with project calls by analyzing the characteristics of researchers and past or preferred projects to generate personalized recommendations.

In contrast to collaborative filtering, it does not rely on preferences of other researchers, making it effective even for highly specialized domains with a small number of scientists. A properly designed collaborative filtering system can enable researchers to discover emerging project calls that align with their expertise.

However, as content-based filtering relies on individual preferences to recommend items similar to what the user has already seen, it can reduce exposure to diverse content. This may result in limited access to interdisciplinary opportunities in the process of building research teams for addressing project calls. Furthermore, as research interests evolve in time, scientists may be provided with offers that do not fulfill their current preferences, if their profiles are not actual.

Considering that content-based filtering relies on features extracted from the items to be recommended, missing or incorrectly labeled metadata can lead to inaccurate results. This is an important issue in case of an intelligent search component for Agora as metadata that comes from diverse acceleration services provided by the Agora platform can vary in quality, recency and granularity.

Long-term operation and scaling of a content-based filtering system can be easier than its collaborative filtering counterpart since it does not require storage and updating large user interaction matrices. However, sustainable deployment of content-based filtering in the Agora platform requires strategy for maintaining actuality of metadata to prevent divergence between current preferences of scientists and project calls being offered via acceleration services.

IV.3.1.3 Hybrid approaches

Hybrid approaches (e.g. Gomez-Uribe and Hunt, 2016) which dominate industrial settings combine collaborative and content-based filtering. The goal of hybrid techniques is to improve recommendation accuracy by reducing the over-specialization of content-based methods and lowering the impact of popular but non-specific recommendations yielded by collaborative filtering.

While hybrid methods share advantages of collaborative and content-based algorithms and as such should be preferred, in terms of sustainability they introduce additional challenges. Hybrid architectures require more complex implementations. They generate higher computational costs and are more difficult to diagnose in case of unsatisfied or incorrect results.

IV.3.2 Retrieval methods

IV.3.2.1 Keyword search

Keyword search is a technique used to retrieve information based on exact or partial matches between terms specified in the user query and the documents indexed in the content repository.

The results of keyword search are easy to interpret and the path that leads to the particular search outcome is easy to follow. It does not require specialized training on the user side. Keyword search works well with large repositories of documents and is computationally cost-effective, if compared to more advanced search solutions that rely on AI-driven methods. Its main limitation is the lack of the ability to understand context and interpret meaning of the user query. This may easily lead to the result that encompasses irrelevant documents or misses the relevant ones.

In terms of fostering the process of forming international research teams, the main advantage of keyword search is the ability to specify precise filtering conditions that obey domain terminology that is prevalent in the given field of research. It also enables users to identify researchers that are affiliated with a particular institution or work in a specific country. However, if the terminology in a particular area of research is inconsistent, the lack of information about associations between semantically related terms will lead to missing results.

IV.3.2.2 Semantic search

Semantic search is a search technique that retrieves results based on meaning rather than exact keyword matches. It uses vector embeddings which are dense, numerical representations of documents and queries to measure their semantic similarity (cf. Reimers, and Gurevych, 2019). Unlike keyword search, it can recognize synonyms and paraphrases, improving retrieval accuracy.

Searching for semantically related terms that are described differently in various domains instead of relying on keyword matching facilitates finding relevant work across various disciplines. This is a desired feature as matching scientists that work on similar topics is a key usage scenario for intelligent search in the Agora platform.

It has to be taken into account that semantic search can also lead to irrelevant results, if the goal of the user is to retrieve data that strictly conform to the terminology being used in a specific domain. Semantic search also generates significant computational costs and results in slower search performance for large datasets than keyword-based methods.

From a sustainability perspective, one has to consider if vector embeddings are computed locally or provided via API from an external vendor. If the external vendor is considered the long-term availability of the service and price fluctuations are major risk factors that have to be carefully analyzed. Furthermore, the compliance of the service hosted by the external vendor with AI Act and GDPR has to be checked before the intelligent search system is deployed as a part of the Agora platform (see Section 4 Regulatory considerations). If vector embeddings are going to be stored and/or generated locally, the issue of selecting an appropriate storage technology is a key factor for the sustainability of the intelligent search in the Agora platform. While there are several relatively new database products that provide dedicated storage solutions for vector embeddings, their long-term availability and maintenance perspectives remain uncertain.

IV.3.2.3 Retrieval Augmented Generation

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is a hybrid system that combines an information retrieval component with a generative model to enhance response accuracy and relevance (Lewis et al., 2020). Instead of relying solely on a large language model for answering queries, RAG retrieves relevant information from external sources before generating the response. The retrieval component ensures that responses are grounded in factual, externally sourced information, reducing the risk of hallucinations which are a common problem in generative models. As a RAG-based system employs a generative model to formulate the final answer, it can provide references to the sources it used, enabling users to verify the origins of the information provided.

RAG allows to combine both unstructured and structured sources of information, which is a significant advantage for building the intelligent search component for the Agora platform, as information required to accelerate international collaboration is distributed among sources that vary in the scope of structuring the information content - ranging from text sources, such as academic papers, through semi-structural data sources, such as personal profiles in expert databases, to knowledge databases that follow well-defined metadata schemes, such as infrastructure catalogues.

However, the risk of amplifying biases and inaccuracies of the retrieved data by the generative component of RAG has to be taken into consideration when deciding to integrate it into the Agora platform. A risk that is not present in simpler search architectures which can retrieve biases or inaccurate data from the sources but are not able to amplify these issues further.

In terms of sustainability the deployment strategy is a major risk factor as RAG is a hybrid architecture with complex implementation that requires both a retrieval component and an AI

model to be maintained. Efficient realization of an internal deployment requires significant computational resources including GPU-powered systems. If external deployment is considered, one has to take into account the long-term availability of the service and the exposure to price increases.

IV.4 Regulatory considerations

The intelligent search component of the Agora platform as any AI system to be put into service in the European Union has to conform to the legal requirements of the European Parliament and of the Council. As *Regulation (EU) 2024/1689* of the European Parliament and of the Council (the AI Act) places specific requirements and obligations for operators of **high-risk AI systems, general purpose AI models and general purpose AI models with systemic risk**, it is necessary to check, if the model of intelligent search selected for deployment inside Agora falls under any of these categories.

In accordance with *Article 6: Classification Rules for High-Risk AI Systems, paragraph 2* of the AI Act and the corresponding Annex III under high-risk AI systems category fall "AI systems intended to be used for the recruitment or selection of natural persons, in particular to place targeted job advertisements, to analyze and filter job applications, and to evaluate candidates;(Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, Annex III paragraph 4 (a)). Thus, for example, if an intelligent search component of the Agora platform provides the capability for selecting individual collaborators for projects that result in the change of their employment status, then the intelligent search component should be considered a **high-risk AI system** and conform to the obligations imposed by Chapter III of the AI Act which in Article 26 obligates deployers of high-risk AI systems to: implement technical and organization measures to ensure that they are used in accordance with the provided instructions (paragraph 1), assign human oversight to qualified persons (paragraph 2), ensure that input data is relevant and representative (paragraph 4), monitor the operation of the system (paragraph 5), preserve the automatically generated logs (paragraph 6), inform the workers (paragraph 7), conduct data protection impact assessment (paragraph 9) and inform natural persons that they are subject to the use of the high-risk AI system (paragraph 11). This is a major challenge for Agora, but also an opportunity for the growth of the platform, if the obligations are met.

Besides the considerations that stem from the potential use cases of the intelligent search in the Agora platform, one also has to take into account the consequences of choosing certain AI technologies. As stated in *Recital 100* of the AI Act systems that integrate general-purpose AI models that are capable of serving a variety of purposes should be considered general-purpose AI systems. Chapter V of the AI Act imposes multiple responsibilities on the providers of general-purpose AI models with additional obligations being imposed on the providers general-purpose AI models with systemic risk distinguished in *Article 51*. Thus, if the architecture of the intelligent search engine to be integrated into the Agora platform implies the use of a **general-purpose AI model** (e.g. RAG architecture discussed in Section 2), then it is necessary to verify if the employed model is a **general-purpose AI model with systemic risk**,

and if the provider of the model complies with the regulatory obligations imposed by Chapter V of the AI Act. In view of Chapter V, paragraph 1 (b), the provider of Agora as a provider of an AI system who intends to integrate the general-purpose AI model should be supplied with actual and comprehensive documentation by the provider of the general-purpose AI model. The documentation has to satisfy the requirements imposed by Annex XII of the AI Act. In particular, the information provided should encompass the number of parameters (Annex XII, paragraph 1 (f)) of the model which at the time of writing is not disclosed by major providers of general-purpose AI models.

IV.5 Recommendations

In view of the requirements analysis conducted in Section 2, analysis of existing intelligent search methods presented in Section 3 and regulatory considerations discussed in Section 4, we propose the following set of recommendations that should be met by the intelligent search engine being developed.

Recommendation 1: Provide search functions through an AI assistant

Taking into consideration that Agora is supposed to provide access to heterogeneous acceleration services that differ in the kind, scope and volume of collected data and that the services themselves vary in access rules, intended users and the level of integration with the Agora platform, we recommend to offer the search capabilities of the platform via a specialized AI assistant that follows RAG architecture. While the other intelligent search methods discussed in Section 3 can be employed to realize some of the usage scenarios presented in Section 2, only the introduction of a conversational interface offered by the AI assistant ensures uniform access to all the search capabilities that stem from the proposed scenarios without the need for developing elaborate training procedures for HEI staff.

Due to the rapid progress in the field of artificial intelligence, state-of-the-art retrieval techniques can become obsolete in a short period of time; therefore, we refrain from suggesting one specific search technique or machine learning model to be implemented. From the sustainability perspective, it is more important to indicate non-functional requirements that the intelligent search component of the Agora platform should satisfy, rather than to suggest a particular AI model for deployment.

Recital 27 of the AI Act lists seven principles for trustworthy and ethically sound AI developed by the high-level expert group on artificial intelligence (AI HLEG) of the European Commission:

1. human agency and oversight;
2. technical robustness and safety;
3. privacy and data governance;
4. transparency;
5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness;

6. societal and environmental well-being;
7. accountability.

Regardless of having the status of a high-risk AI system or being built with the use of a general-purpose AI model with systemic risk (cf. Section 4 Regulatory Considerations), the intelligent search component of the Agora platform being an AI system deployed in the European Union should follow the aforementioned principles.

While human agency (1) is the consequence of the problem setting in the case of intelligent search, because the decisions enacted on the basis of the search results are the sole responsibility of the Agora platform users, the other principles to be preserved require organizational and technical efforts that we recommend below.

Recommendation 2: Implement standard practices imposed by GDPR

To ensure privacy and data governance (3) we recommend to follow standard practices imposed by General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

Recommendation 3: Collect extensive usage logs

For safety (2), transparency (4) and accountability (7), we postulate to collect usage logs that encompass search queries, results being returned, timestamps, fingerprints of all AI models utilized in the process of executing the user query and GDPR-compliant user data. This is an obligatory practice for high-risk AI systems (Article 26, paragraph 6 of the AI Act). However taking into consideration the effectiveness of log analysis for quality control, detection of security accidents and determining the responsibility of natural and artificial agents in the search process, it is beneficial to implement usage logs even in case of AI systems that present moderate risk only.

Recommendation 4: Implement periodic red-teaming

Red-teaming refers to the practice of testing the system under study by simulating attacks, probing weaknesses and identifying vulnerabilities. If a general-purpose AI model with systemic-risk is employed to implement the intelligent search component, then to reduce safety risks (2) extensive red-teaming with the use of domain-specific data should be performed with the goal of detecting hallucinations, misinformation and harmful content. Furthermore, specific requirements placed by the stakeholders and owners of the acceleration services with regard to copyright and access rights and the organization of the access rights in the Agora platform itself (see *Part III: Schema of access rights for users in the created system*; chapter III.3.2 Recommendations for access authorization design) have to be taken into consideration while penetration tests are executed to minimize the risk of revealing unauthorized data.

Recommendation 5: Quantify environmental impact of search

While societal impact (6) is a concern that should be analyzed at the system-wide level with intelligent search being considered one of many building blocks of the Agora platform, the environmental impact and in particular carbon footprint of the implemented search solution should be assessed.

Recommendation 6: Develop a domain-specific benchmark

To guarantee technical robustness (2) of the implemented search solution, standard performance measures adopted in the industry and research practice such as Precision@K, Recall@K, mean average precision, and discounted cumulative gain (Järvelin and Kekäläinen, 2002) should be tracked across revisions. For the purpose of evaluation, we recommend to develop a domain-specific dataset and an automatic benchmark that implements the usage scenarios discussed in Section 2 and performs multi-criteria assessment of the search component to be integrated into the Agora platform across revisions, comparing alternative search methods and streamline detection of common problems that arise from the use of general-purpose AI models such as hallucinations and generation of harmful content.

Recommendation 7: Assess fairness

Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness (5) are key concerns that have to be addressed in the intelligent search engine which aims to streamline collaboration across scientists and institutions on the basis of qualifications and competences. To minimize the impact of non-merit criteria on the search results, we postulate making the measurement of fairness (Barocas et al. 2023) an integral part of the proposed benchmark.

III.6 References

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